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Reading Food in Literature,
the Arts and across the Media

Cultural Intertexts

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Editor's Note

The 2024 issue of *Cultural Intertexts* focuses on representations and translations of food, advancing multiple evaluations and reading grids. The volume includes a guest section of articles collected by scholars from the University of Bucharest – “Reading Food in Literature, the Arts and across the Media” – in partnership with the editing team at “Dunarea de Jos” University of Galati, and hosts contributions on “Translating Food”.

Part one sheds light on the poetics and politics of cultural texts which encode images of food and aliment various decodings. The corpus is generous, including: diaspora women's writing; feminist discourse; food blogs; newspaper articles; individual novels, screenplays, films, poems, paintings. The findings gravitate towards the following conclusions: food performativity is both constitutive and reflective of transnational identity construction (Sima Aghazadeh); counter cookbooks have the potential to mobilize revolutionary culinary spaces (Majda Atieh and Batoul Deeb); food is a symbolic medium whereby female identity is built and negotiated (Nicolae Bobaru); food blogs add to the (virtual) food literature accompanying migration (Betty Chukwu and Robin Oakley); food plays a significant role at different junctures of a novel's narrative pattern (Antony Hoyte-West); explorations of hunger (as starvation and insatiable craving) reveal the gap between classes (Lorena-Clara Mihăeș); fruit imagery supports existential questioning, spiritual emptiness and societal critique (Monica Manolachi); food aesthetics expresses societal concerns, class distinctions, moral lessons, and cultural exchanges (Lidia Mihaela Necula); real and figurative hunger are recurrent themes in the literature covering the horrors of the Holocaust (Cristina Mihaela Nistor); the theme of striving for food reflects the struggle for justice (Raluca Ștefania Pelin); banquet menus transcend culinary functions, conveying broader political and societal messages (Adriana Soholodeanu); investigations of veganism underpin exploration of ethics and the interconnectedness of all living things (Alin Temeliescu).

Part two brings forth culturally-oriented translation and interpretation efforts aimed at clarifying food related issues and their journey across temporal and spatial frontiers. It offers incursions into the challenges of rendering contemporary local textures and tastes, enriching and re-appropriating older food-related terminology, investigating gastronomic culturemes in successive translations into a minority language. The case studies include Muamer

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Spahic's cookbook *The Bosnian Cuisine* (2016), Jonathan Grimwood's novel *The Last Banquet* (2013) set in late 18th century France and Jane Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* (1813; trans. into Romanian 1943, 1968, 1992, 2004, 2006, 2011, 2012, 2016, 2017).

The editors of *Cultural Intertexts* renew their gratitude towards reviewers, contributors and partners, acknowledging their valuable input and commitment to the publication of the series.

Michaela Praisler

PART I

Reading Food in Literature, the Arts and across the Media

Collected and edited by Monica Manolachi and
Lorena Mihăeş (University of Bucharest)

Food Performativity and Transnational Identity in Selected Diasporic Women's Writings

Sima AGHAZADEH*

Abstract

Studying the intersection of food and identity is essential, especially when it interlaces with diasporic cultures. Through the process of immigration and acculturation, food acquires new shapes, meanings and accents, influencing, informing and even transforming our relationship with the world. Incorporating concepts from diasporic discourse such as culinary citizenship, third space and performativity, this paper demonstrates how the use of food narratives and practices in literary works plays a vital performative role in conveying the experiences of individuals living away from home, dealing with displacement and navigating their evolving transnational identities. Food is a cultural zone where different identity determinants intersect and engage in debate. This paper explores how some women writers from different diasporas use food for two primary functions: 1. to negotiate their female characters' identity in displacement and produce the possibility of replacement, all while navigating the complexities of preserving or reconstructing their cultural identity; and more critically; 2. to enlighten their intended readers about the existing challenges, pains, prejudices and tensions in the assimilation process. In this context, food strategically performs as a discursive and multilayered agent, establishing diversity awareness, challenging exclusionary attitudes and stimulating cross-cultural interactions. Food performativity is both constitutive and reflective of transnational identity construction across political borders – a point not to end here but to begin.

Keywords: *food narratives, diaspora literature, food performativity, food and identity, transnational identity*

Introduction

One thing is certain about food: it has never been just about sustenance (Eagleton 1998). Beyond its basic function, food serves as a powerful signifier, representing deeper emotional and psychological imagery as well as broader personal and cultural expressions (Mannur 2010). In our transnational world, marked by rapid migration and mobility, food has become an even more prominent personal and political marker, especially in literary studies, where “food has long served as a cultural marker of complex and oft-conflicting desires, affiliations and identities” (Coghlan 2020: 1). Recent scholarship has underscored the significance of studying the intersection of food and culture, particularly in the context of diasporic communities (Ho 2005; Xu 2008; Mannur 2010; Dalessio 2012). Through the process of immigration, food takes

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on new forms, meanings and nuances, shaping and transforming our relationship with the environment and identity determinants such as race, class and gender. Critics like Wong (1993, 2000), Ho (2005), Xu (2008), Dalessio (2012) and Mannur (2010) have highlighted the role of culinary narratives in diasporic literature, particularly within various ethnic-Asian American communities, and explored its connection to identity formation and representation. In this context, food exerts discursive power and agency, facilitating cultural exchange and challenging the notion of a singular, fixed identity, while also revealing its potential for transformation.

Food is performative in that it functions as a relational construct, continuously and dynamically shaped by the subjective practices that imbue it with meaning. This idea aligns with the theory of Judith Butler (2006) about “gender performativity”, where she argues that gender is performative because it is socially, culturally and politically constructed and enacted through repeated behaviours assigned to male and female categories. Similarly, food is performative, conveying and reinforcing specific messages within a social network while reflecting identity conflicts – particularly at the intersections of gender, race, class and more – often most evident in immigrant kitchens (Halloran 2016).

In its broader sense, diaspora refers to individuals of a particular culture or ethnicity who have voluntarily or forcibly relocated to different geographical regions (Grossman 2018; Cohen 2022). Diasporic discourse is part of an ongoing transnational network characterised by continuous negotiation between roots and routes. People in the diaspora use various narratives and strategies to navigate the challenges of assimilation in a new homeland while maintaining a nostalgic connection to their original one (or an imagined homeland) (Brah 1996). Among the shared traditions of a diaspora, food and culinary preferences have emerged as significant narratives accompanying people, practices and cultures, and telling their stories as they move across the globe (Halloran 2016). Food narratives play a crucial performative role in conveying the experiences of individuals living away from home, dealing with displacement and navigating their evolving identities in a new land. These narratives serve as cultural zones where different identity determinants intersect and engage in dialogue. This perspective raises questions at the intersection of food, culture, migration, home and identity – concepts that are constantly evolving and in flux.

Building on these questions and with diaspora as its backdrop, this paper examines how some women writers use food narratives to navigate their female characters’ identities in displacement, creating the possibility of transformation (Ingold 2015). These writers, hailing from different diasporas, share two key objectives: first, to portray their immigrant characters as “others” who grapple with the complexities of cultural identity through their food

choices and preparation, while managing the tensions between assimilation and cultural preservation; and second, to use food narratives to inform and educate their readers about the challenges, pains and prejudices faced by immigrants and minorities in their host countries (Ho 2005; Xu 2008; Mannur 2010). Thus, food serves as more than just a literary metaphor or symbol; it acts as a medium with productive and transformative power, capable of bridging differences and fostering a sense of connection. As Anita Mannur's concept of "culinary citizenship" suggests (2010: 29), food not only represents but also shapes identity and culture. Mannur situates her discussion of food and identity within the complex intersections of class, ethnicity, sexuality and gender, explaining how these factors influence how South Asians articulate their experiences of preparing and consuming food as expressions of their ethnic and diasporic lives.

Similarly, writers from various diasporas view food and culinary discourse as one of the safest and most profound ways to express their emotions and assert their identities in a new environment. In transnational literature, food narratives illustrate the blending of cultures by portraying characters who navigate the tension between recreating their ethnic dishes and incorporating new cuisines (Ristaino and Li 2022). When closely examining stories of women immigrants, two common reactions emerge. Some characters struggle with the challenges of assimilation and, in response, seek to maintain a strong connection to their homeland through food. These narratives often recount the bitter experiences of displacement, highlighting the constant conflict between preserving ethnic cuisine and confronting the Western antithesis, where attempts at harmonious fusion and blending of flavors often fail. Conversely, other characters adopt a more strategic approach to adaptation and assimilation, where food serves as a casual and safe medium for cultural exchange, connecting immigrants with the mainstream audience. In this context, the fusion of cuisines and ingredients becomes a transformative strategy for survival and inclusion. This blending of migrant and Western elements creates a hybrid identity, symbolized by a dish where dual or multiple homes merge, resulting in a transnational identity (Sherman 2020). The following section presents the voices of various diasporic women and their efforts to assimilate into American society through their culinary practices.

Different voices and tastes from the diaspora

Jhumpa Lahiri's stories provide excellent examples of the two reactions previously mentioned. She writes about her Indian-Bengali female characters and their deep connection to food in America, where they constantly grapple with preserving their cultural identity while adapting to a new environment and navigating their complex, often ambivalent positions. Food becomes a way for these characters to express their gendered, racialized and class-based

identities in the hope of finding connection and belonging in their new home. However, it can also highlight feelings of isolation, difference and intolerance. In her acclaimed novel *The Namesake* (2003), the story begins with Ashima Ganguli attempting to recreate the taste of her favorite Indian snack. For Ashima, this snack represents more than just a craving—it is an expression of her nostalgia, homesickness and desire to revive lost memories of home. Yet, in the diaspora, replicating authentic national or ethnic dishes is nearly impossible due to the unavailability of traditional ingredients. As a result, authenticity is expressed through the continuous recreation and reinvention of dishes with whatever ingredients are accessible, allowing individuals to assert their identities. As the novel progresses, Ashima gradually overcomes her sense of alienation, realizing that surviving in Western society requires finding a balance between two cultures—a journey that aligns with the meaning of her name, Ashima, which signifies “limitless, without borders” (26). She evolves by embracing aspects of the American lifestyle while maintaining a connection to her roots, ultimately embodying a transnational identity that is “without borders, without a home of her own, a resident everywhere and nowhere” (276). Ashima’s culinary hybridization becomes a form of “culinary citizenship” as she adapts to cooking familiar dishes using unfamiliar ingredients, such as making *halwa* from cream of wheat, *sandesh* from ricotta cheese (276) and roasting a Thanksgiving turkey seasoned with garlic, cumin and cayenne (64).

Similarly, Mrs. Sen, one of the main characters in Lahiri’s short story collection *Interpreter of Maladies* (2000), expresses her struggles with cultural assimilation and loneliness through her food preparation. She, too, longs to recreate the tastes of home, hoping to be transported back in time and place and to experience the comfort associated with these familiar flavors. Lahiri meticulously describes the effort Mrs. Sen puts into her cooking, revealing the character’s internal conflict and the weight of gendered and racialized expectations she carries. Through detailed descriptions of Mrs. Sen’s kitchenware and cooking practices, Lahiri emphasizes how the character’s racialized identity and unique gendered agency—often misunderstood—are expressed. Unlike Ashima, Mrs. Sen is unable to adapt to her new environment. Her disorientation in her new home is symbolized by her obsession with obtaining a specific type of fish to prepare her Bengali dish and her struggle to learn to drive. She clings to the traditions and customs of her homeland through the way she cooks, dresses and interacts with her husband. Mrs. Sen might be viewed as “a snapshot of a woman in the early years of her life as a struggling immigrant” (Madhuparna 2006: 195), with the potential for gradual change towards assimilation and hybridity, similar to what we see in Ashima. By exploring the complexities and emotional conflicts tied to food preparation, Lahiri seeks to dismantle stereotypes and help her Western readers understand

the confusion and sense of disconnection that come with being caught “in-between” (Bhabha 1994), offering a nuanced portrayal of the realities faced by immigrant women [1].

In her memoirs, *The Language of Baklava* (2005) and *Life Without a Recipe: A Memoir of Food and Family* (2017), the Arab-American novelist Diana Abu-Jaber records her experience as a second-generation immigrant in America and her struggle to earn the approval of both sides of family members (her Arab father and European mother) through cooking and eating. She uses the language of food to explore her cultural identity and her aspiration to integrate into American society. By combining traditional recipes with personal stories, she addresses her emotional and moral needs, noting on the first page of the “Foreword” that: “Food always turned out to be about something much larger: grace, difference, faith and love.” (1)

Diana shows the cultural clash through the contrasting culinary traditions of her family. Her German grandmother’s methodical baking, with its emphasis on precision and adherence to rules, contrasts sharply with her Jordanian father’s passion for spices and improvisation. These differences not only reflect the emotional trauma influencing her but also the development of her fluid and expressive “culinary citizenship”. In her recollections of home and family and her journey toward self-discovery, food preparation becomes a platform where her marginalized Jordanian father in America can assert his masculinity and cultural heritage, while her mother’s resistance is expressed through her refusal to partake in these meals. Diana strategically incorporates elements from both culinary traditions, creating a unique blended cuisine that represents her transnational identity – a concept that defies rigid definitions, as suggested by the title of her second memoir.

The recipes serve to appropriate and embody the traditions and values they represent, reflecting Abu-Jaber’s efforts to adapt to contemporary social and personal circumstances in America. Simultaneously, she reflects on the inherent appeal for American readers in immigrant stories that depict the process of reshaping their identities under the pressures of assimilation:

I believe the immigrant’s story is compelling to us because it is so consciously undertaken. The immigrant compresses time and space- starting out in one country and then very deliberately starting again, a little later, in another. It’s a sort of fantasy- to have the chance to recreate yourself. But it’s also a nightmare, because so much is lost. (2005: 1)

What Abu-Jaber tries to highlight in retelling stories of her family is that, in practice, the people of the host country fail to recognize that, no matter how hard the immigrants try to be assimilated and included, they are still seen as “perennial outsiders... due to their accent, name, skin colour, or style of dress” (Halloran 2016: 7). Abu-Jaber recalls a family picnic in the front yard of their

home in Syracuse, which provokes a discriminatory reaction from their non-immigrant neighbours. On the school bus, one of Diana's schoolmates tells her that eating in the front yard is unacceptable:

My parents saw you out there the other night. I heard them talking with the neighbours. They said it was an "unholy disgrace". See, okay, the thing is, you better know that in this country nobody eats in the front yard. Really. Nobody... If your family doesn't know how to behave, my parents will have to find out about getting you out of this neighbourhood. (2005: 82)

In response, the diverse immigrant families in the neighborhood organize a larger front-yard picnic and invite their white American neighbors to sample international cuisine. Diana humorously renames her father's grilled chicken recipe from that event as "Distract the Neighbours Grilled Chicken" and describes it as a "delightful, simple dish that will fill the neighborhood with a gorgeous scent" (2005: 79). Beyond using food as a personal bridge between contrasting cultures and traditions, Abu-Jaber offers her recipe as a means of partial belonging, encouraging readers to view the world through a new perspective and to foster understanding, connection and empathy towards cultural diversity. Through her culinary sign system, Diana redefines her hybrid identity, demonstrating how the personal can assert agency in the political realm and challenge marginalization. She constructs and embraces her complex transnational identity, reflected in the rich layers of passions and contradictions surrounding food, akin to the diverse flavors and aromas of baklava (Halloran 2016).

Like Abu-Jaber, Iranian women in the diaspora use food strategically to counteract negative media stereotypes in the West and, more importantly, to foster a sense of inclusion. They blend recipes and food stories with their personal narratives, weaving together themes of migration, nostalgia and cultural identity. Unlike other Asian diasporic writings, Iranian women writers (and Middle Eastern writers more broadly) aim to present a more positive image of their original culture to Western audiences, especially in the wake of 9/11. This effort is strategic, focusing less on personal assimilation struggles – as seen in Mrs. Sen's character – and more on addressing the political challenges of negative Middle Eastern portrayals in the West. The strained relations between Iran and the US since 1979, the post-9/11 designation of Iran as part of an "axis of evil", debates over Iran's nuclear program and a deep emotional nostalgia for a lost homeland following the 1979 Islamic Revolution all influence the life stories of Iranian women in their new home [2] (Fotouhi 2015; Naghibi 2009, 2016).

In her two memoirs, *Funny in Farsi: A Memoir of Growing Up Iranian in America* (2003) and *Laughing Without an Accent: Adventures of a Global Citizen* (2008), Firoozeh Dumas uses humor to explore cultural differences and the

challenges of adapting to American life through food. She provides a dual perspective of a girl navigating between two cultures, learning to understand and mediate between them. In *Funny in Farsi*, Dumas shares amusing anecdotes about her family's encounters with American cuisine and their confusion over fast food, hot dogs and bologna, often leading to funny and heartwarming moments [3]. She describes her family's attempt to assimilate by blending Iranian flavors [4] into their Thanksgiving celebration, illustrating their efforts to preserve their cultural heritage while also embracing American traditions. Dumas uses these humorous stories to showcase Iranians' ability to adapt and their desire to assimilate under challenging circumstances, suggesting that sharing food and laughter are effective ways to build trust and bridge cultural differences.

Rhetorically, Dumas (2003) uses food and humor as a means to lightly critique serious political tensions or threats while engaging her American readers. With a playful tone, she addresses the sources of prejudice and hostility she and her family have encountered in broader American culture. As she writes:

With each passing day, palpable hatred grew among many Americans, hatred not just of the hostage takers but of all Iranians. The media didn't help. We opened our local paper one day to the screaming headline "Iranian Robs Grocery Store". Iran has as many fruits and nuts as the next country, but it seemed as if every lowlife who happened to be Iranian was now getting his fifteen minutes of fame. Vendors started selling T-shirts and bumper stickers that said "Iranians Go Home" and "Wanted: Iranians for Target Practice". Crimes against Iranians increased. People would hear my mother's thick accent and ask us, "Where are you from?" They weren't looking for a recipe for stuffed grape leaves. Many Iranians suddenly became Turkish, Russian, or French. (117)

This is one of many instances where Dumas (2003) employs humor to address issues she cannot confront directly. Through her storytelling, she invites her audience to understand what it means to reconstruct herself from a demonized identity as an Iranian immigrant in America. For example, when she writes, "I believe peace in the Middle East could be achieved if the various leaders held their discussions in front of a giant bowl of Persian ice cream, each leader with his own silver spoon. Political differences would melt with every mouthful" (75), she emphasizes that food can play an active role in uniting people and reminding them of their shared humanity. At the same time, she appeals to American readers to accept her for who she truly is, countering Western misconceptions. By transforming a bowl of saffron ice cream into a symbol of cross-cultural diplomacy, Dumas uses food as a platform for negotiation and a performance to encourage a more nuanced understanding of transnational identity. Her works are critically acclaimed for introducing American

audiences to the more humane, sweet and humorous facets of Iranian culture, highlighting the challenges of being an Iranian immigrant and embracing a hybrid identity.

Among various ethnic communities in the diaspora, Chinese (and Asians more broadly) are often the most persistently racialized through their food and eating habits (Pazo 2016; Liu 2022). In the Chinese diaspora, food reflects complex multi-generational experiences, family or communal bonds, a sense of group identity and cohesion, as well as cultural heritage, rituals, nostalgia and stories of displacement. Diasporic writers like Amy Tan and Leslie Li use food as a medium to depict the cultural and generational clashes between first-generation immigrant mothers and their second-generation daughters in America. However, like other diasporic writers, they also aim to provide a more nuanced and less stereotyped view of Chinese experiences, engaging Western readers with relevant social and cultural issues while fostering greater interest and empathy.

In her seminal novels *The Joy Luck Club* (1989) and *The Kitchen God's Wife* (1993), Amy Tan depicts mothers who use food and storytelling to pass down Chinese traditions and connect with their American-born daughters. Food in Tan's novels symbolises the mothers' gendered and racialized identities, their competence, knowledge, power and love: "That's the way Chinese mothers show they love their children, not through hugs and kisses but with stern offerings of steamed dumplings, duck's gizzards and crab." (1989: 202) At the same time, it reflects the American-born daughters' complex cultural identities. These second-generation children are often drawn to American-coded foods due to the pressure to conform to the broader American social context. They face a constant struggle with the cultural dissonance between their two worlds and a desire to "belong to the cultural terrain of the United States and to rid [their] body of the stigma associated with otherness" (Mannur 2010: 153).

The Kitchen God's Wife is rich with scenes of celebratory dinners, feasts and meals in America, as narrated by Winnie, the Chinese immigrant mother, and Pearl, her American-born daughter. Pearl's commentary on food highlights the generational cultural conflicts, while Winnie's food narratives aim to bridge this divide. Winnie intertwines her experiences in China and her later life in America with food stories, helping her daughter understand the hardships she faced in both countries. As Huntley (1998) notes, "as the novel continues to follow Weili through her transition from a young girl to a young wife, food outlines the cultural and geographical contexts of her life" (93). Typically, first-generation immigrants often resist the culinary styles and eating habits of their new country. For instance, Winnie tries American food for the first time at a party:

I tried them all, three kinds of taste. The first was a soft dumpling, named for its colour, brownie – so sweet it made my teeth ache. The second was the necklace

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food lining the tree, popcorn. It was very dry and scratchy, and my mouth watered, trying to find a flavour. And then I ate a little cracker with something awful on top. Hula ate one too, thinking mine had been rotten by mistake. No mistake. That was the first time we ever ate cheese. (385-86)

On the other hand, traditional Chinese food is often not favoured by American-born daughters. When Winnie attempts to teach Pearl how to cook, Pearl responds: "It's boring. Too much trouble. I'd rather eat McDonald's hamburgers instead." (137) Driven by a desire to assimilate into mainstream American culture, the second generation exhibits a pronounced "food shame" [5] regarding their traditional dishes and a strong attraction to Western foods. In this context, Chinese food is depicted as a sporadic source of ethnic anxiety for the daughters.

However, in Winnie's stories of war, hunger, poverty, homelessness, abuse and grief, food acts as a crucial agent for fostering connections among family and friends, creating "a third space of enunciation" (Bhabha 1994: 37) where two cultures can intersect and negotiate. Bhabha (1994) describes this third space as a realm where multiple cultures interact, leading to the emergence of new identities. In this hybrid space, Winnie is able to find herself and reconcile with her daughter (Liu 2022). This reconciliation is facilitated through the performativity of food images, which include detailed accounts of food shopping, preparation, cooking and consumption. The depiction of Chinese New Year and the significance of various food items—reflecting their shape, taste and symbolism—serves as an example of cultural transfer that Winnie aims to share with her daughter, similar to the mothers in *The Joy Luck Club*. Tan uses food not only as a narrative device to advance the plot but also as a means to explore the depth and complexity of the characters' experiences. It becomes a powerful tool for illustrating their cultural identity and the challenges of preserving it in a new environment. Additionally, Tan highlights the diverse nature of the immigrant experience and the different ways each generation navigates towards their Asian-American identity. Food serves as a link between past and present, tradition and modernity, and mother and daughter in both novels.

In the foreword to her memoir, *Daughters of Heaven: A Memoir with Earthly Recipes* (2005), Leslie Li states: "Food—its cultivation, preparation, the people who cook it, those who consume it, the rituals surrounding it and the events that demand its abundant presence—is the core of this book, much like rice and vegetables are fundamental to any Chinese meal." (xiv) The memoir is richly infused with vivid food imagery and recipes, making it more culinary focused compared to Tan's novels. It offers a profound exploration of Leslie's experiences as a Chinese American girl growing up in the Bronx, where she struggled with "shame to be Chinese" (12) and worked to conceal her ethnicity from her peers. Despite these challenges, her journey of self-discovery leads to

a reconciliation with her hybrid identity. The rituals and foods of Chinese New Year help Leslie bridge the gap between her family's experiences and her cultural identity. She notes that the good wishes are not just spoken by guests but are also conveyed through the food they eat:

“Happiness to everyone” wasn’t said but served in the form of shark’s fin soup. Then came “Happy Spring Festival”, also unspoken but more than implied in the shape of spring rolls. [...] It preceded a concoction made with dried oysters, or *haosi*—a word that means “something good is bound to happen”—black mushrooms, *bok choy* and *fat choy*, a black hairlike seaweed whose auspicious name not only signifies wealth but also provides half of the Chinese New Year greeting. Taken together the ingredients comprise a dish appropriately called *gung hay fat choy*. (28)

The Chinese New Year reunion meal in America symbolizes her family's sense of connection and nostalgia, sparking memories and fostering a vision of a future where they can preserve their cultural ties while overcoming feelings of displacement and isolation. Food thus serves not only as a cultural marker but also as a catalyst for self-discovery and a means to honor her family's shared history. The act of preparing and sharing these meals becomes a ritual that strengthens her identity (Pazo 2016). Leslie's acceptance and expression of her hybrid Chinese-American identity are reflected in her recipes.

Both Tan and Li navigate the interplay between their two cultures, shedding light on the nuances of Chinese traditions and the challenges of cultural identity and migration. Beyond depicting struggles and triumphs, they aim to provide Western readers with a realistic and empathetic view of Chinese immigrants. Food serves as a versatile tool in their narratives, representing trauma, resentment and conflict, as well as comfort, connection and cultural pride.

Conclusions

Lahiri, Abu-Jaber, Dumas, Tan and Li each explore the diasporic experiences of their female protagonists and their pursuit of cultural hybridity, as conceptualized by Homi Bhabha's idea of the “third space” or “in-between space” (37). This space represents a contact zone where characters can recreate or express their transnational identities. These writers provide a nuanced understanding of food as a dynamic socio-cultural marker that enables their characters to connect with their heritage and engage across cultures.

Lahiri illustrates how food serves as a means for diasporic Indians to remember and recreate their lost homes. Abu-Jaber and Dumas offer a sensory exploration of food, allowing readers to experience the sights, smells and tastes that counteract misconceptions about Arabs and Iranians in the West. Tan and Li, representing the Chinese diaspora, delve into the complexities of immigrant

life, focusing on issues of belonging, assimilation and mother-daughter relationships in a new environment.

While most characters successfully perform their “culinary citizenship” through food, Mrs. Sen is an exception. It is noteworthy that these writers and their characters, despite their diversity, share a common social class, which aids their transnational integration and success. Their relative financial stability and access to education shape their perspectives and narratives. Future research could explore how food narratives intersect with social and economic status, particularly how working-class individuals navigate identity within new cultural and economic contexts.

Overall, these narrative voices use food to bridge gaps in their new homes, highlighting shared humanity while acknowledging differences. They craft a palatable narrative where the bitterness of displacement and assimilation pressures blend with the sweetness and vibrancy of adaptation. This results in a transnational hybridity that challenges the notion of a fixed national identity, embracing “in-betweenness” as an ever-evolving construct. The aim is to spread the scent of connection and the taste of inclusion.

In conclusion, this paper proposes that identity is an adaptive and evolving socio-cultural construction, particularly in our transnational era. It is crucial to build new interpretations linking food to various identity structures, such as race, ethnicity, gender and class. Food functions as a discursive and multilayered space where literature intersects with extra-literary conditions to foster diversity awareness, challenge exclusionary attitudes and encourage cross-cultural interactions. Food performativity thus plays a foundational role in identity construction across political borders, serving as a starting point for further exploration.

Notes

[1] Other novels by women writers that delve into various socio-cultural aspects of Indian diasporic life through the lens of food include Meera Syal’s *Anita and Me* (1996), Anita Desai’s *Feasting, Fasting* (1999), Amulya Malladi’s *Serving with Curry* (2004) and Amit Majmudar’s *The Abundance* (2013). In these works, food serves as a crucial element for exploring diasporic themes such as home, family ties, strategies for acculturation, generational divides, socio-economic challenges and the concept of hybridity.

[2] For more examples of diasporic Iranian women’s life writing, see *Diasporic Iranian Women’s Life Writing*, a 2020 doctoral dissertation by F. Abla, at Concordia University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada.

[3] Several studies have been done on the significance of humour and satire in Dumas’ works. As one example, see Hai, A. (2018). “Laughing with an Iranian American Woman: Firoozeh Dumas’s Memoirs and the (Cross-)Cultural Work of Humor”. *Journal of Asian American Studies* 21(2): 263-300.

[4] Vivian Nun Halloran’s *The Immigrant Kitchen* (2016) offers a fascinating lens to examine the role of Thanksgiving in the immigrant experience. The book is a rich

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tapestry of stories that explore how food, ethnicity and diaspora intersect in the lives of immigrants. It provides a pivotal analysis of how this holiday serves as a microcosm of the immigrant experience, their performance of assimilation and negotiation of cultural differences.

[5] The term is borrowed from Leslie Li's memoir (11), analysed in this paper.

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The Politics of Responsive Cookbooks: Counter Gastronomy Collectibles in Laura Esquivel's *Like Water for Chocolate*

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Abstract

This essay examines the politics of counter cookbooks whose role shifts from receptacles to responses that mobilize revolutionary culinary spaces in the war narrative of Laura Esquivel's Like Water for Chocolate (1989). In particular, the essay redirects the main theories and critiques that have been established and espoused in culinary studies. In this reading of Like Water for Chocolate, a cross-cultural intervention in the existing scholarship on domestic spatiality and female identity is addressed. Esquivel's narrative features provisioning collectibles that encode the mobility of the kitchen as a repository of women's counter-discourses that not only reverse but also chaotically recreate the structured conceptions in the master war narratives. The kitchen in Esquivel's narrative compiles cryptic scrapbooks of recipes whose technologies of knowledge are either decoded or re-inscribed from one generation to another. Arguably, women's transgenerational gastronomic writings function as intersemiotic artefacts that activate performative subject positions in gendered households and varied social contexts that reflect the dominant power dynamics. So, Like Water for Chocolate decentralizes the impact of external wars, as it curates recipes that are ekphrased and recreated in foodways that empower individuals, galvanize new alliances, and decolonize female relations from the national/international ideologies of warscapes, cultural signifiers, and collective memory. The essay incorporates Homi Bhabha's theory on the relation between the codification of history and the art of collecting to examine the discursive relations between food and power. Ultimately, this study revisits the complex dynamics of foodways as narrative functions, especially in relation to social inequalities and justice as portrayed through literature and cultural narratives.

Keywords: *responsive cookbook, counter-discourse, gastronomy, food justice, domestic wars, public wars.*

This essay focuses on a narrative that invites an analysis of how media spaces (traditional, cultural, aesthetic, embodied, mnemonic) are recreated to reposition wars in space and time in a manner that is transformative across political, social, cultural and personal spheres. In particular, this reading critiques how culinary recipes are militarized to mobilize wars that extend the ideologies of the external combat zones. The propagation of ideological wars, such as of civil wars or international invasions, is highlighted in the domestic

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wars between mothers and daughters in the narrative of Laura Esquivel's *Like Water for Chocolate* (1989). The setting of this focal narrative presents two kinds of wars, the first is the political, national, and patriarchal war in the public sphere, while the other is the "political," domestic and matriarchal war in the private sphere. One can note the parallelism between the external wars in the narrative, on the one hand, and the internal wars, on the other hand. However, the narrative mobilizes the various social dynamics embedded in power structures that are associated with our daily food habits and culinary practices. In this regard, *Like Water for Chocolate* presents counter personal recipes that reveal how the dominant structured conceptions during wars are not merely reversed but recreated chaotically. Arguably, the essay demonstrates that as well as looking back to historical situatedness, cultural signifiers and personal memory, cookbooks mobilize action and promote activism.

The recent scholarship on the cookbook genre has displayed a shift in the reading of cookbooks from reflections of society, culture or history, into active forms of intervention into those spheres. In this regard, critic Laurel Forster (2023) demonstrates that: "rather than considering what the cookbook implies and reveals in terms of social history, recent food symposiums focused upon how cookbooks make an intervention in culture and politics. Cookbooks were seen less as records of socio-historical times past, and more as sites of cultural energy and assimilation in themselves" (246-247). Cookbooks are currently critiqued as reflecting a dynamic cultural agency, suggesting moments of cultural ambition, rather than passively holding a mirror to society as repositories of social history. As such, current cookbook criticism has focused on the changeable role of the cookbooks from repositories to active responses and dynamic forms, which presents a new turn in culinary studies. There was an emergent sense of the cookbook being actively involved in shaping culture, gathering people and groups together with purpose, and making an active statement. So, new food studies offered new approaches that highlight the discursive function of cookbooks as they intervene in cultural contexts, galvanize groups, empower individuals, and resist ideologies. One particular example is the issue of *Food and Foodways* in which cookbooks are presented as sources of group allegiances, or formation of new alliances and processes. The collection demonstrates that as well as looking back to historical situatedness, cultural signifiers and personal memory, cookbooks also mobilize action and promote activism. The essays in this collection examine the cultural and social arguments and events that have generated cookbooks and explore how cookbooks have spoken back to groups, be they readers, writers or communities. In discussing how cookbooks have responded to cultural arguments, cookbooks have a much more active role to play. Cookbook activism has also redirected the relation between food and identity politics. Warren Belasco (1989), for instance, has explored how the radically new and

alternative approaches of “countercuisine” cookbooks have influenced more radical food lifestyles. Katharina Vester (2015: 3-4) has considered how food discourses have produced and impacted upon American identities, where cultural representations of food, food power and ideologies create performative subject positions that defy the culinary consolidation of social, ethnic, and gender roles. Floyd and Forster (2003) reveal how recipes are sites of interaction between stories of “family sagas and community records, of historical and cultural moments or changes, and also personal histories and narratives of the self” (2).

The cookbook collectibles in the selected war narrative of *Like Water for Chocolate* display the alignment between countercuisine cookbooks and performative subject positions. The way cookbooks articulate female agency provides a hidden repository of counter-discourses that challenge established social conceptions. In this regard, many social and gender assumptions have shaped the world of cooking. In “The Culinary Triangle,” Claude Lévi-Strauss identifies gender signifiers in varied recipes of the same food item:

Boiled food signifies refinement and sophistication compared to roasted food. However, the consolidation of gender roles reversed these associations, as boiled dishes are often linked to familial intimacy and traditionally prepared by women. At the same time, roasted fare is associated with public celebrations and a more masculine domain. Not only have these assumptions shaped gender roles within families, but they have also shaped the male-dominated world of fine cooking in terms of prestige and social status. (2008: 1)

Like Water for Chocolate contributes a countercuisine cookbook that interrogates the culinary extension of consolidated gender roles to war settings and their master historical documentation. [1] In this regard, war scholarship reveals that many female writers tend to view war differently as they present stories about girls who suffer from injustice, pain, neglect, and betrayal within the bigger picture of war while they try to restructure their lives to survive the psychological, domestic, and public wars at the same time. For instance, the Nigerian author and critic Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie leads a new wave of writing about wars in presenting the narrative of the Biafran War as the big frame of the stories about certain individuals from different classes and political or religious orientations in her novel *Half of a Yellow Sun* (2006). This wave suggests a new reading of war stories and entails the construction of a new genre of novels that are not aligned with classical battlefield novels. Instead, they do tell war stories from different viewpoints to avoid what Adichie famously called “the danger of a single story”. Arguably, Esquivel is not propagating a narrative on numbers, figures, and historical archives that shape a single story. Instead, she proposes a new way of telling war stories within a bigger frame that has a humanitarian touch. *Like Water for Chocolate*

displays varied provisional collectibles that reflect the dynamics of consolidating socially restrictive roles to mobilizing personal histories. The narrative displays a curation of recipes that communicate empowerment, camaraderie, and decolonization of female relations from the national/international ideologies of warscapes, cultural signifiers, and collective memory.

Like Water for Chocolate is set during the Mexican Revolution of 1910. The revolution also referred to as the Civil War, lasted for almost ten years and resulted in the end of the thirty-year dictatorship and the establishment of a constitutional republic. Mama Elena is one of the subjects who has been oppressed by the patriarchal society and traditions and transfers such oppression to her domestic space. Mama Elena takes the dominating role in the family that consists of three daughters Rosaura, Gertrudis and Tita De La Garza. After the death of her husband, Elena finds herself a young widow with three daughters and a ranch to manage. The weight of responsibility, as a mother inside the house and a manager outside the house, has turned Mama Elena into a strict dictator. She controls everything around her including the destiny of her girls and assumes the role of not only a male dictator but also a higher power that takes the role of the punisher, a higher force of oppression. Mama Elena's control over her daughters is exemplified by what Foucault (1995) refers to as "rationing of food, sexual deprivation, corporal punishment, solitary confinement" (15). Following her husband's death, Mama Elena "becomes the man of the house" (Perez 2009: 13) and eventually impersonates the male oppressor. The attitude of the oppressive matriarch causes a clash between Mama Elena and her daughters, especially Tita who is the first victim of her mother's dictatorship. Tita, according to traditions, is destined to be a slave for her entire life since she has to take care of her mother until her death. This absurd tradition of imprisonment and enslavement is claimed by Mama Elena as her legitimate right, being a matriarch.

In *Like Water for Chocolate*, the conflicts between the daughters and their mother introduce technologies of warring cookbooks. Michael Antony (2008) argues that feminists propose false claims about war: "The feminists have claimed that war is a product of 'patriarchy' or male domination, but there is no evidence of this." (110) This claim is crucial for the understanding of private wars and their development in Esquivel's narrative. Women play major roles in both spaces as they resist both enemies: the matriarchal enemy in the private sphere and the patriarchal enemy in the public sphere. Esquivel showcases that the so-called masculine craft is no longer gender specific. Women are no longer absent in the external battlefield and the battlefield itself is no longer a gender-restrictive outdoor space.

The first act of culinary resistance in *Like Water for Chocolate* (1992) is Tita's birth in the kitchen in a magical way that delivers tears, salt, and a baby. Tita

makes her “entrance to this world, prematurely, right there on the kitchen table” and “was literally washed into this world on a great tide of tears” (1). The image of Tita flowing into the world in a flood of tears prefigures the sadness and longing that will pervade her life. However, the salt accumulated from the tide of tears is dried to be used for cooking on the farm, which emphasizes the culinary gifts that Tita provides to the house. Being her birthplace, the kitchen becomes Tita’s natural space, “where she spent most of her life from the day she was born” (1). Tita’s birth also prefigures and signifies the motherly disempowerment of Mama Elena, who is now unable to produce milk (being devastated by the recent death of her husband) and consequently hands off Tita to the house cook, Nancha, who raises the child in the kitchen. Surrounded by the colours, smells, and routines of Nancha’s kitchen, Tita comprehends the world in terms of food and in a way that is different from that of her sisters, Gertrudis and Rosaura. She enjoys her isolation in the domain of the kitchen. And food becomes her language of self-expression that supports her stand in the culinary war and her ownership of the kitchen.

In *Like Water for Chocolate*, the matriarch’s psychological strategy is an authoritative intervention in culinary composition. The narrative demonstrates how the oppressive mother has a new target to control her daughters: “since it is no longer the body, it must be the soul” (Foucault 1995: 16). Mama Elena subjugates Tita’s soul and quenches her intrinsic love for cooking by transferring and infusing her oppression as a new ingredient in Tita’s food preparation. One major example is Tita’s love for Christmas rolls which is violated by Mama Elena’s announcement. Nancha and Tita “were together in the kitchen making Christmas rolls. As the name implies, these rolls are usually prepared around Christmas, but today they were being prepared in honour of Tita’s birthday” (5). Using food-swapping terminology, Chenchu indirectly comments on Mama Elena’s plan to have Pedro marry Rosaura instead of Tita. Tita’s first reaction reflects a limited assurance while she is cooking: “She would not accept what she had just heard.” (5) Feigning calm, Tita proceeds with her inborn instructions for making Christmas rolls. However, Tita’s innate culinary practice is interrupted by Mama Elena’s intervention in the recipe: “When Tita was finishing wrapping the next day’s rolls, Mama Elena came into the kitchen and informed them that she had agreed to Pedro’s marriage to Rosaura.” (5) With this announcement, Mama Elena quenches both Tita’s desire for Pedro and her self-empowerment and healing through the food she makes: “And now she had to give him up. It wasn’t decent to desire your sister’s future husband [...] She started to eat the Christmas roll Nancha had left out on her bureau, along with a glass of milk, this remedy had proven effective many times.” (7-8) However, Tita’s favourite recipe could not even cure her sadness. She is crippled by a feeling of cold. The warmth that Tita would usually get from her favourite food cannot end the coldness induced by

her tragic love. Tita's understanding of life through food fails to comfort her, and the inadequacy of food as an alternative to love becomes her new reality.

To sustain her authoritative position, Mama Elena resorts to a dismantle-to-rule plan. Her power has been directed toward cutting off all kinds of connections between all people in her house, especially Tita and Pedro. Elena specifically fights Tita's love for Pedro not only by forbidding their marriage but also by prohibiting any kind of communication between the lovers. So, gendered war is revisited since Esquivel's argument indicates that the feminist war against patriarchy is not the solution to gaining female freedom, as suppression is initiated here by a matriarchal authority. For Mama Elena, all forms of interaction pose a great danger to her authority. So, she forbids verbal communication. The lovers try to connect through Tita's recipes. For example, when Tita becomes the Chef, Pedro gifts her a bouquet of red roses. But Mama Elena orders Tita to throw it in the garbage. Even the smallest gestures of indirect contact have been monitored and eradicated by the matriarch. However, Tita uses the same roses to create her counter recipe quail in rose petal sauce, which becomes a source of communication with Pedro. Her food preparation becomes the artistic expression that empowers and enables her to connect with her lover while being at the table with Mama Elena: "That was the way she entered Pedro's body, hot, voluptuous, perfumed, totally sensuous." (21) The consumption of quail in rose petal sauce is of high importance for our understanding of the counter recipe. With that meal, it seems they have discovered a new system of communication, in which Tita is the transmitter, Pedro the receiver, and Gertrudis the medium or the conducting body through which the singular romantic message is passed. Tita's counter culinary media of communication have also several effects on each character according to their effaced desires. However, Tita's passion remains the most essential of all. Some may read Tita's situation as that of a victim, but the consumption of quail in rose petal sauce presents her as a powerful figure who manipulates people by cooking. And the most important example is her impact on Gertrudis's life. By taking the essential role of the cook, the food security of the ranch becomes under her control since Elena is not a cook, but a violent killer: "Mama Elena was merciless, killing with a single blow. For Tita she had made an exception; she had been killing her a little at a time since she was a child." (18) The recipe resistance exceeds the geographical limitations of Mama Elena's cuisine and realizes remote physical connection despite Mama Elena's presence. In this sense, Tita succeeds in resisting the matriarch by claiming the recipe of what has been supposed to isolate her and turning it into a venue of creation and communication. Tita's resistance accumulates power through gastronomical composition and proves that, as a woman, Tita is not the victim of matriarchy but an active player in the war against the unjust authority of the matriarch.

Tita's Quail recipe creates a female camaraderie that also liberates Gertrudis from Mama Elena's power. Esquivel clarifies that passion, not gender, becomes the driving force that elevates the person to lead. The case of Gertrudis is the best example as she has been infected by a magical potion of passion after eating quail in rose petal sauce already cooked by Tita. The cooked petals had already been infused by Tita's blood as she held them "to her chest so tightly that when she got to the kitchen, the roses, which had been mostly pink, had turned quite red from the blood that was flowing from Tita's hands and breasts" (19). Tita's blood and Pedro's roses that transmitted love through food have "proved quite an explosive combination" (19) and had an intense effect on Gertrudis, who is whipped into a lustful state and flees the ranch in the arms of a revolutionary soldier. She defies her mother's authority, first by the public expression of her sexuality as she flees naked from the house on the back of the rebel's horse in one of the most daring scenes in the novel, then by ruling an army of men. Even though the main battle over authority is between Mama Elena and Tita, Gertrudis launches an equally destructive war with her mother when she escapes her home to invade the public sphere. Mama Elena burns Gertrudis's birth certificate and all her belongings to set a precaution for her sisters, especially the rebellious Tita. Gertrudis has been liberated by Tita's recipe to pursue her passion for leadership. Her skills and courage at war pave the way for her to be the general who rules an army of loyal and obedient soldiers. In this sense, Tita's gastronomical composition encourages Gertrudis's rebellion against the matriarch in the private sphere and the patriarchal authorities in the public sphere.

Gertrudis's journey can be read as the metamorphosis of the passionate rose. It is a story of becoming, even in the toughest deserts of Mexico, geographically and metaphorically. It starts in the kitchen when Tita presents quail in rose petal sauce which "precipitates her outrageous escape" (Chakraborty 2015: 5) and ends in the kitchen when Gertrudis orders her loyal, yet culinary ignorant, soldier to prepare her favourite dessert (cream fritters). Tita has left the kitchen to discuss her pregnancy with Pedro. Gertrudis, General of the Army, has found herself alone with a recipe: "Gertrudis read this recipe as if she were reading hieroglyphics" (Esquivel 1992: 88). Her power and success on the battlefield do not help her when it comes to the "batter field"! To solve the problem, she resorts to her authority over the loyal soldier Sergeant Trevino and commands him to prepare the syrup, or she will shoot him dead. Even though Gertrudis manages to be a national icon of resistance and rebellion, only domestically, she needs culinary assistance. When Chenchu, the cook, refuses to help the General, Gertrudis resorts to her army and to Sergeant Trevino to ask about the cooking measures (90).

Esquivel manages to reverse the gendered roles in different recipes and proposes not equality, but rather neo-gender superiority in some instances.

Gertrudis, who lacks culinary knowledge, resorts to her authority just like her mother. But the victim here is the Sergeant who turns from a courageous fighter to a pastry chef to please his superior and save his life (92). Gertrudis's journey reflects new gendered dynamics in the battlefield and the kitchen: "Gertrudis' delegation of the baking shows her status as head of her community" (Komori 2010: 40). Gender equality is not the focal discussion in *Like Water for Chocolate* as Esquivel presents an anti-feminist perspective, not in the sense that it objectifies women but in the sense that it highlights female power without the considerations of patriarchy or the so-called masculine superiority. There is a war between men and women over spaces and freedom. The real war that the daughters fight is the war against matriarchy. Tita's battle may be limited to the culinary sphere, but Gertrudis's battle, even if not highlighted enough, is highly significant for today's women. It represents the battle of strong women who choose to live beyond the borders of their mothers' cuisine.

Tita leads another counterattack to intervene in her mother's recipes when the matriarch has been injured. Even though Mama Elena orders Tita to be the cook of the ranch in an attempt to control her inside the kitchen, she does not realise that by doing so Tita will dominate their food and the kitchen which is the heart of Mama Elena's space. The rebels have attacked Mama Elena's farm twice. The first attack caused Tita's nervous breakdown after the rebels violated the dovecote and "rounded up enough to feed the entire battalion for a week" (Esquivel 1992: 38). Even though Tita's birth has been described earlier as if she had been delivered by a wave of tears on the kitchen table, her real birth is when Dr. Brown has "found Tita naked [...] curled up in a fetal position" (46). Mama Elena then asks Dr Brown to confine her to an asylum. The war against Tita has different consequences, and the psychological one is the most difficult. Mama Elena jeopardises Tita's sanity after tormenting and dislocating her from the community and keeping her a prisoner. The dovecote incident is highly metaphorical. In the same way that the bandits take all the doves to devour them, Mama Elena has devoured Tita's will to live and left her covered in pigeon droppings and feathers, so she may never fly from the matriarch's nest. However, Dr Brown intrudes to deliver Tita into life again by moving her from her mother's concrete womb to life, but first through a spatial incubator. The whole concept of motherhood is readdressed as new forms of mothering emerge due to different power dynamics between the characters. In this sense, Tita's exile from her motherland is a new and painful birth after which she becomes an empowered woman who knows her rights and fights for her place in the matriarchal world.

The second attack against Mama Elena was by a group of bandits who ransacked the ranch. The bandits' invasion of the farm has turned Mama Elena into a disabled matriarch and has anticipated Tita's final culinary invasion. So, her mother receives her in silence: "For the first time Tita firmly held her gaze,

and Mama Elena lowered hers. There was a strange light in Tita's eyes." (58). Even though Elena has exiled Tita and ordered Dr. Brown to put her in an asylum, Tita has returned to her mother's space. Many people may read this as an act of purity or kindness. However, by so doing, Tita's recipes invade the kitchen of her disabled mother and dethrone Mama Elena. Yet, Tita faces a culinary dilemma since whatever she cooks for her mother, the matriarch describes it as "nasty and bitter" (59). Mama Elena thinks that Tita is planning to poison and get rid of her in order to be with Pedro, but she does not verbalize her worries. Instead, she just refuses to eat anything that Tita cooks or offers. Tita resorts to other chefs to cook for her mother. Still, Mama Elena continues to believe that Tita is poisoning her food. The disabled matriarch uses verbal abuse with all the cooks that Tita hires, and resorts to chemicals to supposedly clean her gut from the toxins. Tita aims at relocating herself in the matriarchal space, but as a free cook and woman not as an oppressed daughter. For Mama Elena, Tita's return has been regarded with caution as it represents a threat to the matriarch. That is why "she refused to eat anything that Tita had cooked" (61). Gastronomy plays a vital role in Tita's domestic intervention as she manages to reclaim her space on the farm as the master chef despite her mother's refusal (Atieh & Deeb 2021: 6).

Tita's curated recipes become the historical framework that restructures *Like Water for Chocolate* as the main episodes of each chapter are centred around the preparation or consumption of the dishes that Tita's recipes feature. Theorists' references to curated books as functional collectibles that symbolise power within social and historical hierarchies and status structures are significantly relevant to the provisionary collectibles. In this regard, Homi Bhabha (1995) reflects on book curation as a historical reference of personal mobility. Writing about unpacking his own crate of books, he asks: "Does the order of books determine the order of things? What kind of history of oneself and one's times is coded in the collecting of books?" (5) In this regard, critic Laurel Forster (2023) demonstrates how Bhabha's reflection is relevant to her relation with the order of her cookery books (246).

Like Water for Chocolate is re-ordered in light of the chaotic memories that Tita's recipes yield. The narrative is divided into twelve chapters, one for each month of the year, and each chapter comes with a Mexican recipe that correlates to a specific event and meal preparation in Tita's life. The narrator of the story is Esperanza's daughter, nicknamed Tita after her great-aunt. She describes how, after the fire, the only thing that survived under the smouldering rubble of the ranch was Tita's cookbook, which contained all the recipes described in the preceding chapters and told "in each of its recipes this story of a love interred" (118). The recipes are curated by Tita, who rebels against the family tradition that confines her to a loveless life. Her insistent questioning (even though she does not petition Mama Elena directly) of her lot

in life can be identified as one of the feminist impulses in the novel. This refusal to accept an assigned and undesirable social role marks the beginning of Tita's path that ends with self-assertion and freedom. On the other hand, the recipes are correlated with different months. So, they function as the alternative calendar or historical timeline that documents Tita's life. Such culinary history becomes the counter record to Mama Elena's master narrative that follows the timeline of the general war. Tita's cookbook reorders and corrects the restrictive reading of her life in light of her wars with Mama Elena.

The way Tita curates her cookbook restores the originality of the recipe and affirms self-balance and self-assurance that does not lead to destructive bleeding or merciless killing. The curator Tita positions the recipe of "Chrutnuw Ro" at the beginning of the narrative. The order of this recipe makes it a framing narrative that emphasises Tita's need for healing and self-assertion. The recipe refers to onion-induced weeping and offers a tactic of placing some onions on the cook's head in order to stop the tears. The recipe articulates the possibility of resistance and healing that presents a counter-narrative to Mama Elena's master narrative of oppression. In line with this frame, the following recipes are responsive compositions to the internal recipes that are intercepted by Mama Elena's authoritative cuisine. For instance, the February recipe "Chabefa Wany Cake" is given precedence to the violated recipe that has been inscribed by Mama Elena for Pedro and Rosaura's wedding. The March recipe is another articulation of reinscribed self-awareness as it violates the original recipe in order to resist the mother's authoritative intervention in Tita's communication with Pedro.

The other curated recipes register Tita's progressive journey toward healing, balance, and self-assertion. The April recipe, "Turkey Mok with Almonoj", features care and tenderness that reflects Tita's motherly feelings when she nurses Roberto, the son of Pedro and Rosaura. The recipe highlights the need to have turkey fattened up properly. Again, this recipe is important as it reflects the sustainability of love, care, and nurture through food and ultimately transcends Mama Elena's attempts to separate Tita from Pedro by sending him, Roberto, and Rosaura to San Antonio. Similarly, Tita's May recipe "Northern-tyler Chorizo" is a call for self-control that avoids the continuation of boiling/anger that leads to violence and destruction. This recipe is a counter record to the federal troops' raid on the ranch and the ensuing loss of Tita's large dovecote which has her cherished doves and pigeons that she used to nurture with care. The June recipe, "Makiny Matcheo", is a composition of comfort and distance from Mama Elena's oppressive ranch. It defies the language of isolation that Mama Elena advocates, suggests a recipe for an inner fire that yields protection and self-care and replaces the exterior fire of wars and conflicts. The June recipe feeds the idea of "because I don't want to" in Tita's personality and initiates her journey toward independence and selfhood.

The curated July recipe “Ozc-Tad Soup” also features its purpose of effective healing: “Soups can cure any illness” (54). The July recipe is another component in Tita’s cookbook that recognises healing as an effaced truth in the midst of wars (Esquivel 1992: 54). Tita’s August recipe “Champanngo” refers to resilience through pain. The recipe’s ingredients of finely chopped onions are linked to the first curated recipe that communicates the technique of putting onions on the cook’s head to avoid weeping (65). This counter technique is still needed by Tita to exercise control over rage or the feeling of “like water for chocolate,” referring to the preparation of chocolate, during which water is brought just short of boiling several times before use in the recipe.

The culinary collectibles of September and onwards register the empowerment of new relations that resist isolation and passive endings. The September recipe of “Chocolate and Three King’ Day Bread” transfers power through nourishment, comfort, and family reunion. The composition of this recipe reiterates the mixing of several types of good chocolate beans (75). The preparation of this meal coincides with Rosaura and Gertrudis’s return to Tita’s cuisine where she offers remedies for Rosaura’s indigestion and discomfort through her nourishing food and where Gertrudis finds connection and camaraderie with her sisters in the ranch. So, the chocolate recipe correlates with comradeship that, again, decenters the isolative impact of the master war that has been consolidated by Mama Elena. This female solidarity is galvanized in the October recipe “Cream Fritter” which instructs the need to maintain a low flame that allows the cream mix to thicken. This meal preparation simulates Gertrudis’s need to listen with patience to Tita’s articulation of desires in order to build steadfast support that encourages Tita’s self-assertion. The November recipe “Bea with Chile Tezcucana-Tyler” communicates the need for the infusion of food preparation with joy in order to transmit positive energy. Like the beans that need to be boiled with baking soda (96), the food needs to be purified from the anger and toxic feelings that shape the conversation between Tita and Rosaura over her planned marriage to Pedro. The December recipe of “Chi in Walnut Sauce” recipe reflects the urgency to free the self from rigid social structures and cultural conceptions. The December recipe involves “shelling the nuts several days in advance” (107-108). This last recipe also signifies new beginnings and directions initiated by the cross-cultural marriage of Alex, John Brown’s son, and Esperanza, which terminates a toxic legacy of oppression and destruction.

To conclude, Tita’s provisionary collectibles create an alternative timeline that reverses the master war narratives that end with death and destruction. The order in which these recipes are curated in Tita’s cookbook rereads the final scene of the ranch fire and the death of Tita and Pedro as an intervention that brings new hope for justice. The rearranged recipes articulate a culinary wisdom of activism that preserves history but embraces liberation.

As such, Tita's cookbook realises food justice as it shifts the role of her curated recipes from being militarised receptacles into active responses that mobilise performative subject positions and galvanise alliances that are decolonised from the dominant social moulds and restrictive cultural memories.

Notes

[1] María Teresa Martínez-Ortiz (2010) reads Esquivel's narrative as a cookbook that belongs to a traditionally considered feminine genre and is situated in war settings since the nuns in convents began to compile recipes to recover culinary history during the Mexican colonial period (167).

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Feasts of Resistance: The Role of Food in Shaping Feminist Cultural Discourse

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Abstract

*This paper explores the multifaceted representations of food as a symbolic medium in constructing and negotiating female identities, tracing the lineage from mythological narratives to postmodern feminist texts. By delving into the thematic intersections of food symbolism and female agency within a broad spectrum of literature, the arts, and media, the study elucidates how culinary motifs articulate power dynamics, social politics, and resistance movements. It engages with Vandana Shiva's critique of global food politics in *Stolen Harvest: The Hijacking of the Global Food Supply* (2000), and Michaela DeSoucey's analysis of culinary resistance in *Contested Tastes: Foie Gras and the Politics of Food* (2016). Furthermore, it highlights the contributions of Jessica B. Harris in *High on the Hog: A Culinary Journey from Africa to America* (2011), illustrating the profound connection between gastronomy, identity politics, and the feminist movement. Employing a multidisciplinary approach, the research juxtaposes mythological depictions of women as nurturers and providers with postmodern representations that challenge and subvert traditional roles through culinary metaphors. It highlights the evolution of female identities from passive subjects of mythic lore to active agents of feminist resistance, underscoring the transformative power of food imagery in articulating and contesting gender norms. Furthermore, it examines how contemporary feminist narratives harness the symbolism of food to critique societal structures, thereby reinforcing the connection between gastronomy and the politics of identity. By analyzing the contributions of scholars like Carole Counihan, and Penny Van Esterik in *Food and Culture: A Reader* (2013) and the critical perspectives offered by Arlene Voski Avakian and Barbara Haber in *From Betty Crocker to Feminist Food Studies* (2005), the article reveals the nuanced ways food serves as a vehicle for exploring and asserting female identities across temporal and cultural divides. It contributes to the broader discourse on gender, power, and resistance by showcasing the enduring relevance of food symbolism in the ongoing struggle for female autonomy and empowerment.*

Keywords: *food symbolism, female identity, feminist resistance, cultural narratives, gender roles.*

Introduction

The interplay between food symbolism and female identity within feminist cultural discourse offers a unique lens to explore broader societal norms and resistance movements. This article embarks on a multidisciplinary journey to

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unravel the complex narratives that food symbolism intertwines with the essence of women's agency and autonomy. From the ancient mythological depictions of women as nurturers to the postmodern feminist narratives that challenge and subvert these roles, food emerges not merely as sustenance but as a potent symbol of rebellion, empowerment, and identity.

The study of food in relation to gender and identity is not new; however, its exploration within feminist discourse offers fresh perspectives on resistance movements and power dynamics. Scholars like Carole Counihan and Penny Van Esterik (*Food and Culture. A Reader*, 1997) have emphasised the role of food as a cultural marker, deeply entwined with gender roles and societal expectations. Similarly, Arlene Voski Avakian and Barbara Haber's anthology *From Betty Crocker to Feminist Food Studies. Critical Perspectives on Women and Food* (2005) highlights the critical perspectives on women and food, emphasising the transformative potential of culinary motifs in feminist narratives. Furthermore, Jeffrey Pilcher's examination of food in world history (2005) provides a global context to this discourse, illustrating how culinary practices have been used to assert cultural identity and resist colonial powers.

To develop a comprehensive theoretical framework for analysing the role of food in shaping feminist cultural discourse, it is essential to integrate fundamental concepts from feminist theory and cultural studies. This framework will be the foundation for understanding how food symbolism operates within literature, the arts, and media to negotiate and articulate female identities, power dynamics, and resistance movements.

Firstly, feminist theory offers critical insights into how gender norms and power relations are constructed and contested in society. Scholars such as Simone de Beauvoir (*Le Deuxième Sexe*, 1949) and Judith Butler (*Bodies That Matter. On the Discursive Limits of "Sex"*, 1993; *Gender Trouble. Feminism and the Subversion of Identity*, 1999) have illuminated the performative nature of gender and the concept of the "second sex," respectively, arguing that gender is not a fixed biological fact but a social construct that is performed and reiterated through cultural practices, including those surrounding food. Integrating these perspectives, the framework will explore how culinary practices contribute to gender performance, serving as sites of conformity to and resistance against patriarchal norms.

For Beauvoir, gender is "constructed," but implied in her formulation is an agent, a *cogito*, who somehow takes on or appropriates that gender and could, in principle, take on some other gender. Is gender as variable and volitional as Beauvoir's account seems to suggest? Can "construction" in such a case be reduced to a form of choice? Beauvoir is clear that one "becomes" a woman, but always under a cultural compulsion to become one. (Butler 1999: 12)

Additionally, cultural studies, particularly the works of Stuart Hall (*Cultural Studies*, 1983) and Raymond Williams (*Culture and Society, 1780-1950*, 1960), offer a lens through which to view food as part of a cultural system that reflects and influences social relations, identities, and power structures. This approach examines how food-related practices and representations in media and literature are embedded within and comment on broader socio-political contexts, including gender inequality, colonialism, and globalisation.

The intersection of these theories provides a robust framework for analysing the multifaceted representations of food in feminist cultural discourse. This analysis will reveal how food is a symbolic medium for exploring and asserting female identities and how it challenges and subverts traditional gender roles and power relations. Through this theoretical lens, the article will critically examine selected texts and media, highlighting the evolution of female identities from passive subjects of mythic lore to active agents of feminist resistance.

This theoretical framework sets the stage for a detailed exploration of the role of food in shaping feminist cultural discourse. By employing a multidisciplinary approach, the research will delve into the thematic intersections of food symbolism and female agency, articulating how culinary motifs express, contest, and transform gender norms across different cultures and historical periods.

Feminist reinterpretations of food, myth, and gender roles

In many mythologies, female deities like Demeter in Greek mythology or Annapurna in Hindu mythology are revered for their roles as providers of food and nourishment, embodying the principles of fertility and abundance. These goddesses are often celebrated for their nurturing qualities, symbolising life-giving forces and the sustenance of societies. For instance, Demeter, the goddess of harvest and agriculture, is central to the myth of the Eleusinian Mysteries, which celebrated the cycles of life and death and the eternal return of abundance (Hamilton 1942: 53-58). Similarly, Annapurna, the Hindu goddess of food and cooking, represents the divine aspect of nourishment; her mythology is deeply intertwined with themes of generosity and provision (Kinsley 1998: 174).

However, the reverence for these mythological figures and their associations with food and fertility has translated into societal expectations for women to embody similar roles as caretakers and providers in the domestic sphere. This translation from myth to societal norms has not been entirely empowering. While these roles are crucial and respected within many cultures, they have also contributed to the confinement of women to domestic spaces, limiting their participation in public and political life. The celebration of female deities in mythological contexts contrasts with the restriction of women's roles

in reality, where the domestication of food preparation and consumption often reinforces traditional gender hierarchies.

The transition from mythological empowerment to domestic confinement reflects broader patterns of gendered expectations and the valuation of women's labour. In exploring this theme, it is essential to consider how contemporary feminist discourse seeks to reclaim and reinterpret these mythological narratives. By highlighting the complexities of food symbolism and its ties to female identity and power, feminist scholars and activists challenge the historical confinement of women to the domestic sphere, advocating for broader recognition of women's roles and contributions beyond traditional boundaries.

This discussion underscores the need to examine mythological and cultural narratives surrounding food and gender critically. By unpacking these stories, we can better understand the roots of contemporary gender roles and explore avenues for resistance and empowerment within and beyond the domestic sphere.

The interplay of food, seduction, and power is a nuanced theme explored in various cultural texts, where culinary skills extend beyond mere sustenance to become instruments of influence and autonomy. This dynamic is particularly pronounced in feminist literature and cinema, where food is often depicted as a tool for women to navigate and subvert patriarchal power structures.

For instance, in Laura Esquivel's *Like Water for Chocolate. A Novel in Monthly Installments with Recipes, Romances, and Home Remedies* (*Como agua para chocolate. Novela en doce entregas con recetas, amore y remedios caseros*, 1989), the protagonist, Tita, uses her culinary expertise to express forbidden emotions, turning traditional Mexican dishes into conduits of desire and rebellion. Each meal she prepares becomes a form of silent communication, challenging the oppressive norms that seek to confine her passions and aspirations. In a setting where traditional Mexican society severely limits the expression of female autonomy, Tita's culinary creations become her voice, allowing her to articulate her identity and exert influence over those around her. The emotional resonance of her dishes transcends the kitchen, bringing changes in the lives of those who consume them, thereby challenging the boundaries imposed upon her as a woman.

Similarly, in Joanne Harris's *Chocolat* (1999), the arrival of Vianne Rocher in a conservative French village with her exotic chocolate shop catalyses change. Through her chocolates, Vianne awakens people's desires and challenges the village's rigid moral codes and patriarchal structures by offering an alternative space where relationships are forged. Her ability to seduce and influence others through food highlights the transformative power of culinary expertise as a form of resistance. Her culinary prowess grants her autonomy

and positions her as a catalyst for changes within the community, subverting the power dynamics and empowering individuals.

These narratives underscore the complexity of food's role in the interplay of seduction and control, illustrating how women utilise culinary skills to carve out spaces of autonomy and influence within restrictive environments. By infusing food with emotion and intent, they challenge existing power relations and redefine their identity and agency boundaries.

Kitchen revolutions and feminist empowerment

Within feminist discourse, traditionally seen as a domain of domesticity and female subservience, the kitchen transforms into a battleground for resistance and empowerment. Culinary resistance, as explored through feminist texts and narratives, showcases how women wield food and cooking as potent tools against societal norms and expectations, crafting a rich tapestry of rebellion that spans cultures and epochs.

Amy Bentley's insightful analysis of food rationing during World War II unveils the kitchen as a site of subtle subversion (*Eating for Victory. Food Rationing and the Politics of Domesticity*, 1998). Women, navigating the constraints of rationing, ingeniously repurposed limited resources to sustain their families and communities, simultaneously challenging and conforming to their expected roles. This period highlighted the duality of women's relationship with food—bound by societal expectations yet innovative within those confines, laying early seeds for culinary resistance.

The postwar era, particularly the 1950s, as examined by Erica Endrijonas in *Processed Foods from Scratch: Cooking for a Family in the 1950s*, further complicates the narrative of food and gender—the advent of processed foods promised liberation from the toil of cooking. However, the societal expectation of culinary perfection for women remained a paradox that underscored the persistent gendered dynamics within the kitchen. Women's navigation through these contradictions—embracing convenience while contesting the perfectionist paradigm—illustrates the evolving nature of culinary resistance.

Deborah Lupton (*Food, the Body, and the Self*, 1996) and Elspeth Probyn (*Carnal Appetites. FoodSexIdentities*, 2000) delve deeper into the identity politics of food, arguing that culinary practices are intimately tied to the construction of self and others. Through cooking and eating, women articulate identities that resist reductionist stereotypes, crafting spaces of autonomy and self-expression within and beyond the kitchen. The personal narratives shared in their works underscore the transformative potential of food as a medium of personal and political expression.

Doris Witt's food exploration in the context of race and gender unveils another layer of culinary resistance. Her analysis of African-American culinary traditions highlights how food serves as a medium to challenge racial and

gender stereotypes. The kitchen becomes a space where African-American women assert their identity and agency, reclaiming and celebrating their culinary heritage as a form of resistance against the marginalisation and commodification of their culture: "Aunt Jemima is otherwise identical to the cookie jars created by white America: obese, black, and smiling. The potential for rebellion, her portrayal might suggest, is already contained within the stereotype and simply awaits activation under the right historical circumstances." (Witt 1999: 50)

These narratives of culinary resistance are not mere acts of defiance but are deeply embedded in the broader struggle for gender equality and empowerment. They reflect the complex interplay between conformity and rebellion, where food and cooking emerge as powerful symbols of identity, autonomy, and resistance. Through these acts of culinary resistance, women negotiate their place within societal structures, challenging and reshaping the gendered norms that have long confined them to the domestic sphere.

The preparation and sharing of food have long transcended mere acts of sustenance, morphing into powerful expressions of identity, autonomy, and resistance. This transformation is vividly captured in contemporary feminist narratives, where food symbolism becomes a medium through which women articulate and assert their identities, challenging traditional gender roles and societal constraints. Through the lens of selected feminist texts and media, we can explore the multifaceted ways culinary practices serve as conduits for empowerment and self-expression.

These narratives underscore the potency of culinary practices as forms of personal and communal empowerment. The act of cooking, especially for women, becomes a space of creative expression and agency, challenging the historical relegation of women to the domestic sphere and the devaluation of their labour. By reclaiming the kitchen as a site of power and resistance, women redefine their roles within their families and societies.

Moreover, food sharing often serves as a ritual of inclusion and exclusion, defining community boundaries and identities. In this context, women's roles in preparing and sharing food become acts of cultural preservation and resistance, particularly in diasporic communities where food is a vital link to the homeland. The kitchen, thus, transforms into a space where gender, culture, and politics intersect, with women at the helm navigating and negotiating these complex dynamics.

The intricate relationship between food symbolism and feminine empowerment transcends cultural boundaries, offering a rich tapestry of narratives that illustrate the universal and culturally specific ways women use culinary practices as resistance and self-expression. By integrating case studies from diverse cultural backgrounds, we can explore the global relevance of food symbolism in feminist discourse, highlighting how culinary narratives serve as

potent mediums for articulating identity, challenging power dynamics, and fostering community and individual empowerment.

Breaking barriers in diaspora and professional spaces

The narrative of Vertamae Smart-Grosvenor in *Vibration Cooking, or the Travel Notes of a Geechee Girl* (1970) provides insight into the African-American experience, blending recipes, memoirs, and cultural commentary. Smart-Grosvenor uses food to explore her identity and heritage, challenging stereotypes and asserting the richness of African American culinary traditions. Her work exemplifies how food serves as a medium for cultural preservation and resistance against marginalisation, illustrating the complex interplay between race, gender, and food in the American context:

I want to stake out a position about Vertamae's seminal work that I think bears considering: part of what makes Vertamae's cookbook a manifesto is the way in which she intervenes in the dialogues—then and now—to resituate the place and the definitions of African American food and foodways and the roles of the black women who procure, prepare, present, and consume them. (Smart-Grosvenor 1970: 18)

While rooted in specific cultural contexts, these narratives share common themes of resistance, empowerment, and identity formation through culinary practices. They highlight the universal aspects of food symbolism in feminist discourse, such as the use of food to express love, desire, and political dissent, while also underscoring the culturally specific ways these themes manifest. Through the lens of these diverse narratives, we gain a deeper understanding of the global significance of food symbolism in articulating female identities and challenging traditional gender roles.

Historically, women's food production and preparation roles have been closely tied to societal expectations and gender norms. However, these roles have also given women a unique agency within their communities and families. In many cultures, women have been the primary keepers of culinary knowledge, passing down recipes and food traditions from generation to generation. This role, while often undervalued in patriarchal societies, has given women a form of power and influence that is deeply interwoven with cultural identity and continuity.

The act of cooking and feeding, traditionally seen as a woman's duty, can also be a subtle form of resistance and empowerment. In *Something from the Oven: Reinventing Dinner in 1950s America* (2004), food historian Laura Shapiro highlights how post-World War II American women navigated the rise of convenience foods and the societal push towards modernity by creatively blending traditional cooking with new food technologies. This period marked

a significant shift in how women engaged with food as they began to assert their preferences and resist the homogenisation of taste and culture.

In the Global South, the relationship between women and food takes on additional complexity due to colonialism, globalisation, and economic inequality. Women in these contexts often bear the brunt of food insecurity and have been at the forefront of struggles for food sovereignty. For example, The Via Campesina movement highlights women's role in advocating for sustainable agriculture and resisting the corporatisation of food systems. Through their activism, these women challenge not only gender norms but also larger socio-political and economic structures that marginalise rural and Indigenous communities:

Perhaps most important is the persistence of ideologies and cultural practices that perpetuate unequal and inequitable gender relations. For instance, the gender division of labour means that rural women have considerably less access to a most precious resource, time, to be involved in leadership positions in farm organizations. Because women remain primarily responsible for the care of children and elders, they find it far more difficult than men do to leave their households for, say, a ten-day international farm meeting. [...] As the First International Women's Assembly of the Via Campesina pointed out, while women had made some advances in carving out more spaces as women's organizations and/or in mixed organizations, the specific condition and subordinate position of women relative to men in most (if not all) societies remain a key barrier to gender equality. (Desmarais 2007: 178)

Culinary resistance and cultural identity across the globe

The kitchen can serve as a site of cultural resistance for immigrant women, who use food to maintain connections to their homeland while navigating the complexities of their new identities in diaspora communities. Preparing traditional dishes becomes an act of cultural preservation and resistance against assimilation. In her works on Middle Eastern and Mediterranean cuisines, cookbook author and food activist Anissa Helou (*Levant: Recipes and Memories from the Middle East*, 2013; *Feast: Food of the Islamic World*, 2018) explores how food bridges cultures, enabling women to assert their identities and resist cultural erasure.

These historical and socio-political perspectives reveal the multifaceted ways in which women engage with food to negotiate power and assert their identities. Through their roles in food production, preparation, and activism, women challenge the societal norms and structures that seek to confine them, using food as a tool for resistance, empowerment, and cultural expression.

The culinary arts have long been a domain where women have exercised creativity and skill. However, the recognition of their contributions has often been overshadowed by the persistent gender biases within professional kitchens and culinary institutions. However, women have increasingly used

the culinary arts as a platform for feminist expression and resistance, challenging traditional narratives and asserting their place within the culinary world with vigour and innovation.

One notable figure in this movement is Julia Child, who revolutionised American cuisine and perceptions of cooking through her cookbook, *Mastering the Art of French Cooking* (1961), and her television cooking series, *The French Chef* (1963-1973). Child demystified French cuisine for the American public, presenting cooking as an accessible art form and encouraging women to explore culinary creativity in their homes. Her work contributed to a transformation in American culinary practices. It challenged the male-dominated culinary industry by proving that women could excel in and fundamentally alter the landscape of professional cooking: “When the *San Francisco Examiner* put the question directly to a dozen famous women in 1975, Julia admitted, ‘I guess I am liberated,’ pointing out that she was of her own free choice doing what she wanted and loved.” (Fitch 1997: 372)

In recent years, chefs like Dominique Crenn, the first woman in the United States to receive three Michelin stars for her restaurant Atelier Crenn, have continued breaking barriers and challenging gender norms in the culinary industry. Crenn’s approach to cuisine, which she describes as “poetic culinaria” (Crenn and Leibowitz 2015: 7), embodies artistic and feminist expression that defies conventional expectations of food preparation and presentation. Through her culinary creations, Crenn showcases her exceptional skill and creativity and advocates for sustainability, equity, and inclusivity in the culinary world.

Beyond the professional kitchen, women food activists and writers have used their platforms to highlight the intersection of food, feminism, and social justice. For example, Vandana Shiva, an environmental activist and food sovereignty advocate, has been at the forefront of the fight against industrial agriculture and genetically modified crops, championing the rights of small farmers, particularly women, in developing countries. Shiva’s work (*Staying Alive: Women, Ecology and Survival in India*, 1988; *Stolen Harvest: The Hijacking of the Global Food Supply*, 2016) emphasises the importance of preserving indigenous knowledge and practices related to food and agriculture as a form of resistance against corporate control of the food system.

Similarly, food writer and activist Michaela DeSoucey (2016) has explored the concept of *culinary resistance* by examining *foie gras* and food politics in France. Through her analysis, DeSoucey illustrates how culinary preferences and practices can become battlegrounds for cultural identity, ethics, and resistance, offering insights into how individuals and communities use food to negotiate social and political power:

Contestation around foie gras exposes acute political tensions around consumption, identity, and cultural authority in today’s culinary world. These

battles illustrate how the juxtaposition of moralistic concerns and the culture of markets makes our ongoing relationship with food—and with each other—invariably political. Some call foie gras historically and culturally irreplaceable for who they are, personally or professionally. Others find its very existence upsetting, offensive, and a reason for protest. (DeSoucey 2016: 19)

These examples underscore the multifaceted ways women engage with the culinary arts as a form of feminist expression and resistance. By creating dishes and culinary experiences that defy traditional norms, female chefs, cookbook authors, and food activists celebrate female creativity and autonomy and contribute to broader conversations about gender equality, sustainability, and social justice within the culinary landscape.

Intersections of food activism, feminism and race

The intersections of food, race, and gender form a complex tapestry within the culinary world, revealing deep-seated inequalities and challenges faced by women of colour. However, despite these obstacles, women of colour have been at the forefront of transforming culinary practices, food activism, and the broader food justice movement. Their contributions challenge stereotypes and systemic barriers and enrich the culinary landscape with diverse perspectives and flavours.

Leah Chase, the Queen of Creole Cuisine, is pivotal in this discourse. As the chef and proprietor of Dooky Chase's Restaurant in New Orleans, Chase broke racial barriers by serving black and white patrons during segregation, using her restaurant as a space for political activism and civil rights discussions. Chase's culinary contributions go beyond her mastery of Creole cuisine; her work symbolises the power of food as a tool for social change and the importance of black women's leadership in challenging racial and gender norms within the culinary industry.

Similarly, the work of chef and author Jessica B. Harris, *High on the Hog: A Culinary Journey from Africa to America* (2011), provides invaluable insights into the African diaspora's culinary history, highlighting how food serves as a medium for cultural identity and resistance. Harris's extensive research and writing explore the intricate connections between food, culture, and history, offering a counter-narrative to the often-marginalised culinary contributions of African and African-American communities. Harris champions the recognition and appreciation of black culinary heritage through her work, asserting the importance of women's roles in preserving and sharing these traditions:

New waves of immigrants have arrived from the African motherland, set up restaurants, and reacquainted us with tastes of our long-departed homeland. Morou Ouattara cooks recipes learned from his Ivorian grandmother in the Washington, D.C., area and Pierre Thiam reinvents Senegalese classics in

Brooklyn, New York. Bryant Terry creates vegan soul food in Oakland, California. Around the country, African American chefs are stepping up to stoves and creating foods that are expressions of the sum total of the black cultural experience: African, Southern, Caribbean, and more. (Harris 2011: 101)

The food justice movement has also seen significant contributions from women of colour, who advocate for equitable access to healthy and culturally appropriate foods. Activists like Karen Washington, a farmer and co-founder of Black Urban Growers (BUGs), have been instrumental in addressing food deserts and advocating for urban agriculture to empower communities and challenge systemic food inequalities. Washington's work emphasises the intersectionality of food justice, highlighting how race, gender, and socioeconomic status impact access to healthy food options.

Moreover, the rise of digital food cultures has provided women of colour platforms to share their culinary traditions, challenge stereotypes, and engage in food activism. Food bloggers and social media influencers, such as Ayesha Curry (*The Seasoned Life: Food, Family, Faith, and the Joy of Eating Well*, 2016) and Hawa Hassan (*Bibi's Kitchen: The Recipes and Stories of Grandmothers from Eight African Countries that Touch the Indian Ocean*, 2020), use their online presence to celebrate their heritage and advocate for diversity and inclusion within the culinary world. Their success illustrates the potential of digital spaces to amplify marginalised voices and foster a more inclusive and equitable food industry.

These examples underscore the critical intersections of food, race, and gender, highlighting the challenges faced by women of colour in navigating stereotypes and systemic barriers. Nevertheless, their contributions to culinary practices, food activism, and the food justice movement reflect resilience, creativity, and a commitment to change. Recognizing and addressing racial and gender inequalities in food-related discussions is essential for achieving equity within the culinary industry and honouring the diverse cultural expressions that enrich our shared culinary heritage.

From heritage to innovation in a global world

In the tapestry of global culinary landscapes, women have emerged as pivotal figures in the dialogue between tradition and innovation. Their role in the kitchen transcends mere cooking; it is an act of cultural preservation, resistance against homogenisation, and an embrace of global influences.

The innovation process within traditional cuisines is a testament to the creativity and resilience of women across cultures. Faced with the influx of global culinary trends, women chefs and home cooks alike have found ingenious ways to incorporate new ingredients, techniques, and presentations into their traditional recipes. This fusion revitalises ancient cuisines and ensures their relevance in a rapidly changing world. For instance,

incorporating non-native spices into traditional recipes or adapting classic dishes to suit modern dietary trends illustrates how women are at the forefront of culinary evolution. These innovations are not just about creating something new but about preserving the essence of traditional cuisines in a form that resonates with contemporary audiences.

Women's contributions to culinary evolution are deeply rooted in their roles as cultural heritage custodians and agents of change. Through their intimate knowledge of traditional cooking methods and ingredients, they are uniquely positioned to bridge the past with the present. By selectively incorporating global influences, women enrich their culinary repertoire and assert their agency in a domain often dominated by external economic and cultural forces. This act of adaptation is also a form of resistance against the marginalisation of their culinary traditions and against the economic pressures that threaten to homogenise global food cultures.

Adapting traditional dishes under the influence of global trends carries significant economic and cultural implications. Economically, it opens up new markets and opportunities for women, empowering them to achieve financial independence and recognition within the global culinary scene. Culturally, it acts as a bulwark against the erasure of culinary identities, ensuring traditional cuisines' survival and continued evolution. However, this journey is fraught with challenges, including the risk of diluting the authenticity of traditional dishes and the potential for cultural appropriation. Women's balance in navigating these challenges speaks volumes about their resilience and ingenuity.

The narrative of adaptation and resistance in the culinary world is a powerful reflection of women's roles as both preservers and innovators of culture. Through their culinary practices, women keep the flame of traditional cuisines alive and kindle the fire of innovation, ensuring that these traditions continue to evolve and resonate with new generations. Their ability to weave together the threads of tradition and modernity highlights the dynamic nature of cultural identity in the face of globalisation. As we move forward, the stories of these women will remain crucial in understanding the complexities of culinary adaptation and the enduring strength of cultural heritage.

Conclusions

Through an intricate exploration of the intersections between food, gender, and culture, this article has unveiled the profound ways in which culinary practices shape and are shaped by women's lives across the globe. From the commodification of traditional foods amidst the tides of globalisation to the profoundly personal battles fought at the intersection of food, body image, and identity, the narratives of women's culinary engagement emerge as potent

testaments to their resilience, creativity, and resistance against constraining societal norms.

Globalisation, while knitting the world closer, has presented a complex tableau of challenges and opportunities for women's culinary practices. It has ushered traditional dishes onto the global stage, transforming them into commodities that straddle the fine line between cultural celebration and exploitation. As the bearers of culinary tradition, women navigate this new global landscape, striving to preserve the authenticity of their heritage while embracing the economic opportunities it presents. This delicate balance between adaptation and resistance is a recurring theme, highlighting women's agency in redefining their roles and asserting their culinary traditions against the backdrop of global homogenisation.

Equally compelling is the exploration of food's role in shaping body image and identity, a domain where societal norms and personal narratives collide. The feminist critique of these norms, coupled with advocacy for body positivity, underscores the transformative potential of viewing food not as an adversary but as an ally in the journey toward self-acceptance and empowerment. This reclamation of agency over one's body and dietary choices emerges as a powerful counter-narrative to prevailing beauty standards, offering a space for women to redefine their relationship with food on their terms.

In synthesising these diverse strands, the article presents a compelling narrative of how food – far from mere sustenance – becomes a locus of power, identity, and resistance. It underscores the need for continued exploration, advocacy, and action to ensure the culinary world is inclusive, equitable, and reflective of the rich tapestry of women's experiences and contributions. Through this lens, the article not only contributes to the broader discourse on gender, culture, and food, but also celebrates the indomitable spirit of women who, through their culinary practices, can challenge, redefine, and enrich our understanding of the world.

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What is 'Soup'?

Exploration of a Staple in Nigerian Food Blogs

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Abstract

Food blogs are literary virtual forms and important ways in which migrants share recipes, stories and ingredients. On blogs, some foods become emblematic of specific spaces linked to concepts of identity, affordability and health. Using text, photos and videos, people express the ways to make authentic dishes with novel ingredients. Over the past several years, food blogs have become valuable means for Nigerian migrants to share recipes, highlighting ways to substitute ingredients and still retaining the essential flavour and perceived nutritional content of the dish. One such important staple dish for Nigerians is 'soup'. By focusing on recipes for 'soup' we ask: what makes 'soup' such an important on Nigerian food blogs? Which soups are most popular and what narratives do popular bloggers share about soups and their ingredients? Using content and narrative analysis, we argue that soup recipes on blogs are part and parcel of food literature that accompanies migration.

Keywords: *food blogs, recipes, Nigerian foods, soups, content analysis*

Introduction

Nigerians have a long history of migration (Heaton 2013) and have taken their recipes along with them. Food blogs have become valuable means for Nigerian migrants to share recipes, highlighting ways to substitute ingredients while still retaining the dish's essential flavour and perceived nutritional content. Recipes can be transmitted orally, through books and other hard copy media but more recently, the internet provides a powerful virtual space for diasporic migrants, to experience foods linked to specific valued places through blogging. On blogs, some foods become emblematic of certain experiences or shared health benefits. One such important dish for Nigerians is 'soup.' Here we ask: what makes 'soup' such an important presence on Nigerian food blogs? What are the most popular soups 'narrated' by bloggers? What are the limits of perceived ingredients, preparation styles and acceptable elements of substitution? Soup recipes shared on blogs, a literary form consumed by millions of Nigerian subscribers, are not only roadmaps to authentic dishes but also snapshots of how people maintain cultural continuity through migration.

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Food, recipes, health

Food habits, knowledge and meaning are social constructs, determined by historical and cultural contexts. Food can be considered an artefact that shapes us physically, socially, and culturally (Caplan 2013; Macbeth and MacClancy 2004). Food is specific to where we have come from, who we are, who we want to become, and how we perceive or represent ourselves (Crowther 2018; Konefal, and Hatanaka 2019). Food knowledge can reveal elements of historical continuity and how people cope with change (Camarena et al 2011). A recipe provides guidance on how to properly prepare a dish to maintain its authentic texture, taste and organoleptic qualities and meanings (Etkin 2008: 30). By providing guidance on one's eating culture, recipes can also change the way that we eat through historical time or space, how what we consider edible changes, or maintains consistency (Crowther 2018: 135). Both food and recipes can be considered cultural artefacts that reveal change and continuity through time and space.

While there is a link between food and culture, there is also a close link between foods and understanding of health, which is often deeply embedded in medical folklore, beliefs, taboos and recipe-based prescriptions (Counihan & van Esterik, P. 2008: 290; Igoli et al 2005; Mafimisebi & Oguntade 2010) Along with perceived pharmacological elements, food is directly related to wellbeing (Etkin 2008; Caplan 2013: 9; Crowther 2018: 8; Macbeth and MacClancy 2004; Pieroni and Price 2006).

Nigeria is a country in West Africa. Though multilingual, the official language is English (Adamo 2007). It has about three hundred and seventy-four (374) distinct ethnic groups, which could be classified into six geo-political zones and deep and rich pre-and post-colonial history (Ene-Obong 2013). Likewise, Nigerians can be found in every continent, and there you will also find variations of Nigerian foods.

An ethnopharmacology of food (Etkin 2008) is evidenced in Nigeria's agrarian economy, which provides virtually all the nation's home-produced foods, and medicines (Anoliefo et al 2003; Adamu 2013). Historically, Nigerians rely almost exclusively on traditional medicines – the combination of plants, or animal products with spiritual therapies, or techniques for healthcare needs (Mafimisebi and Oguntade 2010). Most of Nigeria's traditional foods are plant-based, with little contribution made through faunal products (Adegboye et al 2016: 2485; Ayogu et al 2017: 66). Bark, leaves, roots, flowers, fruits and seeds have remained important sources of health maintenance for most Nigerians (Adamo 2007: 40; Etkin 2008). This belief in traditional medicines then impacts how, what and when Nigerians prepare or/and eat. Studying recipes, therefore, provides profound insights into how recipes have changed over time due to cross-cultural influences and migration (Bodomo and Ma 2012: 18).

Sharing recipes in textual form has a long history, not just in North America and Europe. Several cookbooks have been produced in Nigeria and the diaspora over the past century (Mars and Tooleyo 1961; O'Reilly-Wright 1979; Ogunsanya 1998). These have been explored to a limited extent online (See, for example, the website *Kitchen Butterfly*). With the rapid expansion of the internet, the relationship between humans, food and computers has been burgeoning (Arnold et al 2018). In these conditions, the food blogging culture has proliferated and expanded (Holak, 2013; Schneider et al 2018: 203-219; Min et al 2017). Nigerians, like many others, have created food blogs, where recipes and stories are melded into a unique cultural experience and are presented through multimodal interweaving of extensive use of videos; links; enticing images of selected dishes; and captivating personal and cultural narratives, stories, reviews that attract followers' and readers' comments (Elliott et al 2021; Leena 2016; Lepkowska-White and Kortright 2017). Dominant food blogs, such as *All Nigerian Recipes* (Nigerian Food Blog), *All Nigerian Foods*, and *Dobby's Signature* are notable examples, having many followers. These digital forms of cookbooks are also a means to create, modify, document, display, share and expand recipes to include wider aspects of cultural and historical life beyond the bare recipe book format that was particularly characteristic in the 20th century (Rodney et al 2017; Pires Viera da Rocha 2016). Blogs are "computational artefacts" (Deng et al 2022) and offer powerful "expressive spaciousness" with posts ephemerally appearing day after day (Maitzen 2023).

The top ten Nigerian food blogs sampled in the study were selected because they collectively cater to more than three million subscribers. They are mostly gendered by adult women, common in other food blogs (Rodney et al 2017). This gendering of Nigerian food blogs by women seems to point to the literature that in most African countries like Nigeria, cooking as well as the satisfaction of the culinary needs of the family is the prime role of the woman (Elwert-Kretschmer 2001; Agbasiere 2000). The sampled blogs also emphasised that women play the prominent role of cooking in the family, and as such, end up as the promoters of cultural tradition, providers and managers of what and how the family eats.

Some blogs have become so popular that people also expand them into books as a way to preserve the knowledge of the elder generation and inspire people through times of economic want and displacement (Cannucciari and Cannucciari 2009). Likewise, Nigerian bloggers transform digital content into hard copy materials such as *The Ultimate Nigerian Cookbook: Best Cookbook for Making Nigerian Foods* (2020) by C. Anegbu or *All Nigerian Recipes Cookbook* (2013) by Flo Madubike. Although these media have huge audiences, few studies are focusing on food blogs which offer rich sources of cultural and historical information on change and continuity in global cuisines.

Methods

Since food is a wide cultural domain, this study draws on both qualitative and quantitative methods to increase reliability and validity (Bernard 2017). Specifically, both componential and content analysis were utilised. A purposive/judgment and convenience/haphazard sample (Bernard 2017: 147, 149) was selected using Google as the main search engine and we targeted the top ten Nigerian food blogs (See Website Sources below). A specific search term like “Nigerian food blogs” was used as the “seed term” (Kurtz et al 2017).

Upon evaluation of the sampled Nigerian blogs, it was discovered that some had more categories of recipes than others, thereby reflecting the enormous food diversity (Adegboye et al 2016). For example, one blog had over 186 categories of recipes (Nig). Among this diversity, “soup” was one of the most common food types and among these, – “ogbono” (wild mango) soup is the most common of all, hence, we asked what makes the ogbono soup as articulated on Nigerian food blogs.

Methodology

This study utilised componential and content analysis in order to identify the components (characteristics, elements, main ingredients) of ogbono soup. Componential Analysis had characteristically been associated with linguistics, and we found it useful to study the syntax of soups. This involved developing binaries and scrutinising these binaries for definitive elements, attributes and ingredients that can be included or excluded (Bernard 2017; Goodenough 1956). For the easy identification of the components of ogbono soup recipes and their different variations, the nuances of ingredients noted in the componential analysis of ogbono soup, and their various versions were categorised under essential (or main) and non-essential ingredients. *Essential or main ingredients* are mentioned by all (100%) of the sampled blogs which mention this soup. *Non-essential ingredients* have not been mentioned by all the sampled blogs (less than 100% of the sampled blogs). While the latter could be used to add to the content of the soup, they are optional – one could do without them (Wives; Dobby; Sisi; Don). Additionally, a macro-level content analysis and narrative analysis (Bernard 2017) of the posts on ogbono soup recipes on the sampled Nigerian food blogs was conducted.

Soups and swallows

When considering Nigerian foods and appreciating the diversity (Onabanjo and Oguntona 2003), there are dominant and historically stable food patterns such as a carbohydrate-based meal including vegetables such as roots, tubers and cereals which are consumed with soup (Onabanjo et al 2013: 368). One popular side used in eating soups is “swallows.” These are mostly starchy foods which are regarded as “swallows” and cut in small fractions, rolled into

a ball, dipped into the soup, and rather than being chewed, swallowed. Swallows usually accompany soups.

The English word 'soup' is commonly used by Nigerians to refer to a staple food. Soup is defined as foods made by boiling solid ingredients like animal proteins in liquid until the flavours are extracted, forming a broth that is usually thickened with vegetable-based thickeners and eaten with staple foods.

One additional thing worth mentioning before exploring the content of soups, is to provide a snapshot of some of the endearing ways that soups are described by the bloggers. For example, of Bitter Leaf Soup one blogger says that one will be deemed a bad cook if his/her bitter leaf soup tastes bitter (Rec), and White Soup is referred to as a hearty Nigerian soup (Nig) or a soup with bold flavours. Then there is Egusi Soup, described as well-loved and cooked (IQ), and Afang Soup which "guarantees most people will be present for lunch" (IQ). These narratives capture the hopes of the bloggers to appeal to diasporic Nigerians' desire to experience family, a sense of home, wellness and identity and sometimes humour.

Image A. The "Well-Loved Soup": Melon ("Egusi") Soup

Nigerian recipes are usually named based on the typical elements of the dish, which form the major characteristic of the recipe (Seki and Ono 2014). This makes it easier for a user to grasp the main characteristics and ingredients of a recipe at first glance. For instance, recipes may be named after the major vegetable or ingredient used in their preparation such as *egusi* ("melon") soup (Okeke et al 2009: 271, 279).

Some basic similarities could be referred to as "Nigerian foods" (Ene-Obong et al 2013; Adegboye 2016). These could be defined as foods generally consumed in all parts of Nigeria but bearing in mind too that there may be local regional variations. There may further be variations between households due

to availability, price, season and nutritional knowledge, taste preference food taboos, cultural and religious practices and preferred techniques of preparation (Anoliefo et al 2003; Ayogu et al 2017; Counihan & Esterik 2008; Etkin 2008). “Nigerian foods” then, comprise a varied food supply, and provide a rich source of medicinal materials for therapeutic purposes, which are understood to be essential to maintain the culture, health and wellbeing of Nigerians. It is this nexus of culture and health through food, and how recipes have changed over time, that will, therefore, be explored in this project through the selected food blogs.

Three popular soups: snapshot and portrait

We lack space here to cover the vast array of soups, but we would like to provide a snapshot of two popular soups before diving into the details of the main soup on the menu. First, one of the most popular traditional Nigerian soups is “Afang” (*Gnetum africanum*). It is made of water leaves (which could be substituted with watercress, lambs lettuce, spinach, malabar spinach (“amunututu”), “afang/okazi/ukazi” leaves, meat, smoked/dried fish, palm oil, pepper, crayfish, salt and seasoning cubes. While some of these ingredients could be substituted, the essential quality, as well as the star of this soup is the presence of “afang/okazi/ukazi” leaves which cannot be substituted. As such, if absent, it could render the supposed “afang” soup mere vegetable soup – a soup which could be made with any vegetable. However, traditionally, “afang/okazi/ukazi” leaves must be combined with another essential ingredient, water leaves, with the water leaves being added first. Further, onions would have to be eliminated when making the authentic version of “afang” soup, not because it renders the soup something else, but because it destroys the authenticity, which one of the bloggers describes as the “ancestors’ way of making” “afang” soup.

Image B. Afang (*Gnetum africanum*) Soup

As a result of its popularity, one of the bloggers noted that local Nigerian music artists feel obliged to mention this soup in the lyrics of their songs, especially if the song has to do with food, in order to accredit popularity to this soup (IQ). Another blogger said it could ignite people's interest in Nigerian foods (Foods), and yet another affectionately referred to it as a "Soup You Can Never Go Wrong With" (Dob)

"The Ever-giving Tree Soup": Palm Fruit/Nut ("Banga/Akwu/Abak") Soup
Another very popular Nigerian soup is "The Ever-giving Tree Soup": Palm Fruit/Nut ("Banga/Akwu/Abak") Soup. This soup is said to be very popular because it showcases – palm fruit (9ja). The palm nut tree has been described as "the ever-giving tree". All the blog narratives emphasised the durability of the soup as it "seems to improve with age" (IQ) and tastes better with frequent reheating and could even last for months (Don).

Image C. Palm Fruit Soup/Stew

Focus on African wild mango (ogbono) soup

Due to its popularity, all the sampled food blogs typically have at least one recipe for ogbono (wild mango) soup. African wild mango soup, locally called ogbono soup by the Igbos (9ja), and "ugiri" or "apon" soup by the Yorubas (9ja; Dob), is prepared with the nut of African wild mango (Dob; IQ), which is botanically called *Irvingia gabonensis* (Dob) and locally called "oro" by the Yorubas (9ja). African wild mango ("ogbono/apon/ugiri") soup which is generally known as "ogbono/ogbolo" soup in Nigeria (hereafter, ogbono soup), amongst other draw soups like okra soup, is another "offering of draw [or slimy] soup" (IQ; Foods). It has also been noted as one of the most popular local Nigerian dishes in Nigeria (Dob; Sisi; Foods) such that one can find it on many Nigerian restaurant menus' list (Don; 1Q).

From the blog narratives on this soup, ogbono soup has been described as a “very delicious soup” (Afro; Foods) such that one may “over-eat [it] if one is not careful” (Wives). It is also contended that the version of this soup without palm oil tastes great, although its colour is sometimes not very appealing due to the absence of palm oil (Wives). Further, ogbono soup has been described as greatly loved and enjoyed by many because of its slimy consistency texture which makes ingesting morsels of swallow very easy and enjoyable as it makes the lump of swallow slide down the throat easily (Dob; Sisi; Foods; Wives). As a result, when toddlers are first introduced to eating solid foods, they are mostly given this soup since the sliminess of this soup helps them swallow solids with ease (Sisi; Foods). Nevertheless, this soup is consumed by both children and adults mostly at lunch (Don). In fact, it is indicated as one of the most versatile and widely consumed soups in Nigeria since it is very affordable and can be made in large quantities with just a few ingredients. This has earned it the nickname “the poor man’s soup” (Sisi). Simultaneously, it has also been described as very easy and fast to cook (9ja; Wives), but it could also be difficult to cook (Rec). Since it is consumed throughout Nigeria, none of the sampled blogs and bloggers specified its origin story. They generally only mentioned the name of the soup.

Image D. African Wild Mango (Ogbono “Ugiri” / “Apon”) Soup

The components of ogbono soup and its variations

It was discovered from the blogs that the method of preparing and the taste of the ogbono soup differ from tribe to tribe (Dob; Sisi). Regardless of these variations, as shown in *Table 1* below, in order to make ogbono soup, the methods are similar: The lightly aromatic seeds of African wild mango (ogbono/ “oro” seeds) are typically dried in the sun for grinding or purchased whole or in a powder form (9ja; Sisi). While ogbono seeds in their powdery form could turn into little stones if left for a few hours, once added into liquid, they dissolve completely (Dob). The ground ogbono seeds are mixed with

either hot broth or hot water (9ja). This mixture is then used as a thickener (Dob). When mixing the ground ogbono seeds in liquid (which could be hot broth/water), one must ensure to maintain the high viscosity (Don), the trademark of this soup (Dob).

Just like most Nigerian soups, ogbono soup could also be made plain – with or without vegetables (Don; Wives), as some people might prefer leafy vegetables such as fluted pumpkin (“ugu/ugwu”) leaves (Don; 9ja; Sisi; Foods; Wives), as well as adding other thickeners like okra or “egusi” to their ogbono soup (Dob; Sisi; also noted by Foods; further noted in Wives). However, if using fluted pumpkin (“ugu/ugwu”) leaves, it is advised that it should not be the only vegetable one uses. One could add some bitter leaves such as kale (9ja; Sisi; Foods), basil/scented (“efirin/nchuwun”) leaves, or preferably, “uziza” (false cubeb) leaves, which are the most important leaves for making ogbono soup. As they are believed to make a lot of difference in the soup flavour (Don; Foods; Wives), they could instantly transform the aroma, taste and flavour when incorporated into any soup (Sisi). However, when using “uziza” leaves or seeds, or both, some of the bloggers warn that one must be careful with the quantity of pepper added to the soup because “uziza” leaves or seeds have a somewhat spicy flavour (Sisi; Wives). With regard to the various versions there could be on ogbono soup, when making ogbono soup without oil, some bloggers recommend using red bell peppers, locally known as “tatashe(y)” in Yoruba or “Jan tatasei” in Hausa, to brighten the color of the soup. However, ogbono soup could be made without them (Nig.).

Table 1. Categories of (non)essential ingredients of ogbono soup

7 Essential ingredients	3 Non-essential ingredients
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Ground “ogbono” or “oro” seeds b) Liquid: hot broth or water c) Protein of choice: meat, fish, seafood d) Ground crayfish e) Pepper f) Brand seasonings (“Maggi”) or local seasoning: fermented oil seeds (“ogiri okepi/ogiri”) or fermented locust beans (“iru” or “dawadawa”) g) Salt 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Palm oil b) Leaves: (fluted) pumpkin (“ugu/ugwu”) leaves, kale, spinach, “uziza” (false cubeb) leaves etc. c) Onions, which should only be used to steam the proteins

The standard of eating “African wild mango (ogbono) soup”

Within the blog narratives, it was noted that the slimy consistency of ogbono soup is best enjoyed with “morsels of swallow” (Dob; Nig). The blogs also

suggest a wide variety of swallows that could be served with this soup, such as semovita (Afro; Wives), starch or “garri/eba” (Afro; Wives; Don), wheat-meal or “amala” (9ja; Wives), “fufu” (Rec), also spelt “foo-foo” and referred to as “akpu” in Igbo (Foods; Wives), pounded yam referred to as “iyan” in Yoruba (9ja; Afro; 1q; Wives) and many other forms of swallows (Wives).

Image E below illustrates how swallows are eaten with soups in Nigeria. However, one could also eat ogbono soup with other sides like “agidi” (Rec), which is made from fermented maize or rice (Wives), pasta (Sisi), sorghum or millet (Akpapunam et al 2019), “tuwo shinkafa” (Rec) or “tuwo” in short (Wives), a rice pudding common amongst the Hausas in Nigeria (Uwaegbute 1991). To aid weight loss, it has also been advised that it is best for one on a weight-loss journey to eat ogbono soup alone, without adding carbs. However, if one chooses to consume carbs, a fist of swallow is sufficient (Wives).

Image E. Diagram Illustrating the Standard of Eating Staple: Foods/Swallow (e.g. pounded yam (“iyan”) with Soup (as above, ogbono soup) in Nigeria

Throughout the blogs, African wild mango seeds and wild mango soup have been characterised as possessing medicinal qualities. First, it is valued for its fat and rich protein content (9ja). It is also contended to lower one’s cholesterol level (Dob), improve one’s cardiovascular health (9ja), prevent sugars from being stored by the body and aid weight loss (Dob; Afro; 1Q). Due to the perceived pharmacological properties of “ogbono” soup which results from its seeds – African wild mango (“ogbono/oro”) seed, it has been noted across the blog narratives that “ogbono” seeds are now being marketed in capsules (Dob) and will soon be exported for medicinal purposes (IQ).

African wild mango soup is widely enjoyed all over Nigeria, although the methods of preparing it, as well as its characteristics, taste and texture, might differ slightly depending on the region and culture. The health benefits

of the soup are underscored in all the blogs. A close contender with wild mango soup is Okra soup known as “very pocket-friendly” on the blogs.

Spices, flavours, substitutes

Lots of spices and flavours are used in making Nigerian soups, some of which have been franchised in other parts of the world (Foods). Nigerian bloggers highlight the adaptive approach to cooking Nigerian soups, which now often includes non-local ingredients (Dob). This adaptability, noted by bloggers (Don; Nig; Sisi), is due to the versatility of Nigerian cuisine. It allows for adjustments based on personal preferences, the availability of ingredients, and even the possibility of creating new recipes by adding or omitting certain ingredients (Dob; Don). However, while doing so, one does not maintain the authenticity or originality, nor the traditional way of making that dish. As one blogger put it, this means not following “the ancestor’s ways” of making such dishes (Nig).

The information on ingredient substitutes provided by the sampled food blogs can be useful for Nigerians living abroad or in areas where certain local ingredients are unavailable. In doing so, these blogs serve as valuable resources for both diasporic Nigerians and those in Nigeria, offering simplified versions of traditional ingredients that help them reconnect with and adapt their cultural and local recipes (James 2009: 357; Hedge 2014).

Substitutes for unavailable soup ingredients in the diaspora are often chosen based on personal factors like budget, taste preferences, and availability. This is evident in the blogs. For example, a blogger who moved from Nigeria to Canada mentioned that while periwinkle in its shell is considered a luxury in Nigeria, it is challenging to find it abroad. She once found it at a Chinese grocery in Toronto, but it was difficult to find it again (Afro). Another blogger noted that she sometimes omits periwinkles from her soups because they can be expensive in Nigeria (Wives). As a result, people often use ingredients within their “reach” – that are available and affordable. Consequently, many Nigerians abroad use powdered ingredients (like swallows) or dried and frozen forms of ingredients (such as leaves and vegetables like bitter leaf and spinach) (Nig).

Discussion

The blogs analysed feature dashboards, comment sections, and subscription options, allowing users to share their opinions or experiences when bloggers post content, such as recipes. After sharing, bloggers often invite readers to contribute additional information, like their own methods of preparing the dish or comments on specific topics. This practice fosters a virtual community, where not only the blogger shares information but users also participate, similar to blogs about other global cuisines (Hedge 2014). It is noteworthy that

nearly all posts on the selected food blogs had user comments, further reinforcing the idea of community through food. Therefore, Nigerian food blogs are not solely reflections of the individual bloggers; instead, they represent a collective experience of the entire blog community – comprising both bloggers and their readers/users, who co-create these blogs, as seen in other blog genres (Lepkowska-White & Kortright 2017).

Nigeria is rich in vegetation that serves both culinary and medicinal purposes (IQ). Given the vast number of Nigerian dishes, this study focuses on one of the most popular soups, “ogbono” soup, which is enjoyed nationwide and widely among the diaspora. Unlike other soups sampled, none of the blogs or bloggers provided a specific tribe or culture of origin for “ogbono” soup, as it is a dish consumed throughout Nigeria. Therefore, it is considered a traditional Nigerian soup rather than one associated with a particular culture, such as Yoruba or Igbo. The blogs mention the local names for “ogbono” soup in different regions or cultures; for example, the Igbo call it “ogbono/ogbolo” soup, while the Yoruba refer to it as “ugiri” or “apon” soup.

As a result of migration experiences, the cultural practices surrounding the preparation of foods like ogbono soup can change significantly. This can lead to the soup being cooked, consumed, and even named differently among various Nigerian cultures and ethnicities (Etkin 2008: 42). As such, it can be challenging to pinpoint the exact origin of a particular soup, especially when it is widely popular across different regions.

This research revealed that soups are often named after their main ingredient or the vegetables and leaves used in their preparation (Seki and Ono 2014: 489). For example, “African wild mango” (ogbono/ugiri/apon) soup is named after the primary ingredient, the ogbono seed, which serves as a thickener. Variations of this soup are named based on the specific vegetables or leaves used, such as ogbono with pumpkin (ugu/ugwu) leaves. However, if the essential ingredients that give the soup its name are changed or substituted, the name of the soup changes as well. For example, in the preparation of ogbono soup, while some ingredients like vegetables or leaves are optional and can be substituted, the key component is the ogbono/oro seeds. These seeds cannot be replaced with other ingredients, such as okra or melon (egusi), without changing the identity of the soup. If such substitutions are made, the dish is no longer ogbono soup but becomes another type of soup named after the new main ingredient. However, when the primary leaves or vegetables used in making the soup are altered, the generic name of the soup changes to reflect the new ingredient. For example, ogbono soup made with pumpkin (ugu/ugwu) leaves is referred to as “ogbono soup with pumpkin (ugu/ugwu) leaves”. Similarly, ogbono soup made without palm oil is called “oilless ogbono soup”. Therefore, the name of a recipe often indicates the

ingredients used, the location of its preparation, and the availability of those ingredients.

Conclusions

Nigerian food bloggers share their global cuisine with each other and the world. Many of these bloggers are adult women who consider themselves as preserving cultural continuity and authenticity while adapting to their local contexts. Among the various Nigerian soups, we focused on a widely recognised one: African mango soup, which appeared on all the sampled blogs. This soup is prepared by boiling a chosen protein with spices before adding the essential ingredient: ground mango seeds. Although this represents the traditional way of making African mango soup, the flavour can vary depending on the soup base and the different ingredients used.

As a result of migration, substituting ingredients can sometimes lead to a fundamental change in a dish, which may result in a new name since Nigerians often name dishes after their primary ingredient. Whether transmitted orally, textually, or now online, Nigerians have adapted by finding substitute ingredients while striving to preserve the essence of their traditional recipes. As we develop deeper interactions with computers and the internet, food blogging gains prominence as a literary form worthy of investigation. Online recipes not only serve as guides to what people consider authentic dishes but also provide insights into how cultural continuity is maintained and how changes are collectively navigated.

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Exploring the Role of Food in *The Prime of Miss Jean Brodie*

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Abstract

First published in 1961, Muriel Spark's novel The Prime of Miss Jean Brodie is one of the most well-known works of 20th-century British literature, and the book's portrayal of the eponymous Edinburgh schoolmistress and her select clique of pupils during the turbulent 1930s now forms part of contemporary popular culture. After presenting a quick panorama of the author and the work, this article adopts a bipartite approach to describe the role of food at different junctures in the narrative. Initially, it focuses on the types of foods presented and the occasions where they are served (for example, as high teas), thereby seeking to outline whether any wider literary symbolism can be detected. Subsequently, the article examines the unusual role of food and foodstuffs in Miss Brodie's romantic relationship with Mr Lowther, the school's music teacher, a liaison which is ostensibly centred around her focus on him consuming large quantities of food in order to gain weight. These two sets of food-related observations are then interpreted, analysed, and summarised before further suggestions for additional research on the topic are outlined.

Keywords: *20th-century British literature; food in literature; literary depictions of food; Muriel Spark; The Prime of Miss Jean Brodie.*

One of the classics of 20th-century British literature, Muriel Spark's 1961 novel *The Prime of Miss Jean Brodie* has been the subject of many studies from a range of theoretical and thematic perspectives. Inspired partly by Spark's own adolescence in interwar Edinburgh, the book charts the story of Miss Jean Brodie, an iconoclastic schoolteacher at a prestigious girls' school who attempts to imbue her select clique of students with her own non-conformist sentiments and unorthodox worldview, including her latent fascist sympathies. Famous for Miss Brodie's belief that she is in her "prime", the work also became widely known through its later film adaptation, as will be mentioned subsequently. Bearing in mind the breadth of existing scholarship on the novel, this contribution examines two interrelated topics that have seemingly received scant attention to date. After a brief presentation of the novel and its author, in the first instance, it outlines how food is described in the book, before proceeding to examine the curious role of food and the chosen foodstuffs in Miss Jean Brodie's ill-fated relationship with the school's music master, Mr

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Lowther, whom she seeks to “fatten up”, a scheme which ultimately ends in the couple’s breakup. These aspects will be interpreted through reference to the relevant literature, seeking to offer insights into the function that food plays in the work as a whole.

The author and the novel

Muriel Spark (1918-2006) was born in Edinburgh, Scotland, but spent most of her adult life in Italy. One of the most prominent British authors of the 20th century, she was awarded a damehood in 1993, and her long and prolific literary career was distinguished by the production of several critically acclaimed novels, of which perhaps one of the best-known is the subject of this analysis (see British Council Literature 2024).

The Prime of Miss Jean Brodie first appeared in October 1961 in *The New Yorker* magazine, comprising almost the whole issue [1]. Set in the 1930s, and narrated in retrospect, the story – familiar though it may be – is essentially the tale of an unmarried Edinburgh woman in her early forties, Miss Jean Brodie. Having lost her fiancé in the First World War, Miss Brodie teaches at a leading school in the city, the Marcia Blaine School for Girls, where she marshals a group of favourite adolescent pupils into the so-called ‘Brodie’ set, the “*crème de la crème*” whom she aims to mould in her image and likeness. This she does not only through the idiosyncratic content of her classes (she is their form mistress), but also by involving them deeply in many aspects of her personal life outside of school, exerting overbearing power and influence over them and making them privy to a range of intimate details.

Miss Brodie is a distinctly enigmatic and complex figure, with a range of unusual opinions about a wide variety of topics, including politics; these include her own open admiration for the Italian and German fascist movements which were then in the ascendancy on the continent. In creating her exclusive set of pupils, Miss Brodie’s methods of educating her charges are distinctly at odds with the more orthodox approach of the school establishment, and though attempts to remove her are seemingly always scuppered, it is ultimately one of her own proteges (the aptly-named Sandy Stranger) who decides to betray her, leading to the teacher’s forced retirement. To her grave, however, Miss Brodie never discovers who it was.

On its appearance, the novel was an instant success, leading to critical and popular acclaim for its author and her literary oeuvre. Indeed, as noted in an article in *The Guardian* newspaper following Spark’s passing in 2006, the personage of Miss Jean Brodie remains “one of the very few postwar fictional characters to have attained household status” (Wood 2006). As also mentioned in that article, several of the terms featured in the work have passed into wider culture, including the title, which reiterates Miss Brodie’s inimitable belief that she is in her “prime”. The book has been adapted as a stage play, a television

series, and even for the big screen; the film version was directed by Ronald Neame and starred Maggie Smith in the titular role (see Neame 1969). This, too, was critically acclaimed, garnering two Oscar nominations and the Best Actress award for Smith at the 1970 ceremony (see Academy of Motion Picture Arts and Sciences 2024).

Unsurprisingly, the novel's fame and Spark's status as a canonical author means that a variety of research has been undertaken on various facets of the work. These include analysis of the interesting narrative and textual aspects of the novel (e.g., Bower 1990; Brown 2006), spatial and temporal features of the city of Edinburgh as depicted in the work (Keyser 1975; Ray 1978), as well as the omnipresent shadow cast by the role of politics at that time (e.g. Suh 2007). However, in line with the topic of the special issue of this journal, a broad survey of some of this prior research reveals limited focus on the role played by food, especially with regard to its function in a series of key events towards the middle of the book, where, on the rebound from a failed dalliance with Teddy Lloyd, the school's married art master, Miss Jean Brodie sets her sights on the quiet and mellow music teacher, Gordon Lowther.

General remarks on food in the novel

As observed elsewhere (e.g., see Fitzpatrick 2012: 122-123; Manolachi 2021: 87, etc.), critical analysis of the intersection of food and literary studies is a relatively new phenomenon. Yet, as demonstrated by handbooks and edited collections such as *The Routledge Companion to Literature and Food* (Piatti-Farnell & Brien 2018) and *Food Cultures Across Time: Flavours and Endeavours* (Mitrea & Iancu 2021), interest in the topic has spread from the domains of anthropology, culture, and the social sciences to encompass the domain of literary and artistic production. As in real life, the presence of food in literature can serve many roles beyond merely being a necessary source of nourishment. Indeed, in an article in *The New Yorker*, American writer Adam Gopnik outlines his belief that there are four types of food in literature: "food that is served by an author to characters who are not expected to taste it; food that is served by an author to characters in order to show who they are; food that an author cooks for characters in order to eat it with them; and, last (and most recent), food that an author cooks for characters but actually serves to the reader" (Gopnik 2007).

In *The Prime of Miss Jean Brodie*, food indeed serves an important role. To take Gopnik's schema, it certainly appears that the second – i.e. food which is served to the book's protagonists in order to reveal aspects or details about them – could be considered the most relevant. At this juncture, it is important to mention that at the time of the novel's publication in 1961, Britain had only just finally emerged from the privations of rationing, introduced during World War Two to conserve scarce resources, and whose last remnants were only lifted in 1954 (see Imperial War Museums 2024). With the novel's interwar

setting in the milieu of a prestigious girls' school, however, Spark is able to portray some of the culinary luxuries enjoyed by middle- and upper-class members of society at that time. An example can be seen early in the novel, where Sandy, a member of the Brodie set and the one who ultimately 'betrays' her teacher, is celebrating her tenth birthday at her home with her best friend, Jenny, a fellow member of the set:

The speciality of the feast was pineapple cubes with cream, and the speciality of the day was that they were left to themselves. To Sandy, the unfamiliar pineapple had the authentic taste and appearance of happiness, and she focussed her small eyes closely on the pale gold cubes before she scooped them up in her spoon, and she thought the sharp taste on her tongue was that of a special happiness, which was nothing to do with eating and was different from the happiness of play that one enjoyed unawares. Both girls saved the cream to the last, then ate it in spoonfuls.

'Little girls, you are going to be the *crème de la crème*,' said Sandy, and Jenny spluttered her cream into her handkerchief (Spark 2000: 16). [2]

Here, the exotic and luxurious pineapple –“a symbol of nobility, decadence, and the unusual” (Howard 1998: 362) – is the centrepiece of Sandy's birthday afternoon tea. Much prized in colonial times, its spiky rind and unusual flesh has now been rendered into bite-sized morsels, its strong taste evoking a particular sentiment of joy in Sandy. The allusion to happiness continues in the ensuing conversation when the girls observe that they have been told by adults that this time of their lives is supposed to be the happiest part. Indeed, in some ways, as acknowledged by the narrator's retrospective gaze, the years spent under Miss Brodie's tutelage may perhaps have been so, given that in adulthood many of her set have sad fates. This is true of Mary, who perishes in a hotel fire; of the latecomer to the set, Joyce Emily, who runs away from school and is killed in the Spanish Civil War, and of Sandy, who chooses to isolate herself from society by taking holy orders and sequestering herself in a convent.

The decadence of the cream counterpoints the sour taste of the pineapple and provides a segue into Sandy's mimicking of Miss Brodie by the use of her phrase “*crème de la crème*”, the French term which Brodie often uses to instil her charges with a sense of all-round superiority. Yet, in gently mocking their teacher through this impression (of course, natural among schoolchildren), it could also be argued that both girls are aware, even at that tender age, of the frequently ridiculous and eccentric notions that Miss Brodie aims to instil in her select clique.

Sandy and Jenny's conversation then moves from happiness to speculation about the art master, Teddy Lloyd (a paramour of Miss Brodie) and the arrival of his latest child, leading both girls to realise that he and his wife

must have had sexual intercourse in order to have conceived the infant. The girls' seclusion, however, is interrupted by their mothers:

Sandy's mother looked round the door and said, 'Enjoying yourselves, darlings?' Over her shoulder appeared the head of Jenny's mother. 'My word,' said Jenny's mother, looking at the tea-table, 'they've been tucking in!' Sandy felt offended and belittled by this; it was as if the main idea of the party had been the food (Spark 2000: 17).

Indeed, Sandy's reaction to the phrase highlights the signalling aspect of the food as an apparent metaphor, especially with regard to the later developments which take place in the novel. As an ostensible symbol of present happiness, the tart taste of the pineapple combined with the sweetness of the cream could be taken as a bittersweet metaphor for what the future holds for the Brodie set and their complex interactions with their teacher and her world, as well as the general vicissitudes of life once their schooldays have finished.

Though the selected foodstuffs are seldom defined, high teas also serve as a key vector of how Miss Brodie cultivates her set and promotes her influence over them. From the beginning, when the girls enter her class, the reader is aware that "Miss Brodie had already selected her favourites, or rather those whom she could trust; or rather those whose parents she could trust not to lodge complaints about the more advanced and seditious aspects of her educational policy" (Spark 2000: 26). Indeed, the chosen few were singled out: "Miss Brodie's special girls were taken home to tea and bidden not to tell the others; they were taken into her confidence; they understood her private life [...]. They learned what troubles in her career Miss Brodie encountered on their behalf" (26).

Indeed, these occasions continued after the two years when Miss Brodie had ceased to be their form teacher and the girls had progressed to the senior school, for "on most Saturday afternoons, Miss Brodie entertained her old set at tea and listened to their new experiences" (79). The memory of these high teas was to linger long in the mind of her former pupils, with Eunice, who "cut capers for the relief and amusement of the tea parties, doing cartwheels on the carpet" (26), reminiscing to her husband many years later that Miss Jean Brodie "was full of culture. She was an Edinburgh Festival all on her own. She used to give us teas at her flat and tell us about her prime" (27).

Yet this image of elegance and exclusivity conjured up by Miss Brodie's tea parties is later contrasted, for example, by an event which takes place at the house of Teddy Lloyd, the married art teacher and renounced paramour of Miss Brodie. Invited to pose as a model for him, Sandy is horrified when he kisses her unexpectedly. On coming out of his studio, Lloyd's unaware wife Deirdre invites Sandy to stay for tea and biscuits, which takes place among the din of six small children all fighting for attention:

"I've heard such a lot about Miss Brodie from the girls," Deirdre was saying. "I really must ask her to tea. D'you think she'd like to come?"

"No," said Teddy.

"Why?" said Deirdre – not that it seemed to matter, she was so languid and long-armed, lifting the plate of biscuits from the table and passing them around without moving from the low stool on which she sat.

"You kids stop that row, or you leave the room!" Teddy roared.

"Bring Miss Brodie to tea," Deirdre said to Sandy.

"She won't come," Teddy said. "Will she, Sandy?"

"She's awfully busy," Sandy said. (103)

This hubbub and din of bohemian family life is a complete contrast to Miss Brodie's select events, and indeed, it becomes clear that though the essential activity – of having tea – may be the same, the milieu and occasion are totally different. Unlike the high teas that the set are used to with their mentor, from an analytical perspective it appears to be a notably less formal occasion – i.e., just tea and biscuits. Indeed, the whole situation is one that it is impossible to imagine Miss Brodie taking part in; thus, Deirdre's invitation is doomed before she has even verbalised it. Lloyd's feelings for Miss Brodie notwithstanding (Lloyd paints a portrait which resembles her closely), it is clear that she represents an anathema to the chaos of his household, with her love of order and control and general inaccessibility make it a space into which she could never venture. Indeed, the rumours of a kiss between Miss Brodie and Teddy Lloyd are confirmed, many years later, by Sandy when she looks back on another meeting with her former teacher after the war,

[...] when they sat in the Braid Hills Hotel eating sandwiches and drinking tea, which Miss Brodie's rations at home would not run to. Miss Brodie sat shrivelled and betrayed in her long-preserved dark musquash coat. She had been retired before time. She said, 'I am past my prime'. (55-56)

Here, and especially compared with the lavish repasts that will be described subsequently in this article, it is highlighted that even a relatively meagre offering like tea and sandwiches is beyond Miss Brodie's means. Therefore, the food is emblematic of Miss Brodie's reduced circumstances; deprived of her power and influence through being forcibly retired, she is now a quasi-pathetic figure, her once-famous "prime" now receded into time.

Food and the "fattening up" of Mr Lowther

Food is also of key importance towards the middle of the novel. Smarting from her lack of success in her situation with Teddy Lloyd, and though her heart still lies with the art master, Miss Brodie subsequently opts for the quiet figure of the music teacher, Gordon Lowther, a "bashful, smiling bachelor" (86) who

previously relied on the domestic assistance of two spinsters who were also the school's sewing teachers, the Kerr sisters. From the outset of their relationship, and having made short shrift of the Kerrs, she believes that Lowther, who is both slighter and shorter than herself, requires "fattening" up (90). This is a procedure which requires an extensive dietary programme of her own devising.

Interestingly, this occurrence happens at a point in the novel where two of the Brodie set, Jenny and Sandy, notice that their teacher has "a slimmer appearance", drawing the conclusion that "she had lost weight through her sad passion for Mr Lloyd and this noble undertaking of Mr Lowther in his place" (86); with Miss Brodie having turned forty-three, "this year when she looked so much thinner her shape was pleasanter" (89). Yet despite her own weight loss, Miss Brodie seems determined to augment the size of the genial, placid music master, observing that Misses Kerr appeared to be "starving" (88) the man. In spending first Sundays then Saturdays at Lowther's large house in Cramond, she regularly invites her set for tea, in pairs, rotating every three weeks:

One day when Sandy and Jenny were on the visiting list, she gave Mr. Lowther, for tea alone, an admirable lobster salad, some sandwiches of liver paste, cake, and tea, followed by a bowl of porridge and cream. These were served to him on a tray for himself alone, and you could see he was on a special diet. Sandy was anxious to see if Mr. Lowther would manage the porridge as well as everything else. He worked his way through everything with impassive obedience while she questioned the girls. [...] Miss Brodie did not attempt to conceal from her munching host her keen interest in the art master. Mr. Lowther's eyes looked mournful and he ate on. (90-91)

Here, the foodstuffs of choice are a strange mixture of the sophisticated (lobster salad), the standard (liver paste sandwiches and cake), and the somewhat unexpected (the potentially unusual appearance – at least, at high tea – of porridge with cream). Though porridge oats have long been an important base of the traditional Scottish diet (see Robertson 2003), its presence here with the highly calorific (and more luxurious) addition of cream suggests nourishing food for a convalescing invalid or a small child, as well as linking to notions of Miss Brodie's "crème de la crème" – i.e., that just like she aims to transform the minds of her young protégés, she also aims to transform the physical body of her suitor. In this way, it highlights Miss Brodie's dominant role in the relationship, with the modest, gentle music teacher infantilised by her forceful and wilful personality. Evidence of this is displayed after he completes his mammoth repast:

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Miss Brodie poured tea and cast a glance at Gordon Lowther's plate. 'Gordon,' she said, 'a cake.'

He shook his head and said softly, as if soothing her, 'Oh, no, no.'

'Yes, Gordon. It is full of goodness.' And she made him eat a Chester cake, and spoke to him in a slightly more Edinburgh way than usual, so as to make up to him by both means for the love she was giving to Teddy Lloyd instead of to him.

'You must be fattened up, Gordon,' she said. 'You must be two stone the better before I go on my holidays'. (Spark 2000: 92)

Once again, in expecting him to gain almost thirty pounds in a short space of time, Miss Brodie demonstrates her controlling nature. Yet, as illustrated here by her imploring Lowther to eat a Chester cake [3] on top of the vast amount he has already consumed, this surfeit of food is directly announced as compensation for the fact that, in Miss Brodie's heart, her feelings lie with someone else. Various factors have been mooted as to why overfeeding can occur within romantic relationships (see Ogden, Cheung, & Hudson 2022); here, the control she exerts on Lowther's food intake seems to be a project for her, a potential distraction from the love she still feels for Teddy Lloyd. This is underscored by the efforts Miss Brodie makes to demonstrate her new-found domesticity:

Miss Brodie was doing something to an enormous ham prior to putting it into a huge pot. Miss Brodie's new ventures into cookery in no way diminished her previous grandeur, for everything she prepared for Gordon Lowther seemed to be large, whether it was family-sized puddings to last him out the week, or joints of beef or lamb, or great angry-eyed whole salmon. 'I must get this on for Mr. Lowther's supper,' she said to Sandy, 'and see that he gets his supper before I go home tonight'. (Spark 2000: 93).

This quasi-celebratory atmosphere of these feast-like occasions is also highlighted subsequently:

Miss [Sandy and Jenny] waited upon Miss Brodie and saw on the vast old kitchen table the piled-up provisions of the morning's shopping. At one side stood large bowls of fruit, with boxes of dates piled on top of them, as if this were Christmas and the kitchen that of a holiday hotel. (94).

Accordingly, and similarly to her machinations with the Brodie set, everything to do with Lowther is carefully choreographed, whilst he acquiesces. As Suh (2007: 96-97) notes in her analysis of the work from a political lens, Miss Brodie's actions and Lowther's passivity could be viewed as a gendered take on a master/servant relationship. Yet, in this instance, food seems to be a substitution for the inner life of Miss Brodie, which, remains largely inaccessible not only to the other characters in the novel but also to the reader

[4]. As hinted by Kelleher (1976: 84), the presence of excessive quantities of food could be hazarded as a symbol of sexual activity, as Miss Brodie is indeed spending “more often than not the night” (Spark 2000: 86) in Cramond, as exemplified by the Kerrs’ discovery of a nightdress in Lowther’s bedroom.

Yet, Miss Brodie’s controlling and inaccessible nature eventually causes the quiet and amiable Mr Lowther to run out of patience. With Miss Brodie “refus[ing] him all but her bedfellowship and her catering” (104) he becomes “tired of food, for it was making him fat and weary and putting him out of voice” (104). As such, he yearns for a wife who will live with him in Cramond and who shares his passion for golf and singing. Some time after their apparent break-up, his engagement with the science teacher, Miss Lockhart, is announced in the newspaper. This surprise is a situation which causes Miss Brodie great distress, although she consoles herself by noting that compared to the great love she felt for the art teacher, Lowther had “merely been useful”. (113)

Concluding remarks

This brief study has sought to offer insights into the role of food in one of the seminal works of mid-20th-century British literature, *The Prime of Miss Jean Brodie*. In presenting how food is displayed in the novel, this overview has clearly demonstrated that it is utilised as a way to gain deeper awareness of the characters. As such, this accords with Gopnik’s (2007) view of how food can be used to enhance character portrayals in a given literary work. In the first instance, at the birthday party, the pineapple cubes with cream can be interpreted as an interconnected metaphor for happiness and luxury, yet the bittersweet combination of the foodstuffs also heralds the complexities of life that await the Brodie set, as well as Miss Brodie herself.

Another instance is underlined through the occasion of having high tea. Even though the chosen foodstuffs may not warrant individual mention, this is one of the means through which Miss Brodie promulgates her influence over her chosen proteges, as well as signifying social status. As demonstrated above, food plays a key role in the relationship Miss Brodie embarks on with Gordon Lowther; in love with another man, she overcompensates by overfeeding the music master, with food seemingly acting both as a substitute for emotional intimacy and as a way of emphasising her dominance. Accordingly, the portrayal of food is an important component of the plot and characterisation of the novel as a whole, and future research directions could certainly incorporate comparisons with its role in other examples of Muriel Spark’s literary oeuvre.

Notes

[1] For the online version of the original 1961 article in *The New Yorker*, please see Spark (1961).

[2] Though (as mentioned above) the original text of the book is freely available via the website of *The New Yorker*, for ease of citation, the author of this article has opted to use the 2000 Penguin Modern Classics reprint of the 1965 printed version by Penguin Books (see Spark 2000), which differs slightly from the original 1961 publication.

[3] Interestingly, the appearance of the 'Chester cake' in the novel has piqued the curiosity of culinary bloggers with literary interests who have provided recipes for this traditional baked item. For more information, please see Nico and Amy's *Literary Kitchen* (2016) and Selman (2017).

[4] As James Wood noted in his 2006 piece in *The Guardian*, "Around [Miss Jean Brodie's] very thinness as a character we tend to construct a thicker interpretative jacket" (Wood 2006).

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“I was hungered and ye gave me meat”: I n search of the Ultimate Eating Experience in Kazuo Ishiguro’s *The Gourmet*

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Abstract

This article reads Ishiguro’s early screenplay *The Gourmet* (1986) as a work of comic Gothic, blending archetypal Gothic elements (ghosts, cathedrals, crimes) and a dark, eerie, and supernatural atmosphere with elements of comedy and satire. The main character’s quest for the most unusual food on earth, or rather unearthly, serves as a mere pretext to depict a post-Thatcherite London, where homelessness and hunger were at every corner of the street. The screenplay explores two types of hunger: the literal starvation of the poor who have nothing to eat and depend on night shelters for survival, and the insatiable cravings of the rich, embodied by the epicurean Manley, for whom nothing is good enough and who treads the earth far and wide and depletes his great financial resources to satisfy his gastronomic desires. Manley finally manages to reach his goal but is disappointed: the ghost he has eaten does not taste good and he feels sick afterwards. In the end, the two worlds remain separate as they have always been: while the ever-dissatisfied Manley is likely already plotting a new culinary adventure, the hungry remain forgotten and ignored, the real flesh-and-blood ghosts of the story.

Keywords: *Comic Gothic, ghost, gourmet, hunger, tramp*

Introduction

Kazuo Ishiguro, the acclaimed British-Japanese novelist who won the Nobel Prize for Literature in 2017, is best known for his “novels of great emotional force” that reveal “the abyss beneath our illusory sense of connection with the world” (The Nobel Prize in Literature 2017). In addition to these celebrated novels such as *Never Let Me Go* or *The Remains of the Day*, Ishiguro has contributed to world literature through short stories, screenplays, and song lyrics.

His screenwriting, just like most of his novels, is influenced by cinematography, in particular, Japanese movies as Ishiguro himself confesses:

I had a ‘Japanese phase’ in my early twenties when I was hungry about everything about Japanese culture. I found that Japanese filmmakers, such as [Akira] Kurosawa and [Yasujiro] Ozu, had a profound effect on me, and they probably influenced me enormously as a writer (quoted in Matthews 2009: 116).

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His most recent screenplay—*Living* (2022)—is a remake of Akira Kurosawa's film *Ikiru* (1952). A lesser-known work from his early career is the screenplay *The Gourmet*. The script was created for Channel 4, a British television network, as part of a two-teleplay deal which also included *A Profile of Arthur J. Mason* (a Chicago Film Festival Award winner). *The Gourmet* forgoes themes that would later appear in his more famous works, most importantly the obsession with professional fulfilment that would be enlarged upon in *An Artist of the Floating World* (1986) and *The Remains of the Day* (1989). *The Gourmet* was directed by Michael Whyte and produced by Ann Skinner and was broadcast in May 1986. The main character is portrayed by Charles Gray, best known for his role as the villain in the James Bond film *Diamonds Are Forever*.

Like numerous British made-for-television films, *The Gourmet* seems to have slipped into oblivion as it has not been regularly re-aired and is not available on home video. However, following the author's rise to international acclaim, a copy appeared on YouTube in April 2019. The screenplay can be read in *Granta*, a highly esteemed online literary magazine in the United Kingdom, to which Ishiguro had previously submitted a short story—*Getting Poisoned*—but had not been published.

The Gourmet tells the story of an upper-class gastronome who, after having tried it all, becomes obsessed with the ultimate culinary experience. This leads him to all kinds of unusual gastronomic adventures, such as eating garbage and even human flesh. The play foregrounds themes of obsession, the continual quest for perfection, and the sharp divide between the rich and the poor. It also highlights the disappointment and dissatisfaction that the pursuit of ever-greater heights can bring about in those who continually push boundaries without ever finding true contentment.

This article reads *The Gourmet* as a piece of comic Gothic, combining the dark, eerie, and supernatural aspects of Gothic fiction (ghosts, cathedrals, crimes) with the elements of comedy and satire. The main character's quest for the most unusual food turns out to be just a pretext to depict a post-Thatcherite London where homelessness and hunger are at every corner of the street.

Representations of food in Ishiguro's writings

At first glance, food does not hold pride of place in Ishiguro's writing. When it does appear, it has a symbolic meaning often related to memory, identity, class, and human connection.

Food makes a passing appearance in *The Remains of the Day* (1989) when Stevens, the butler, muses on the meticulous preparations and presentation of meals and grand banquets at Darlington Hall. As Stevens's job is literally to wait tables for his master and his guests, the act of serving is a symbol of the divide between two worlds: the servants' and their employers', reflecting the

rigid class-ridden hierarchy and the butler's own sense of duty and identity. While the readers understand the gap between the two classes, Stevens somehow believes in greatness by proximity: because he served tables for the rich and powerful of the day, he, too, is important and contributes to the making of history.

In *Never Let Me Go* (2005), the students' meals at Hailsham are part of their structured, controlled environment. Food in this context helps the guardians to create the illusion of normalcy as opposed to the stark reality of the students' fate: they are mere clones whose organs will be harvested once they have reached adulthood. While they become engaged in typical human activities – eating, attending school, making friends, and even falling in love – they are ultimately genetic copies created to prolong the lives of the originals.

A Family Supper is a less known short story first published in 1982 in the literary magazine *Firebird* and later included in the short story collection *Nocturnes: Five Stories of Music and Nightfall* (2009). The story set in Japan revolves around a family reunion and explores themes of cultural conflict, generational gap, and the prolonged effects of World War II. The patriarch of the family wants to serve fugu fish to his children for dinner although the mother's death was caused by ingesting an improperly cooked fugu fish delicacy. The father, an old-fashioned man, stands for the traditional Japanese values and the honour code of the samurai culture with its suicide connotations, while the protagonist and his sister symbolise the younger generation, influenced by Western ideas and more sceptical of traditional values. The true nature of the father's intentions remains ambiguous throughout the story.

In *Klara and the Sun* (2021), Ishiguro's latest novel, the Sun is represented as a source of nourishment for Klara, the intelligent self-aware robot. While human characters in the novel are subject to genetic modifications and artificial enhancements in a dystopian technologised society, Klara's dependence on the Sun's power reflects the natural world. The irony is obvious: while humans have become more artificial and lost connection with the natural sources of life, the androids depend on nature for their sustenance.

***The Gourmet* – Outline of the plot**

The Gourmet is unlike any of Ishiguro's writings. Usually centred around a quiet and reserved protagonist, his stories are psychological studies in self-delusion and trauma. *The Gourmet* brings to the limelight an extrovert, Manley Kingston, a wealthy and eccentric foodie who becomes obsessed with finding the perfect meal. As he has tasted everything under the sun, his greatest desire is now to eat something which is not of this earth: a ghost.

The movie does not follow the script faithfully. The screenplay opens with a scene from an unnamed church in London that offers a soup kitchen and

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overnight shelter for the city's vagrants. The year is 1904. A close shot focuses on a wooden plaque on the church gate reading:

I was hungered and ye gave me meat
I was thirsty and ye gave me drink
I was a stranger and ye took me in.

The verse is from the Bible, Matthew 25:35 and is part of a larger passage where Jesus describes the final judgment and the separation of the righteous from the unrighteous. It points to the importance of compassion, hospitality, and charity as acts of kindness and care for those in need—such as feeding the hungry, giving water to the thirsty, and welcoming strangers—seen as acts of service to Jesus himself. This Christian teaching, albeit in a satirised form, is to be found at the end of the play after Manley has reached his purpose and feels sick: “I was hungry. I ate. Now I am sick” (Ishiguro 1986).

Against this background, there is a suggestion that a murder might have taken place in the vestry: “a thin line of blood run out from the blackness towards us” as two men carry something heavy between them. Outside, the full moon illuminates an entrance: “This doorway has no door—it is black and ominous, like the gateway to another world” (Ishiguro 1986). The scene features many Gothic elements, such as a crime taking place at night, a full moon, a crypt, and supernatural suggestions.

The time frame then abruptly shifts to 1985: a jetliner is landing, and Carter, a chauffeur described as “sinister and assassin-like” and wearing dark glasses, is waiting for Manley Kingston. His description is equally unsettling:

Manley is in his fifties; large, formidable British upper-class presence. He wears a habitual expression of disdain and boredom, but there is also a maverick streak in his face—a hint of the decadent or criminal (Ishiguro 1986).

As the car drives away, Manley examines a photograph of the church from the previous scene. In his attaché case, there are also two sketch plans of the church and three mortis keys on a ring, each with a large tag—one marked ‘vestry’. Carter has a London working-class accent, and his employer constantly gets his name wrong, which highlights his lack of importance in his employer’s eyes. Manley instructs him to drive to a certain Dr Grosvenor’s residence in a very expensive area of the city. A reception is being held there for Eduardo Perez, who is evidently a gourmet himself and is eager to premiere some of his new dishes. As some of the guests attempt to engage Manley in conversation, he dismisses them, clearly believing himself to be superior.

Manley is received by Dr Grosvenor in his office. His description matches Manley’s and they seem to be cut from the same cloth: “fifty-five, elegant, assured, but also with an air of depravity; he may be a wealthy doctor in private

practice who performs shady operations" (Ishiguro 1986). The books on his desk speak of his interests: *"Eating Rituals of the Aborigines in the Nineteenth Century, Protein and Culture, The Evolution of the Carnivore"*. Dr Grosvenor considers Manley a great pioneer of taste who dares venture into unknown culinary territories:

In the primitive world, man was obliged to go out into an unknown wilderness and discover food. He was unbound then by prejudices about what did and did not comprise the edible. He tried anything he could get his hands on. You, Mr Kingston, are one of the few in modern times worthy of our great pioneers in taste. The rest of us, even someone like myself, we're akin to the womenfolk who waited in the caves worrying about how to cook what the hunters brought back (Ishiguro 1986).

Dr Grosvenor tells him where he can hunt for an edible ghost. Manley goes home and prepares for the hunt by "fastening a small saucepan" (Ishiguro 1986) to his belt. While driving to the church, he remembers Rossi, a Latin American gourmet, who gave him advice on how to catch and prepare a spectre because she had eaten one once: "The process by which one consumes a ghost is not a simple one", but "the taste is exquisite. [...] Like nothing on earth" (Ishiguro 1986). During their encounter, they dine on "soft, pinkish, bloody" joint of what is clearly human flesh.

Having tried it all, Manley wastes no time and goes to the church, hungry not for spiritual food, but for a spectral one which will help alleviate his existential boredom. Equipped with various cooking utensils, a butterfly net, a stove, and a wok, he is ready to capture and cook the ghost that he has been assured haunts the vestry. The church has become a place to shelter and feed the hungry and the homeless. As he waits in a queue, Manley befriends David, a homeless pauper, who waits for his meal. The dialogue between them is satirical because David mistakes Manley for one of his kind. Manley confesses to his insatiable hunger. When David suggests eating garbage from bins, Manley replies he has already done that:

An interesting process takes place inside a refuse bin. A kind of stewing pot of randomness. The chance factor often produces recipes far beyond the capabilities of ordinary imaginations (Ishiguro 1986).

Unable to understand that there are people who are truly hungry because they have nothing to eat, Manley, too, mistakes David for a gourmet who came to the church to eat the ghost that haunts it. In the crypt, the vagrants are all eating:

Some of the men, not far from the trolley, are eating standing up. Others eat sitting on their mattresses, backs against a wall. Not only the environment, but

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the means by which they are obliged to eat makes the whole procedure appear rather disgusting. The men 'drink' the beans from the beaker, then chew, taking an occasional bite from a roll. Some eat hungrily. Others appear to be eating only because they know they should, without really caring if they do or not. Many look mentally and physically exhausted (Ishiguro 1986).

After all the vagrants have fallen asleep, Manley wakes up David to help him satisfy his hunger. Although David does not fully understand what is going on, he agrees, recalling the pangs of real hunger, and leads Manley to the vestry. Upon arrival, David begins to sense that something is off about his new friend when he notices an arsenal of dangling pans, spoons, and other kitchenware: "the stove, the various metallic utensils, the net, jars and containers—and Dr Grosvenor's box" (Ishiguro 1986). Manley then reveals his true intentions: to capture the ghost of a pauper who was murdered in the church eighty years before. With David's assistance, Manley successfully traps the ghost using a butterfly net and a mysterious white powder. To David's horror, Manley then cooks the ghost in his wok. We are not told how the cooked ghost tastes like, only that meat smells "powerful and awful".

The next morning, Manley feels ill and vomits. Some homeless beggar, thinking he has had too much drink, takes pity on him and invites him to sit under his cardboard shelter. It is Manley's turn now to be mistaken for a common drunk just like he had previously mistaken David for a foodie. Manley tells him it was not the drink that had made him sick, but the food: "I was hungry. I ate. Now I am sick," – a rewriting of the Bible verse from a free market capitalistic perspective: "For I was hungry, and you gave me something to eat, I was thirsty, and you gave me something to drink, I was a stranger, and you invited me in". Disappointed, Manley remarks to his driver, who arrives to pick him up, "Life gets so dreary once you've tasted its more obvious offerings" – an oblique critique of the consumerist society as represented here by fine dining, and the hollowness and inevitable boredom that follow once you have obtained the object of desire.

The play ends with David waking up in the church, disgustedly examining the remains of the fried ghost, which he throws away – a twisted interpretation of the proverb "One man's food is another man's poison". Meanwhile, a Rolls-Royce glides through the morning streets of central London. Left feeling frustrated, unsatisfied, and still hungry, Manley may already be on the hunt for new extreme culinary adventures he believes will satisfy his sophisticated cravings.

The Gourmet as a Comic Gothic tale

Ishiguro's writings contain some recognisable Gothic elements. In an interview, Groes asks Ishiguro about the Gothic strand in his writings:

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In the early work, protagonists are haunted by ghosts from the past. The description of the country house in the *Remains of the Day* [1989] sometimes feels a bit 'Gothicky', and in *Nocturnes* [2009] you seem to be engaging with a literary tradition that represents Venice as a place associated with death. (Groes 2011: 248)

One could add other writings to the list. In the short story *A Family Supper*, the ghost of a mother who died from improperly prepared fugu fish haunts the narrative, symbolising unresolved issues from the past. In *A Pale View of Hills*, a mother is haunted by her daughter's suicide and the Gothic mode is manifested through ghostly imagery and an overwhelming atmosphere of horror and dread – what Sloane calls “Etsuko's quasi-gothic dreamscape” (2021: 47). *Never Let Me Go* creates an uncanny atmosphere as the characters, later revealed to be clones raised for organ harvesting, exist in a dystopian world. Ishiguro admits that there are Gothic elements in his work, yet they are more related to “a fascination with the supernatural. But it's an eerie Japanese supernatural” (Ishiguro qtd in Groes 2011: 248-249). Ishiguro even wanted to produce a documentary on Japanese ghosts, but the project was never realised.

In *The Gourmet*, Ishiguro makes use of Gothic imagery to expose and criticize the harsh realities of London in the early 1980s. He does that by blending comedy and satire into what ultimately becomes a tragicomic Gothic tale which is at no point developed into overt horror.

Comic Gothic has received relatively little scholarly attention. At first glance, it may seem at odds with mainstream Gothic horror. Yet, “if Gothic gives textual expression to the fragmentation of the modern subject, then we must recognise that this expression is characterised by irony, scepticism and the enjoyment of comic incongruity even as it engages with anguish, fear, isolation and alienation”. (Horner and Zlosnik 2005: 165-166). Comic Gothic includes elements such as “parody [...]; burlesque; comic grotesque; incongruity; comic inversion of the abject; exploitation of liminality in Gothic fiction” (Horner and Zlosnik 2005:166).

Horner and Zlosnik maintain that “the comic within the Gothic foregrounds a self-reflexivity and dialectical impulse intrinsic to the modern subject” (2005: 4). Gothic texts often use self-parody, intertextuality, and metafiction as tools to critically engage with and respond to various aspects of the contemporary world. While the atmosphere in *The Gourmet* may be Gothic, particularly in the scenes from the church which is described as a “gateway to another world” (Ishiguro 1986) – the underlying tone reflects the grim realities of capitalism, the limitations of Christian charity, and the detrimental social policies of Margaret Thatcher, which exacerbated homelessness in London. The tragicomic narrative thus becomes deeply politicised.

By setting the story in modern London, Ishiguro taps into what is known as contemporary London Gothic, a resurgence of Gothic fiction set in London

in the 1980s and 1990s, represented by authors such as Peter Ackroyd, Christopher Fowler, and Neil Gaiman (Luckhurst 2002). According to Luckhurst, contemporary London Gothic is a product of the fusion of tyranny and farce that defines the city's history of democratic governance—a context that recent 'spectral' interpretations of the Gothic have largely overlooked. Todd maintains that London is reinvented as a "Gothic construct" (1996: 196), haunted by its dark histories. Ishiguro contrasts the London of the 1900s with the modern-day metropolis, shedding light on the impact of Thatcher's damaging policies that weakened the welfare state. He draws from his own experience as a social worker helping the homeless in West London in the late 1970s. By describing both the poor of 1904 and the post-Thatcherite homeless, Ishiguro explores the changing face of poverty in a new globalised world. While the tramp of the early 20th century is described as "old-fashioned" with a "big raggy coat" (Ishiguro 1986), homelessness in Thatcher's London includes all races and age groups:

There are only men here because the church takes in only men. Otherwise, a mixed crowd—multi-racial, all ages. Only a few of them are 'traditional' tramps; most are losing a battle to maintain a conventional 'respectable' appearance. A significant number of teenagers. Their faces are bored and weary. (Ishiguro 1986)

Ishiguro inserts a refined figure from the pinnacle of Western civilisation—the gastronome—into a lowbrow Gothic setting. The screenplay's central metaphor of food and hunger is pushed to its limits: on the one side are the homeless, whose hunger is literal, and on the other is the gourmet—what we would nowadays call a "foodie"—obsessed with chasing the trendiest culinary experiences. Thrust into the world of the impoverished, which he cannot comprehend, Manley mistakenly assumes David is a fellow gourmet upon learning that he, too, eats from the garbage. The ghost itself initially seems to be a flesh-and-blood tramp:

He is middle-aged, small, with a friendly, cheeky face. There is absolutely nothing eerie about him. The tramp rubs his eyes, as though he has just been awakened, then grins sheepishly. (Ishiguro 1986)

The story turns into a play of mistaken identities: Manley is taken for a tramp, David for a gourmet, and the ghost for a real man. Consumed by his quest for the most eccentric dish imaginable, Manley shows utter disdain for the real hunger of the homeless. He remains blind to their existence—they are invisible, the true ghosts haunting the narrative. When Manley mentions he is searching for a ghost, David responds: "I'm the ghost around here. Could vanish tonight, nobody would notice" (Ishiguro 1993).

Conclusions

In *The Gourmet*, Ishiguro reinterprets hunger not as a basic physiological need but as a refined pursuit of the “great pioneers in taste” (Ishiguro 1986). This raises the question: whose hunger is more real – the tramp’s or the gourmet’s? While the former seeks merely to fill an empty stomach, the latter’s hunger represents an artist’s yearning for increasingly sophisticated (culinary) experiences. When a homeless man empathetically tells Manley that he understands what it feels like to be hungry, Manley retorts, “You have no idea what *real* hunger is” (Ishiguro 1986) (emphasis in the original). Manley’s dismissal of the tramp’s hunger as “not real” symbolises the moral detachment of the upper class. In his pursuit of increasingly refined and exclusive experiences, Manley embodies the upper class’s decadence and excess and exemplifies a kind of moral blindness to be found in the neoliberal obsession with individualism and consumerism. His ultimate act of consuming the tramp’s ghost (i.e. the rich eat the poor) literalises the exploitation and disregard for the poor. The worlds of the rich and the poor are meant to stay apart, as always: while the ever-dissatisfied Manley is likely already plotting a new culinary adventure, the hungry remain forgotten and ignored, the real flesh-and-blood ghosts of the story.

Written just a few years after the end of Thatcher’s term as prime minister, *The Gourmet* uses Gothic comedy to satirise and critique her neoliberal social policies which further impoverished the poor. Thus, the tramp, a victim of a violent and exploitative system which literally killed him to harvest his organs for research, is killed again, this time to be consumed as a delicacy by some rich gourmet. Not even in death are the poor equal with the rich. Central to this satire of a decadent society is the balance between horror and absurdity inherent in the Gothic comic.

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“The Children in the Apple-Tree”: The Meaning of Fruits in T.S. Eliot’s Poetry

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Abstract

Since J. Alfred Prufrock asked the question “Do I dare to eat the peach?”, T.S. Eliot’s poems, essays and plays have provided food for thought for generations over the past century. Literary critics, historians and scholars of cultural modernity have occasionally noted the poet’s interest in depicting and commenting on how modern individuals perceive sources of nourishment, their transformative power and the consequences of their absence. This paper draws on previous studies of his work to explore and highlight the representation of fruits, fruition and fruitlessness in several of his poems. It also reconsiders earlier interpretations, shedding light on missing aspects and bringing attention to new insights into poems from his earliest to his last collections. The analysis employs several interpretive techniques, including symbolic analysis to uncover how fruit imagery in Eliot’s work reflects themes of existential questioning, spiritual emptiness and societal critique. It situates this symbolism within the broader modernist exploration of alienation and renewal. Additionally, the study assesses Eliot’s literary influences, such as European satire and French symbolism, and their impact on his thematic concerns. An ecocritical perspective is also used to examine how Eliot’s portrayal of food and nature engages with early 20th-century ecological and cultural issues, reconsidering materialism and spirituality.

Keywords: *modernist poetry, T. S. Eliot, food studies, ecocriticism, close reading*

Introduction

In his 1913 essay “Inconsistencies in Bergson’s Idealism,” T.S. Eliot (2014) reflects on the nature of time, writing that “nothing essentially new can ever happen; the absolute, as Bradley says, bears buds and flowers and fruit at once” (81). This metaphor, which challenges the linear progression of time, offers a vision where beginnings, processes, and outcomes are inextricably linked, reflecting a holistic understanding of life and reality. This interconnectedness, often found in Eliot’s work, invites a closer examination of recurring motifs, such as fruit, which subtly yet significantly contribute to the thematic depth of his poetry.

Despite the growing body of research on T. S. Eliot’s use of food imagery, there remains a noticeable gap in the literature specifically addressing the symbolic role of fruit in his poetry. While scholars like Etienne Terblanche

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(2016) and Jeremy Diaper (2023, 2018) have provided valuable insights into Eliot's ecological concerns and culinary references, the nuanced symbolism of fruit has been largely overlooked. The collection *Gastro-modernism* (2019), edited by Derek Gladwin, features only two articles discussing food in Eliot's poetry. Even Nicola Humble's comprehensive study, *The Literature of Food* (2020), which covers the thematic implications of food in modernist literature, only briefly touches upon fruit imagery in Eliot's work. Regarding Eliot's poetry, Humble emphasises the associations of fruit with "self-denial, internationalism, and religion" (146) and notes that in his "increasingly austere later poetry fruit imagery is more and more dried up, purged of its juices" (147), though such observations seem somewhat hasty.

This paper aims to fill this gap by offering a focused analysis of the representations of fruit in nine of Eliot's poems, spanning his entire career. Through close reading and cultural interpretation, informed by recent advances in food studies, this analysis will challenge existing interpretations and reveal overlooked dimensions of Eliot's fruit imagery. By doing so, the paper will demonstrate that, although not a central theme, fruit plays a surprisingly significant role in his poetry, particularly in relation to other food-related themes. The selected poems, which reference fruit explicitly, include three from his debut collection, two satires from his 1920 collection, *The Waste Land*, *The Hollow Men*, *Ash-Wednesday* and *Four Quartets*.

Fruits, fruition and fruitlessness

Collected in his 1917 debut volume, "The Love Song of J. Alfred Prufrock" (1915) is a dramatic monologue in which T. S. Eliot explores a prevalent modernist theme: the struggles that occur when innate human desires for connection are obstructed by rigid social norms. He accomplishes this by feeding on literary techniques coming from different cultures – French symbolism, Dante's poetry, Ancient Greek satire etc. – to critique his own Anglophone culture, originally the Bostonian society, as he seeks to find his place in the world.

The main personage, Prufrock, is a timid, indecisive young man, who asks himself both metaphysical and mundane questions, demonstrating a subjectivity at odds with the surrounding reality: "Do I dare / Disturb the universe?" (6), "Then how should I begin / To spit out all the butt-ends of my days and ways?" (7). He feels uncomfortable and insecure in a normative society and his self-interrogations express the tensions of the time. These are reflected in Eliot's literary technique: the skilful combination of the most serious themes with everyday details. One such matter-of-fact aspect is the reference to food, a topic usually neglected in the literary studies of the past.

Prufrock enters "sawdust restaurants with oyster shells" (5), where he sees "hands / That lift and drop a question on your plate" (6). Events,

important or not, occur “before the taking of a toast and tea” (6) or “after the novels, after the teacups, after the skirts that trail along the floor” (8). When he describes himself as taking the temporal dimension into account, he admits that: “I have measured out my life with coffee spoons” (6) and “I have bitten off the matter with a smile” (8). The only fruit mentioned in the poem is a peach:

I grow old . . . I grow old.
I shall wear the bottoms of my trousers rolled.
Shall I part my hair behind? Do I dare to eat a peach?
I shall wear white flannel trousers, and walk upon the beach.
I have heard the mermaids singing, each to each. (9)

The question about the peach has been interpreted in many ways over the decades: trivialisation of great dilemmas (Gish, 1981: 17), “puritanical or valetudinarian fears” (Pinion, 1986: 77), “self-paralysing indecisiveness” and inability to ask meaningful questions (Swarbrick, 1988: 21), dramatic self-awareness verging on pathos (Sigg, 1989: 105), nervousness about what is correct (Raine, 2006: 69), “fear of making the wrong choices” (Bloom, 2011: 97), repression of desire (Perloff, 2011: 259), or “a kind of endless sensitivity, a neurosis” or “political correctness” in an ecological framework (Terblanche, 2016: 30). Such diverse interpretations of the peach – spanning moral, psychological, and natural concerns – demonstrate the universal power of poetry to illuminate essential issues. As literary historians and critics often highlight, Prufrock, named after a furniture business in St. Louis, is not Eliot, but a literary artefact that illustrates an overly cautious personality, self-conscious and concerned with appearances, mirroring the rise of psychology as a scientific discipline. According to British writer Wyndham Lewis (1967), Eliot was:

A sleek, tall, attractive transatlantic apparition – with a sort of Gioconda smile. [...] a Prufrock to whom the mermaids would decidedly have sung, one would have said, at the tops of their voice – a Prufrock who had no need to “wear the bottom of his trousers rolled” just yet; a Prufrock who would “dare” all right “to eat a peach” – provided he was quite sure that he possessed the correct European table-technique for that ticklish operation. (282-283)

Apart from these considerations, the poem sets the peach in contrast with “the marmalade” (8), which subtly illustrates the difference between nature and culture. Critic Lee M. Jenkins (2019) cogently demonstrates that Eliot aligned himself with the party of culture, like Wallace Stevens and unlike D.H. Lawrence, who aligned himself with the party of nature. According to him: “Modernist poetry’s polarised representation of and relationship to food anticipates Claude Lévi-Strauss’s anthropological binary of ‘the raw’ and ‘the

cooked'." (183) The critic concludes that Modernist poets' interest in how food is consumed reflects their intense focus on the connection between art, ritual, and reality. While marmalade in English is typically linked to citrus fruits, its history and usage reveal that it can also be made of other fruits. The presence of peach and marmalade in the same poem hints at the emergence of peach marmalade as a popular product in the 19th and 20th centuries, thanks to the rise of home canning. Historian C. Anne Wilson (2000) cites a recipe from as early as 1587 and an 1884 price list that features it. While peach marmalade became widely popular more recently, it has been enjoyed for centuries.

The simplicity of Prufrock's question opens the door to possible other readings. From an economic point of view, the poet's Hamletian concern with (not) eating the peach prefigures the contemporary mass production of fruits, the role of food chains in making them available to urban consumers and all the associated ecological issues. By documenting Eliot's engagement with the organicist movement [1] in Britain, Jeremy Diaper (2018) demonstrates the poet's agricultural sensibility, based on the conception of culture and agriculture as mutually independent. In plus, from a historical standpoint, eating a peach symbolises an understanding of the Orient. Originating in Eastern China, extensively grown in Persia and later introduced to Europe before being brought to the Americas in the 16th century, the peach has a rich transnational trade history, an alternative to the bellicose history of the First World War when the poem was published and when issues like nutritional health and food shortages, rationing and logistics gained prominence in the public sphere.

In "Rhapsody of a Windy Night" (1917), an early urban nocturne inspired by French symbolism and included in his debut collection, the protagonist tramps the streets, aimless and fearful, imagining that the street lamps can talk. A Prufrock of sorts, the speaker is intent solely on making himself utterly miserable, reminding us of George Orwell's first book, *Down and Out in Paris and London* (1933). Bleak and melodic, not enthusiastic as a rhapsody should be, the poem portrays a world filled with loneliness and alienation, tinged with regret and bitterness, and marked by an underlying sense of vice and cruelty. In reaction to this urban nightmare, the poet crafted a new tone, replacing the excesses of romantic sentimentality with a blend of understated bitterness and resignation, creating an unexpectedly celebratory aesthetic.

The reader's senses are assaulted by the speaker highlighting images, sounds, tastes, smells and touches. Images: "Midnight shakes the memory / As a madman shakes a dead geanium." (18), "A broken spring in a factory yard" or "A washed-out smallpox cracks her face, / Her hand twists a paper rose" (19). Sounds: "Every street lamp that I pass / Beats like a fatalistic drum"

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(18). Taste: the cat that “devours a morsel of rancid butter” (19). A blend of several mingling smells:

Smells of chestnuts in the streets,
And female smells in shuttered rooms,
And cigarettes in corridors
And cocktail smells in bars. (20)

The poem ends with allusions to crime, bringing a sense of order to the darker aspects of reality that otherwise gnaw at the edges of consciousness, unsettling the individual without offering clarity: “The last twist of the knife.” (ibid) These sensations are not meant to be pleasant. However, the careful crafting of the language transforms what might seem like stark ugliness into genuinely beautiful art. The frugality of enjoying roasted chestnuts is there to complement the performance.

Can fruit be used to express dissatisfaction? Which one is the most suitable? The satirical poem “Mr. Apollinax” (1916), present in Eliot’s debut collection, employs a technique that alienates readers while simultaneously making them accomplices to an inside joke. The Greek nickname, the use of “Mr.” and the fact that he visited the United States, not America, are all hints that the personage may be a celebrity. The Ancient Greek epigraph from the satirist Lucian of Samosata suggests Mr. Apollinax might be a man of letters or a scholar in the humanities.

According to literary historians, the poem may have been written as a caricature of Bertrand Russell, whom Eliot met at Harvard in 1914, when the analytic philosopher was a visiting professor. The reason was that his former teacher and Eliot’s first wife had an affair at the time when the young couple struggled financially and worried about their future. “His laughter tinkled among the teacups” (25) is a line that describes the culprit in a catering context, as the carefree master of his stifling social circle. The poet’s irritation at being cuckold produces radical language, suggestive of an imaginary decapitation: “I looked for the head of Mr. Apollinax rolling under a chair” (ibid). The atmosphere of socialising and eating out is described in culinary terms: “Of dowager Mrs. Phlacuss, and Professor and Mrs. Cheetah, / I remember a slice of lemon, and a bitten macaroon” (ibid). While name-dropping is a common social tactic, cooking up ludicrous names reduces its typical impact and shifts the critique toward the persons being nicknamed. Since someone who proves to be disappointing can be informally called a lemon in the English language, the poem, along with others from the same first collection, is part of the poet’s battle to resist psychological distress and rotten social conventions.

A work inspired by French poet Théophile Gautier’s “L’Hippopotame”, the satirical poem “The Hippopotamus” (1917), published in his 1920 volume, suggests an intrinsic distrust in modern religion by placing values like hope

and humility, faith and community in a humorous and surprising framework. Its polemical and unapologetic stance suggests its main concern is not salvation, but being in the world and understanding its complexity. The tight rhymes of each quatrain and the unusual transitions and juxtapositions illustrate how novelty and zest can sprout within the confines of conventional religious discourse.

An African animal, the hippopotamus “is merely flesh and blood”, “susceptible to nervous shock”, while the Church “can never fail / For it is based upon a rock” and “need never stir / To gather in its dividents” (43), which sets the figure of the animal and the religious institution in opposition, with the former much weaker than the latter. What they have in common is human characteristics, a mix of anxiety and a capital-oriented attitude. The poetic juxtapositions suggest that, whereas the individual cannot really enjoy the bounty of life, the institution apparently can, as the following stanza explains:

The 'potamus can never reach
The mango on the mango-tree;
But fruits of pomegranate and peach
Refresh the Church from over sea. (ibid)

Approaching the poem from a new materialist and ecocritical standpoint and focusing on the idea of immersion, Etienne Terblanche (2016) posits that Eliot's view on the problem of the church is “its misappropriation of matter” and that “Eliot's God is ecological, not patriarchal” (95). The above stanza suggests that reaching for fruit, traditionally viewed as a sinful act in Christian doctrine, is actually a natural and essential part of earthly existence. Eliot's interpretation of Christianity contrasts sharply with conventional views, proposing that acknowledging and engaging with earthly desires and instincts, like a hungry creature reaching for fruit, is more meaningful than denying them. The metaphor of reaching the fruit, while not literal, emphasises the value of earthly engagement over spiritual detachment.

The individual's helplessness and needs are further set in contrast to the power of the faith-based community, in the context of hunger:

The hippopotamus's day
Is passed in sleep, at night he hunts,
God works in a mysterious way -
The Church can sleep and feed at once. (43)

Both the individual and the community need rest and food, which suggests their essential interdependence despite the contradiction reflected in the simultaneity of ritualistic sleep and eating. The humanisation of animal life and

the animalisation of human life through poetic discourse question the effects of human intervention in nature and in communities from elsewhere (via evangelism, humanitarian work, trade, etc.) and situate the non-human kingdom in a new transcendental light.

Included in his second volume, "Sweeney Among the Nightingales" (1918) is set in a restaurant and evokes a cosmopolitan paranoid world. A focus on the culinary vocabulary reveals uneasy relationships between people and threatening conspiratorial gamesmanship:

The silent man in mocha brown
Sprawls at the window-sill and gapes;
The waiter brings in oranges
Bananas figs and hothouse grapes;

The silent vertebrate in brown
Contracts and concentrates, withdraws;
Rachel *née* Rabinovitch
Tears at the grapes with murderous paws; (51)

Animalised as a "silent vertebrate", Sweeney is a persona Eliot invented to refer to a prototype of the modern savage, instinctual and mind-numbing. He is served exotic fruits like oranges and bananas, and grapes grown in artificial conditions, which expresses the awareness that they are produced far away and shipped to England, or they need to be planted in greenhouses before being acclimatised to colder conditions. Dwelling still on fruit imagery, the next stanza exposes two opposing forms of consumption, low versus excessive: while the man is reserved and introspective, the woman's reaction is filled with strong emotions. From a formal point of view, the tension between the mechanicism of food production and people's animality is captured in galloping prosody.

In *The Wasteland* (1922), the scarcity of fruit imagery encapsulates the central themes of the poem: the spiritual barrenness and fragmentation of modern society, yearning for renewal and redemption. The following lines from "The Fire Sermon" introduce Mr Eugenides:

Under the brown fog of a winter noon
Mr Eugenides, the Smyrna merchant
Unshaven, with a pocket full of currants
C.i f. London: documents at sight,
Asked me in demotic French
To luncheon at the Cannon Street Hotel
Followed by a weekend at the Metropole. (63)

With Eliot's note to the poem ("c.i.f. London" indicating "cost, insurance, and freight to London"), the currants can be interpreted as the goods Mr. Eugenides is trading. Given Mr Eugenides's proposition to the unnamed narrator to have lunch together and spend a weekend in Brighton, they can also be understood as a metaphor for conviviality in cosmopolitan circumstances. Smyrna, known today as the Turkish city of Izmir, was an Ancient Greek city, which has been historically associated with ethnic diversity, religious heterogeneity and international trade. This episode may be part of the recurring theme of sterility and unfulfilled desire, such as Lil's abortions, the typist's encounter with the young man and the withered vitality of the Fisher King, the protagonist of the poem, whose helplessness has brought desolation to the wasteland. However, the "pocket full of currants" also suggests small yet plentiful resources gathered from distant, fertile lands. From a gastronomic point of view, currants are both a nutritious snack and a versatile ingredient in cooking and baking.

Eliot's concern with decay and rebirth draws on his interest in works like *The Golden Bough* (1890) by James G. Frazer and *From Ritual to Romance* (1920) by Jessie L. Weston, which he mentions in his notes to *The Wasteland*. For example, the section "The Burial of the Dead" ends with dilemmas about the meaning of death rituals, when there is no certainty of resurrection:

'That corpse you planted last year in your garden,
'Has it begun to sprout? Will it bloom this year?
'Or has the sudden frost disturbed its bed? (57)

Set against the postwar historical context, these lines question whether large-scale conflict is essential for transformation and encourage readers to consider alternative paths to renewal. The poem's imagery of burial reflects the Grail and Christian myths, both rooted in ancient vegetation and scapegoating rituals. Furthermore, the poem's focus on material fruitlessness—rather than abundance and consumption—highlights modern issues such as resource scarcity, mass distribution, and waste.

In the five sections of "The Hollow Men" (1925), Eliot explores themes of spiritual desolation, emptiness and the failure of modern society to find meaning or redemption. The poem portrays a group of "stuffed men", trapped in a liminal state between life and death, unable to act decisively or achieve spiritual fulfilment. The imagery and tone of the poem convey a sense of despair since the personages are depicted as disconnected from both the divine and the human.

The last section of the poem begins and ends with a distorted version of a nursery rhyme. In the first stanza, the usual "mulberry bush" is replaced with the "prickly pear", creating an effect of defamiliarisation:

Here we go round the prickly pear

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Prickly pear prickly pear
Here we go round the prickly pear
At five o'clock in the morning. (83)

The dance round the prickly pear has been understood as “phantasmagoric” (Simpson 1975, 165), “disillusionment with the world” (Pinion 1986, 171), “a purposeless absurdity” (Swarbrick 1988, 48), “behaviour that is enigmatically empty” (Raine 2006: 20), the “degradation of essential ritual” (Crawford 1987, 154) etc. All these views may have been based on the presupposition that, unlike mulberries, the prickly pear is inedible, disturbing and menacing. And going round and round in circles means engaging in a repetitive or futile activity that leads to no progress or resolution, to no fruition.

Nevertheless, prickly pear is indeed a real fruit, a cactus known as *opuntia*, with edible varieties found in hot climates. Its small spines must be carefully removed by peeling. The contrast between the fruit’s perceived inedibility and its actual use in various cultures encourages a deeper understanding of the poem’s themes. From one angle, cyclical patterns can be found globally, even in regions where prickly pears grow. From another angle, it might critique aimless pursuits, highlighting the relation between rootedness and rootlessness.

The poem ends with another distorted stanza, in which the usual lines “This is the way we wash our face / comb our hair / brush our teeth etc.” are changed into “This is the way the world ends” (84). Such a transformation subverts the original purpose of the children’s song, intended to teach proper behaviour in the modern world. By doing so, the poem questions how fundamental knowledge about life—and death—is transmitted across generations and advocates for radical creativity in navigating cultural differences.

The main message of *Ash Wednesday* (1930), a poem reflecting Eliot’s conversion to Anglicanism in June 1927, is the spiritual struggle of renouncing earthly desires and bodily temptations to seek divine grace and renewal. Fruits, therefore, are of a metaphysical nature. The second section reflects the poet’s memory of spiritual rebirth, not as an emergence of a new self, but as a dissolution. The poet, who believes in “the Garden / Where all loves end” (90), remarks almost joyfully:

And I who am here dissembled
Proffer my deeds to oblivion, and my love
To the posterity of the desert and the fruit of the gourd. (89)

In the Biblical story, after Jonah reluctantly delivers God’s message to Nineveh, he sits outside the city, awaiting its fate. God provides a gourd plant to give him shade but then causes it to wither overnight. Jonah laments the death of

the plant, and God uses this to teach him about compassion and the value of life. Therefore, in Eliot's view, "the fruit of the gourd" is the leap of faith required when one has reached their breaking point, or everything seems to fall apart.

The fifth section concludes with an interrogation left without a question mark, invoking a figure capable to forgive and pray for others regardless of circumstances:

Will the veiled sister between the slender
Yew trees pray for those who offend her
And are terrified and cannot surrender
And affirm before the world and deny between the rocks
In the last desert between the last blue rocks
The desert in the garden the garden in the desert
Of drouth, spitting from the mouth the withered apple-seed. (95)

"The desert in the garden the garden in the desert" is more than clichéd mystical wordplay. It signifies that, as the fall of man was present in Eden, so too can salvation be found in the most barren places. The fall of humanity, symbolized by "the withered apple-seed", is said by some theologians to have led to the confusion of languages. Eliot appears to share this view. In his depiction of corrupted language, there is no dominant authority, only a multitude of conflicting individual voices. Thus, spitting out the withered apple-seed represents speaking a fallen, distorted language. What is the role of "the veiled sister" in this context? Replacing the question mark with a full stop implies that the answer lies within the question itself: a leap of faith. Moreover, since poetic language allows for interpretation, "the veiled sister" could represent any woman or the feminine aspect within everyone—the other self that might lie hidden behind the mask of personality. The line "spitting from the mouth the withered apple-seed" conveys a sense of profound emptiness that someone might feel and the rejection of convictions that have lost their potential for regeneration. It underscores the desolate and arid spiritual state depicted in the poem, where even potential growth, symbolized by the apple-seed, is rendered futile.

The third section of *Four Quartets*, "The Dry Salvages" (1941) begins with a striking image of the brown river-god Mississippi, evoking Eliot's childhood in the industrial city of St. Louis:

I do not know much about gods; but I think that the river
Is a strong brown god—sullen, untamed and intractable,
Patient to some degree, at first recognised as a frontier,
Useful, untrustworthy, as a conveyor of commerce; [...]
His rhythm was present in the nursery bedroom,
In the rank ailanthus of the April dooryard,

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In the smell of grapes on the autumn table,
And the evening circle in the winter gaslight. (193)

The analogy of the river to a deity was not new: in the 1830s, Alexis de Tocqueville (2010) wrote that the Mississippi was “like a god” (35). What was new was Eliot’s poems about his nostalgia for the time spent with his family. In a letter to his mother, on 14 October 1917, Eliot (1988) wrote: “I always think of a return to St. Louis as meaning Concord grapes on the table in the blue fruit basket.” (304) In a letter to his friend, John D. Hayward, on 27 December 1939, Eliot wrote: “One of my strongest associations is that of the smell of grapes and of the charwoman (an old family retainer) who always greeted me on returning in the autumn to our house in St. Louis.” (Eliot, 2015: 965) Thus, “the smell of grapes on the autumn table”, invigorated by the river’s influence and other aspects of urban life, functions similarly to Proust’s madeleine, evoking voluntary memories of youth.

Another fruit mentioned in “The Dry Salvages” is the apple as a symbol of sin and the fruit of knowledge. The second part addresses not only the themes of time and timelessness but also explores the theme of death, serving as a reminder of the Second World War, encompassing the death of the body, psyche and spirit. What remains relevant with the passing of time is rather abstract:

The moments of happiness – not the sense of well-being,
Fruition, fulfilment, security or affection,
Or even a very good dinner, but the sudden illumination – (196)

Despite the inevitability of death, this section fosters hope in what endures beyond it. In the conclusion of the second part, “the bitter apple and the bite in the apple” symbolise human errors and the awareness of them, while time is depicted as a force that both annihilates and safeguards:

Time the destroyer is time the preserver,
Like the river with its cargo of dead negroes, cows and chicken coops,
The bitter apple and the bite in the apple.
And the ragged rock in the restless waters,
Waves wash over it, fogs conceal it;
On a halcyon day it is merely a monument,
In navigable weather it is always a seamark
To lay a course by: but in the sombre season
Or the sudden fury, is what it always was. (196-197)

The fragment reflects T. S. Eliot’s life in the United States, with the Mississippi River flooding the valley where his hometown of St. Louis is located, and the rocky coastal area known as the Dry Salvages, where the poet spent his

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summers, and which inspired the title of the section. The second line evokes the history of racism in the United States, recalling the time when African-Americans were treated as property. At the same time, the river imagery evokes Huckleberry Finn and Jim's friendship from Mark Twain's classic novel, and it also reminds us that Langston Hughes, a contemporary of Eliot, was born in the same state.

The third part of "The Dry Salvages" contains a passage referring to fruition that strongly leans toward conceptual exploration. The use of the verb "to fructify" and of the collocation "fruit of action" questions ideas like fertility and growing:

At the moment which is not of action or inaction
You can receive this: "on whatever sphere of being
The mind of a man may be intent
At the time of death" – that is the one action
(And the time of death is every moment)
Which shall fructify in the lives of others:
And do not think of the fruit of action.
Fare forward. (198)

This passage emphasises the concept of living with mindful awareness, where each moment has the potential for transformation and influence on others, and encourages focusing on the journey rather than its outcomes. Different forms of death—real or imaginary—thus become opportunities to grasp transcendence and envision possible rebirth.

The fourth and final section of *Four Quartets*, "Little Gidding" (1942), also published during World War II, opens with a hopeful line that suggests new beginnings amid the cold: "Midwinter spring is its own season." (201) Despite contradictions, hope still exists: "Between melting and freezing / The soul's sap quivers." (idem) The second part of the section is an encounter with "a familiar compound ghost" (204). This has been interpreted as an alter ego of the poet or a composite spirit of poets and other significant figures, who inspired Eliot's work. The two have a dialogue about the role of language in a changing world, in which the metaphor of the fruit is used to convey meanings:

Last season's fruit is eaten
And the fullfed beast shall kick the empty pail.
For last year's words belong to last year's language
And next year's words await another voice. (204)

First, the cold friction of expiring sense
Without enchantment, offering no promise
But bitter tastelessness of shadow fruit
As body and soul begin to fall asunder. (205)

The final reference to fruit in *Four Quartets* is an apple tree. “Little Gidding” concludes with a meditation on the cyclical nature of life, knowledge, and spiritual rediscovery. It suggests that, after searching far and wide, we return to our starting point, but with newfound understanding. The place where we began is now seen with fresh eyes, as if for the first time, symbolized by “the children in the apple-tree” (209)—a representation of innocence and truth, unnoticed because they are not directly sought. Their presence is felt in moments of quiet reflection, like the calm between waves—a metaphor for the pauses in life where deeper understanding can emerge. While the world has changed, Little Gidding has largely remained the same.

Conclusions

As both a poet and philosopher, T.S. Eliot used fruit imagery as a powerful symbolic tool that reflects the complex interplay of existential, spiritual and societal themes central to his modernist vision. The peach, for example, symbolises internal struggle against societal norms, reflecting broader psychological and cultural issues. Vivid sensory imagery turns urban alienation into a dissonant yet harmonious aesthetic, while fruits like the lemon are used satirically to critique conformism and express personal disappointments. Eliot juxtaposes material and spiritual elements to comment on modern religion, and exotic fruits emphasise global commerce and modern savagery. Fruits like currants and prickly pears represent spiritual barrenness or existential despair, particularly in the context of cultural differences. In his later works, Eliot delves deeper into themes of memory, time, and spiritual renewal, highlighting the cyclical nature of existence and the potential for rebirth amidst conflict and oblivion.

Notes

[1] Organicism is an agricultural and philosophical movement emphasising the interdependence of soil fertility, crop health, and human well-being, advocating for natural farming methods and coexisting harmoniously with nature’s laws.

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Pre-Raphaelite Food Politics or, Feasting on Desire: John Everett Millais, Social Norms and Women

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Abstract

Renowned for his infamous painting *Christ in the House of his Parents* (1849-1850) or for *The Tragic Story of Ophelia* (1851-1852) which brought him domestic and international fame during his lifetime as a British painter, John Everett Millais (1829-1896) is known as one of the founders of the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood (1848), a group of young and idealistic artists determined to instil vibrating energy and novelty into contemporary art which they considered to have been stifled by the prevailing conventions of the Royal Academy. Millais's works display microscopic attention to pictorial realism and manifest an almost fetishistic attention to photographic detail; and yet, it is despite this covert technique (or maybe particularly due to it!) that Millais' art manifests a certain politics springing from an exceptional daring in the way his paintings function as genuine social and cultural parables. Therein, the current paper looks into three of Millais' paintings (namely, *Bridesmaid* (1851), *Isabella* (1868), and *The Captive* (1882)), as mirrors that reflect and challenge while obliquely commenting on and criticising Victorian social norms (particularly those related to gender, gender roles, binary oppositions and desire) through the depiction of food. Hence, the main focus of the paper is not merely uncovering Millais' food aesthetics and the way he uses food as a subject of aesthetic interest but rather looking into Millais' food politics (and poetics) and the way food becomes a vehicle for expressing deeper societal concerns, class distinctions, moral lessons, and cultural exchanges.

Keywords: pictorial realism, social and cultural parables, food politics, desire, Victorian norms, societal concerns, class distinctions, moral lessons, cultural exchanges

Of food and meaning(ful) voices

Forever and deeply entangled in our experiences of life or in our mental representations of the world *without* (outside of us), food has insinuated itself so deeply in our collective unconscious and has become such an important part of human behaviour that it can evoke emotions or bring people together while reflecting our cultural heritage or marking social differences, boundaries, bonds and contradictions. Seen like this, *food is life, food is history, food is culture* and, successively, *life, history and culture* can, in turn, *be understood through food*.

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Food – a powerful symbol chosen to represent various aspects of human experience such as desire, temptation, and social transgression – shares a very close relationship with the artwork of John Everett Millais, a prominent figure in the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood: both media (food and art) have a good grasp of a rich symbolic alphabet (through its diversity of *colour, texture, smell* and *taste* opening up possibilities to be elaborated and combined in infinite ways) enabling us with a *polyphony of experiences* that trespass their immediate form. Particularly in the three paintings under investigation, *Bridesmaid* (1851), *Isabella* (1868), and *The Captive* (1882), Millais uses art to explore themes of desire and social norms: women have a special relationship to food (used symbolically) and a particularly vivid experience of their bodies within the social co(n)text is so heavily (and lavishly) mediated through the visual, the tactile and the olfactory.

The images of food featured in Millais' paintings rely on the olfactory, taste and the visual, triggering off memories, emotions and cultural connections that vibrate differently with each new *reader/receiver/taster* catering for endless new interpretations and building new relationships since neither food nor art act like objects but rather react in relationships. It is through food and the way it is painted on the canvas (the colours chosen, the shades, the shapes and their position or the posture of the human sitters) that we begin to comprehend *the trinity of body image, eating and sexuality*, i.e., Millais' very own *political poetics* through which he reprojects the Pre-Raphaelite social construct(ion) of Victorian women and their bodies. Therein, it becomes obvious that Millais' portrayal of women both challenges and reflects Victorian social norms and expectations cast into doubt by the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood and their artistic credo.

The phrase *Feasting on Desire* suggests an exploration of the *politics* of desire and the way societal norms regulate and suppress individual wishes, all of which are reflected in Millais' art. In this respect, *reading* food in art or *feasting on food through art* gathers complete new meanings (also entailed by societal expectations in conflict with personal longing) set in a Victorian Pre-Raphaelite co(n)text, backgrounded by factors such as social roles and gender construction (especially since men and women delineate themselves differently, through their practices).

Of (inter)sections

John Everett Millais, a founding member of the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood, created some of the most iconic and detailed works of the 19th century. His paintings often contain rich layers of symbolism and social commentary where food plays a significant role in this symbolic language.

If we examine John Everett Millais' poetics, i.e. his *artistic techniques* and the way he uses *visual symbolism* to convey complex themes related to *the trinity*

of food, desire, and social norms, we could endeavour to say that Millais uses *the lens of food* to mediate a rich and nuanced exploration of the intersection between *art, society* and *individual desire* all co(n)textualised by colour, composition, and iconography.

Moreover, by looking over the array of Millais' paintings, it immediately becomes apparent that, despite the limited number of artworks devoted entirely or predominantly to food, three paintings feature fruits engaged in relationships with women, although *his* women are never shown with food in their mouths: fruits are always ready and waiting on the tray and, despite the *stillness* of their presence they do generate a *multiplicity of meanings and relationships* in the space of the painting foregrounding Pre-Raphaelite beauties.

Thus, *Isabella* (1868), *The Bridesmaid* (1851) and *The Captive* (1882) are particularly relevant for the depictions of food that are recurrent in the paintings and that intersect with broader social critiques of Victorian gender roles, social power dynamics, and the *commodification of human relationships*.

Unimportant at first, the presence of the fruits seems unrelated to the symbolic meanings Millais creates in the physical space of his paintings and as yet, it is exactly this deliberate setting of the fruit outside the woman's space, in isolation, that starts yielding new meanings in this *psychosocial space* of the painting. Moreover, critics have looked so far at Millais' paintings as generators of stories, forever revealing infinite layers of intertextual (and intratextual) information, some sort of framing narratives that get a 'voice' under the eyes of the viewer. Also, we could even affirm that Millais' paintings are closer to a 'roman à tiroirs' as, on the one hand, they enable the *psychosocial space* of the painting itself, while, on the other, by the means of the symbols carefully chosen, they generate a myriad of other enframed *psychosocial spaces*.

As such, in *Isabella*, *The Bridesmaid* and *The Captive*, the food is carefully chosen to embed within his art(ful) *politics* by the means of which Millais obliquely criticises a set of Victorian social norms (bridging the outrageous rather than the normal) becoming thus a psychosocial space where personal and social dynamics play out, carrying a symbolic weight that connects to the emotional, psychological, and social interactions of the characters.

In *The Bridesmaid*, the orange resting on the plate, in front of the young woman, functions as more than just a physical object and turns into a psychosocial space through a series of circumstances. First of all, in art, *oranges* symbolise both romantic and sexual desire, and, in the painting, the orange connotes the bridesmaid's societal role in the wedding ritual conveying social pressures surrounding marriage, fertility, and a woman's place in Victorian society. The way the young woman interacts with the orange (the copper-like fruit is on the plate, outside of her physical space) reflects the bridesmaid's inner emotional state as she is torn between her role (and the duty she has to fulfil) and personal feelings. Most probably, the bridesmaid's contemplation

while holding the wedding ring and passing the bride cake through it creates a psychosocial space where the fruit embodies unspoken thoughts of love, loneliness, or resentment which means that, in this case, the food here is a vehicle for psychological and social introspection.

Often associated with bitterness, sourness, and deprivation, the lemons resting on the plate in *The Captive* serve as a key element in the psychosocial dynamics between captor (absent from the painting) and captive (the young woman portrayed): as a rule, food usually represents connection or social interaction but, in captivity, where social interaction is limited, the act of sharing or withholding food becomes one of the few forms of communication between the individuals. Therein, this not only makes the yellow exotic fruits a central point of the psychosocial space (highlighting isolation or a perverse sense of companionship) but it turns food into a psychosocial space which brings to the fore such concepts as power, control, and emotional complexity.

While oranges are known to symbolise fertility and sexuality in art, lemons, on the contrary, symbolise bitterness and hardship, reinforcing, most probably, the suffering of the captive. However, food might also be looked at as a tool of control, since the status of the young captive woman implicitly entails the presence of her captor (even if he is absent), creating, yet again, a psychosocial space where the emotional states of both the captor and the captive are communicated through the act of giving or withholding food. The (offering/receiving) of lemons might suggest an ambiguous relationship between care and domination, where food is both sustenance and a reminder of the captive's vulnerable position, thereby enabling the emergence of the psychosocial space especially since food reflects the emotional undercurrents of isolation, dependency, and subjugation.

Finally, since *Isabella* is based on the tale from Boccaccio's *Decameron* about Isabella and her forbidden love, in Millais' painting, food is central to the psychosocial dynamics of family, power, and desire, all the more since the meal scene is filled with tension. Understandably, the shared meal fails to reflect communal unity or social customs (the family's gathering is occasioned by an (un)fortunate event and it reflects the social hierarchy within Isabella's family) and instead, the scene breathes out violence as the male representatives of Isabella's family (her brothers) dominate the atmosphere and through the symbolical representation of food (particularly through the cracking of the nuts and the spilling of the salt) it further generates rupture and conflict as both familial obligations and hidden desires are negotiated.

Moreover, the food at the table contrasts with Isabella's hidden love for Lorenzo and the brothers' aggression in the meal scene foretells their violent actions against the latter, making the act of sharing food a space for the escalating tensions between loyalty to family and personal desire.

In each of the three paintings by Millais, there is an art(ful) *politics* (and *poetics*) at work which endows food (the meal scene in *Isabella*, the orange and the bride-cake in *The Bridesmaid*, the lemons in *The Captive*) as a psychosocial space facilitating thus emotional expression, either as social power or as a reflection of internal psychological states further entailing relationships and social dynamics that govern the characters' lives.

Food as power and class struggle: 'Isabella' (1868) feasting on desire

Based on a story from Boccaccio's *Decameron* retold in Keats's poem *Isabella, or the Pot of Basil*, Millais' *Isabella* (1868) displays his technical craftsmanship (and artful(ness)) with an almost microscopic precision of the brush: his *Isabella* tells the tragic story of a young woman who is in love with a man named Lorenzo, much to the displeasure of her wealthy merchant brothers who, presumably, murder the latter to maintain control over Isabella's marriage and wealth.

In his depiction of the events, Millais places food centre stage, assigning it a fundamental role in symbolising the power dynamics between Isabella, her brothers, and Lorenzo, so that, set against a Victorian background, this story becomes metonymical of all similar stories about the societal constraints of the time that commodified women and confined them to a single role.

The painting, which depicts a dinner scene, is filled with meticulous detail that draws from both Renaissance influences and the Pre-Raphaelite commitment to realism so that every aspect of the dining table (the wine, the salt, the nut shells, the food plates, the orange fruit) is rendered with dramatic precision, allowing the objects to take on symbolic weight. The composition itself reflects the tragic tension within the narrative as Isabella sits quietly next to her lover Lorenzo, facing her oppressive brothers on the other side of the table; their domination over the meal foreshadows the violence to come, embedded within the metaphor of the food on the table (including the split bloody orange, the crushed nuts or the salt cellar spilling its contents on the white tablecloth). Millais uses the nuts as a central symbol and the crushing of the nutshells by Isabella's brother becomes an act of aggression disguised as a domestic ritual, foreshadowing thus of Lorenzo's fate.

The brothers, seated at the table with Isabella and Lorenzo, are not merely eating but asserting their power over both their sister and Lorenzo through the symbolic gesture of male dominance and control: the nutcracker and the act of crushing and the split bloody orange are ominous symbols of the violence that will befall Lorenzo.

Although the composition of *Isabella* seems to be tightly focused on the figures of the two lovers brought closer by the plate (held by Lorenzo), the eyes of the viewer simultaneously zoom on the elements placed in the background, creating an almost intimate scene that centres on the ritualistic significance of food: the occurrence of the bloody orange split in halves is **symbolic** of

Lorenzo's being murdered [see Appendix A, Figure 1A]; the salt spilt on the white tablecloth is an implied omen [see Appendix A, Figure 2A]; the crushed nuts symbolise the annihilation of Lorenzo's masculinity but also the cracking of his head [see Appendix A, Figure 1b]; and the glass of wine connotes the sacrificial toast of the doomed Lorenzo [see Appendix A, Figure 3A].

The wine's deep dark red hue stands out against the soft tones of the rest of the painting, drawing the viewer's attention to it as one of the central elements of the composition. In Victorian society, wine was often associated with both ritual and indulgence and it was mainly used in sacred ceremonies such as the Eucharist but also linked to sensual pleasure. Held by one of Isabella's brothers in a symbolic gesture of toast, not drinking from it yet, the glass of wine suggests a moment of hesitation, a pause between the present and the future, between Isabella's present innocence and her future experience. The wine, rich in colour and symbolism, evokes ideas of temptation and fertility (Isabella's) and transformation (not only physical but also psychological, entailing a change in the relationship between Isabella and her brothers, currently using her as a commodity exchange) hinting at the deeper emotional and psychological layers of the scene.

As stated above, wine in Victorian society, particularly in the context of weddings, was often associated with ritual, communion, and transformation while in Christian symbolism, wine represents the blood of Christ, linking it to themes of sacrifice, redemption, and spiritual union. By positioning one of Isabella's brothers at the table with the glass of wine, Millais hints at the larger meanings embedded in this moment as the brother's almost hesitant gesture – as he holds the glass of wine but does not drink –, suggests a moment of transition away from the current state to Lorenzo's sacrifice, the symbolical spilling of the blood of the innocent becoming therefore evident that the food element (the wine) is used as a symbol of this transition. Interesting is also the depiction of the wine whose physicality is present despite its absence (in the empty glass) rendered through the almost tactile quality and the smooth surface of the transparent glass, but also through the fluid texture and deep colour of the wine in the half-full glass, rendered with extreme care, creating a sensory experience for the viewer.

Clearly, in this painting, food is tied to the representation of class and control in Victorian society, visible in the way Isabella's brothers use their wealth and authority to dictate the terms of their sister's life. Furthermore, a careful analysis of Isabella's portrayal on the canvas points to her passivity, as she sits at the table in quiet defiance, which contrasts with her brothers' aggressive relationship to food. The attention to the texture and form of the food enhances this symbolism and Millais's use of compelling hues on the nutshells, on the glass of wine or on the orange fruit contrasts with the soft,

passive figure of Isabella, who seems almost disconnected from the physical space she inhabits.

We see the ill-fated loves of Isabella and the trade assistant of her brothers, who, sitting opposite, watch with rage how tenderly she takes the orange - the symbolically blood-red orange that Lorenzo has cut for her. The one in his idle rage cracks a nut as he would willingly crack Lorenzon's head, upsets the salt and viciously kicks at the greyhound that his sister fondles. The other looks with a treacherous smile across his wine-glass, a man to whom the 'serpent's whine' is natural; and the third watches, too, with well-restrained anger; while the nurse - 'an aged dame' observes with apprehension and foreboding the violence of the eldest and most demonstrative 'money-bag'. The ingenious composition, recalling in a measure one of Veronese's 'Feasts,' is supported by the excellence of colour, fine execution, and extraordinary finish which attains its highest perfection, perhaps in the head of Isabella. The drawing is as certain and as pure as Holbein's and far less hard than at first sight appears. There are passages of colour - such as the green cover to the kicker's chair - worthy of Van Eyck. (Harry Spielmann, 2008: 84)

The food on the table becomes a metaphor for control, as the brothers handle, manipulate, and consume it. Millais's technique of layering intricate detail within the composition serves to deepen the symbolic role of food as a representation of power, manipulation, and violence. The shared meal, commonly held as a symbol of communal unity, is perverted herein into a site of conflict and violence particularly as Millais obliquely critiques the way Victorian society commodifies women (metonymically embodied by Isabella), reducing them to a pawn in the economic and social ambitions of the male figures in their lives.

Food as conformity and female passivity: 'The Bridesmaid' feasting on desire (1851)

A contemplation on the role of women within Victorian society, particularly in relation to marriage and gender expectations, John Everett Millais' *The Bridesmaid* portrays a Pre-Raphaelite young beauty with impressive copper-blond hair, flowing down her shoulders, and dressed in the luxuriant yellow garment of a bridesmaid, decorated at the neckline with an intricate floral corsage, tied with a ribbon that adds a touch of elegance and indicates her role as a bridesmaid.

The figure of the young woman is set against an abysmal and mystifying royal blue background which aggressively contrasts with the warm tones of the bridesmaid's hair and dress.

The composition of *The Bridesmaid* is simple but highly effective in focusing attention on the woman's figure and the symbolic elements that occupy her physical space in the painting. Millais uses a tight, cropped frame

that centres the woman and eliminates any extraneous background details. This compositional choice isolates the figure and draws the viewer's focus to her gesture and expression.

In the foreground, the viewer's eyes rest on an exquisite silver sugar caster and a plate with a piece of cake and an orange on it, adding a domestic touch that upholds the entire composition and possibly connotes wealth, fertility, protection, and abundance, all stereotypically attached to the idea of marriage. The delicate hands of the bridesmaid seem to be occupied with something, as she appears to hold a small item between her left index finger and her thumb, presumably a wedding ring, a posture that confers some pulsating energy to the stillness of the visual narrative. [see Appendix B, Figure 1B] The painting illustrates one of many Victorian marriage traditions according to which a bridesmaid would see a vision of her true love if she passed a piece of wedding cake through a ring nine times. (*The Bridesmaid* by John Everett Millais (thehistoryofart.org) accessed 24 August 2024)

Known for a time as 'All Hallow's E'en', the picture represents the popular superstition that the bridesmaid who passes a piece of bride cake through a ring will see a vision of her beloved. It was painted in the same year as *Mariana* and the *Hueguenot* and is exquisite in handling. For the head, Mrs Nassau Senior sat. (Harry Spielmann, 2008: 146)

One of the most striking elements of *The Bridesmaid* is Millais' meticulous attention to detail, characteristic of the Pre-Raphaelite commitment to the highly elaborate, almost hyper-realistic style of early Renaissance art, i.e., *photographic realism*. Every aspect of the painting, from the bridesmaid's gown and hair to the silver sugar caster on her left or the piece of cake and the orange fruit on the plate, in front of her, is rendered with extraordinary precision. This level of detail creates a tactile quality that invites the viewer into the scene, making it feel immediate and real.

Moreover, on the canvas, the bridesmaid holds a central place. The painting is imbued with symbolic references to food and ritualistic consumption, highlighting, yet again, the women's role in Victorian society. The inclusion of food as a symbolic element, in the form of sugar (although out of sight, concealed behind the silver walls of the sugar caster), the orange fruit and the piece of the wedding cake, serves as a central metaphor for purity, sensuality, societal control and gendered expectations placed on women, particularly in the context of marriage and ritual in Victorian life. (En)trapped between the sacred and the sensual, the bridesmaid is caught in the liminal space between innocence and experience. The act of holding the ring simultaneously alludes to purity and sacrifice but also to fertility and desire, casting the figure of the Pre-Raphaelite young woman in a dual light.

The act of holding food (the small piece of the wedding cake), not yet consuming it, points to a deeper societal commentary on women's bodies and their function within marriage: the ring and the piece of cake held at chest level invite the viewer to contemplate the significance of this gesture, which can be interpreted as a moment of reflection, anticipation, or even uncertainty. The placement of the ring in relation to the fruit and the cake on the plate is key to the painting's symbolic power. The bridesmaid's dynamic gesture (passing the small piece of cake through the wedding ring (therefore not eating or tasting it) suggests a liminal state, a moment of pause between the past and the future, innocence and experience. Thus rendered with great precision by Millais, this gesture, emphasises the woman's role not only as a participant in the ritual but also as a symbol of Victorian womanhood, caught between societal expectations and personal agency.

The bridesmaid, with her solemn expression, becomes an emblem of the way Victorian society ritualised and controlled female sexuality, using food as a symbol of purity, sacrifice, and passive consumption. In this way, Millais obliquely criticises the rigid gender roles of Victorian society, where women were often reduced to symbolic functions in the rituals of marriage, expected to conform to societal expectations without expressing their desires or individuality.

Food as emotional symbolism: *The Captive* (1882) feasting on desire

The Captive portrays the graceful figure of a girl in an Oriental dress. Her expression, though serene, conveys a deep sense of resignation and emotional withdrawal as she is bearing before her a silver plate with two lemon fruits on it. The sitter was Miss Ruby Streadfield and this pleasing study in cool colours was at one time known as *Ruby*.

Much in a similar way to *The Bridesmaid*, in *The Captive*, Millais shifts focus to the interior through a dark, confined space intending to enhance the emotional weight of the painting: placed in the space *within* of the young woman (whose passive posture suggests that she is entrapped both physically and psychologically), the fruits become a marker not only of emotional and social confinement but also of limited agency afforded to women during the Victorian era. Despite the muted, sombre tones of the room bathed in dim, foggy light, two small bundles of yellow colour pop out on the tray (both a literal and a metaphorical barrier), somehow isolating, even confining the figure of the young woman within her environment.

Though less overt in its social commentary than *Isabella* or *The Bridesmaid*, *The Captive* uses the motif of food to explore themes of emotional and social captivity and it is the woman's ambiguous physical posture that can be read both as a provider (holding power as she hands out the tray to serve) and as a recipient of food (being in control as she reaches her hands to receive

the tray, being in a vulnerable, dependent position) that highlights her dual role in Victorian society, expected to nourish and care for others while being confined by the very domesticity she upholds. This power dynamic creates a psychosocial space where relationships are, yet again, defined by hierarchy and dependency, characterised as it is by a complex blend of compassion and dominance.

Nevertheless, not to be ignored is the idea of otherness embedded within the painting through the presence of the exotic fruits, the lemons [see Appendix C, Figure 1C], in the context of Victorian England which could hint at themes of foreignness or *otherness*, especially if the captive in the painting is meant to represent someone from a different culture or background but also through the depiction of the beautifully adorned Oriental garment the young woman is wearing, reinforcing thus the idea of the captive as an *outsider*, whose very existence in this confined space is marked by difference and distance from freedom.

In conclusion, the lemons Millais portrays in *The Captive* add to the politics of his aesthetics and serve as a multi-layered symbol, intertwining themes of suffering, temptation, health, and alienation, hence enriching the painting's emotional and psychological complexity.

Some after-thoughts

Art has long been a medium for reflecting and critiquing societal values, and no movement embodies this dual role more vividly than the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood (PRB), an artistic group whose focus on aesthetic reform was entangled with a deeper engagement with the social issues of their time, obliquely commenting on Victorian values, class structure, industrialisation, and gender roles.

One of the founding members of the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood, John Everett Millais, like his fellow PRB artists, aligned himself with the *Arts and Crafts Movement*, which opposed the dehumanising effects of mass production and his particular use of *photographic realism* laid the foundations of a Millaisian *aesthetic poetics* (a genuine technical mastery where minute attention is given to intricate detail and vibrant natural colours that dominate the canvas) that also acts like a particular form of *ideological politics*, obliquely criticising not only the broader Victorian obsession with propriety, refinement and order but also the class-based moral structures of the era.

The Pre-Raphaelites' engagement with social commentary through art, which Millais also followed through, reveals how aesthetics can transcend mere decoration to become a powerful tool for cultural and moral introspection. Nevertheless, while they offered women complex roles in their art, the Pre-Raphaelites often portrayed them as passive subjects of male desire, trapped within the confines of beauty and unattainable ideals which attracted

criticism regarding their idealisation and objectification of women. And yet, despite all criticism, this particular portrayal reflects Victorian anxieties about women's sexuality and the fear of female independence, even as it challenges the moral purity expected of Victorian women.

The almost fetishistic depiction of food in art (and particularly in Millais' works of art) is a testament to its profound significance in human culture: whether as a symbol of abundance, a vehicle for moral allegory, or a means of social critique, food in paintings offers a rich tapestry of meanings and interpretations and, through the ages, artists have used food to explore the complexities of human experience, making it an enduring and evocative subject in the world of art.

While not overtly political, in works such as *Isabella* (1849), *The Bridesmaid* (1851) and *The Captive* (1853), Millais craftfully uses food to enhance the layers of meaning hidden within the psychosocial spaces his paintings thus create by means of rich visual narratives that explore power dynamics, gender roles, and personal identity. Hence, Millais's intersection of art and social commentary through depictions of food adds depth to the Pre-Raphaelite movement's critique of Victorian culture, making his paintings powerful reflections on the societal norms of his time. Therein, the food motifs and their relationship to the figures within these artworks, become vehicles intended to subversively construct a politics by the means of which the oppressive expectations placed upon women in Victorian society, particularly regarding domesticity, desire, and agency are subtly criticised so that both the subject and the viewer engaged in art feast on desire.

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Appendix A
Figure 1A, detail

Figure 2A, detail

Figure 3A, detail

Appendix B
Figure 1B, detail

Appendix C
Figure 1C, detail

Food, Texts and Types of Hunger in Jodi Picoult's *The Storyteller*

Cristina Mihaela NISTOR*

Abstract

*In the media, the theme of the Holocaust has always been most powerfully illustrated visually, with images or videos depicting skeletal human beings on the verge of becoming two-dimensional, almost transparent. In the remaining footage of WWII horrors, one can see that those Jews who were kept in Nazi prisoner camps, and who were lucky enough not to be gassed on arrival, still had to cope with the scarcity – or even total lack – of food, which would eventually turn them into living skeletons. In literature, the theme of the Holocaust has been approached differently, with writers constantly striving to find the best words and phrases to appropriately describe the bodily sensations of those for whom food had almost become an intangible item. This paper intends to show how Jodi Picoult's novel *The Storyteller* (2013) manages to make its readers mentally visualise the horrors of the Holocaust through the close interconnectedness of (at least) two types of hunger: the physical hunger for food that might enable prisoners to survive another day, and the hunger for texts and stories, which nourish the mind and soul. The pursuit of justice, as well as the need for absolution from guilt, are other types of hunger that this paper analyses, with a view towards a more applied approach within the scope of the study.*

Keywords: contemporary literature, stories of Holocaust horrors, types of hunger, perceptions of food, spiritual food

Introduction

Hunger, in its multifarious forms and degrees, has shaped civilisations and determined the rise or fall of empires. What people traditionally eat on certain holidays and what they avoid eating because they have grown up believing that a particular food is forbidden – either as a rule or only during certain time intervals – have been topics of interest to many authors. Some authors focus on cookbooks, whereas others – particularly fiction writers – have elevated the theme of hunger to a deeper, more complex level, where it has branched out into many different sub-themes such as (in)satiability, (un)healthy food, spiritual food, etc. Closely linked to religious and moral values, the consumption and preparation of certain foods have been rigorously regulated by specific norms such as, for example, the *kashrut* [1], since:

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Religion and food go together like bagels and lox. Though this is certainly true of most religions, food and Judaism – with its richly textured laws and traditions of *kashrut*, a history of diaspora and displacement, and a this-worldly theology that encourages celebration and feast – seem to have a particularly strong bond. (Zeller 2015: 114)

In recent artistic productions, novelists and screenwriters have found hunger – whether in its literal or allegorical form – to be a rich source of inspiration. Examples can be seen in books like Markus Zusak’s *The Book Thief* and film series like *The Hunger Games*, which successfully explore and exploit this concept. Hunger, whether in the form of the struggle for nutritious food or the quest for knowledge that could help one survive the horrors of WWII or the brutal trials in *The Hunger Games*, has awakened the survival instinct in the characters, while also refining and reshaping their minds and bodies. As Mattes and Friedman observe, “the term ‘hunger’ has a variety of meanings, and numerous physiological mechanisms underlying the sensation have been proposed” (1993: 65). In artistic representations, particularly in fictionalised expressions, the sensation of hunger has taken on new meanings, straddling philosophical and psychological lines: “Hunger is an important psychological and physiological phenomenon that exerts a strong influence on behaviour. When better characterised, it should be more amenable to monitoring and manipulation for therapeutic purposes.” (65)

Closely connected with the theme of hunger, the atrocities committed during and after WWII have provided ample material for generations of novelists. Among the most delicate and challenging topics is the Holocaust, which has pushed writers to find the most effective language to convey the physical sensations of those for whom food became almost intangible. This paper aims to explore how Jodi Picoult’s novel *The Storyteller* (2013) enables readers to mentally visualise the horrors of the Holocaust by intertwining at least two forms of hunger. On one level, the novel addresses the literal hunger for food that might allow prisoners to survive another day, while on another, it delves into a hunger for stories and texts that nourish the mind and soul. Additionally, the novel presents the pursuit of justice and the need for absolution from guilt as other forms of hunger, which this paper will analyse in a more applied manner within its scope.

Readers’ cravings for narratives

Jodi Picoult’s *The Storyteller* (2013) came into print the same year as Markus Zusak’s *The Book Thief* (2013). It features a Jewish girl, Minka, who has a passion for books and the world of the imaginary, the same as Zusak’s heroine, Liesel. Still, that is where the similitude between the two books ends. Indeed, Picoult’s novel is a mixture of stories told by a multitude of narrators, combined with a

history lesson that is presented at a personal level, all linked together with food recipes, cravings, regrets and longings that invite readers to ponder upon the possible solutions to the characters' problems.

Rejecting a dichotomist view of life where concepts like good and bad are clearly defined and understood, and one's problems get solved with the best solutions possible, *The Storyteller* proposes, in turn, a narrative that is full of twists and turns, and reminds readers that many things in life may be multifaceted and, therefore, complex and morally debatable. To the reader who craves postmodernist plots, the main storyline of Picoult's 2013 novel may seem rather simple. Still, by analysing the type of the narrative more closely, readers may encounter elements that contribute to *The Storyteller's* attempt at becoming a page-turner. In that respect, the theory proposed by Gerard Genette (1983), which takes into account the variables the narratologist called 'narrative level' and 'story', may help boost the literary value of the narrative under scrutiny:

If in every narrative we define the narrator's status both by its narrative level (extra- or intradiegetic) and by its relationship to the story (hetero- or intradiegetic), we can represent the four basic types of narrator's status as follows: (1) extradiegetic – heterodiegetic – paradigm: Homer, a narrator in the first degree who tells a story he is absent from; (2) extradiegetic – homodiegetic paradigm: Gil Blas, a narrator in the first degree who tells his own story; (3) intradiegetic – heterodiegetic – paradigm: Scheherazade, a narrator in the second degree who tells stories she is on the whole absent from; (4) intradiegetic – homodiegetic paradigm: Ulysses in Books IX-XII, a narrator in the second degree who tells his own story. (Genette 1983: 248)

With that categorisation in mind, readers who hunger for textual diversity may find *The Storyteller* a challenging read, especially if one takes into consideration the multitude and types of narrators in Picoult's novel. For starters, readers have the opportunity to listen to a multitude of narrators who tell their own stories, all in their own, particular ways and styles. What is more, the novel includes whole pages that prove to be excerpts from an entirely fictional story written by one of the main characters, Minka, and which represent the very reason that imaginative Jewish girl was protected in the Nazi prisoners camp and finally saved. All those texts, with their different writers and prospective readers, are intertwined in the body of a narrative that pulsates with life and gives 21st-century readers the impression of authentic feeling and drama.

In order to get a full picture of the narrative web woven by Jodi Picoult's multiple narrators, an introduction to the main story might prove helpful. Thus, the reader learns that, in the small town of Westbrook, 25-year-old Sage Singer works irregular, antisocial hours, because, on the one hand, her job requires it—she is a baker—and, on the other hand, she has a facial scar she

tries very hard to hide. Sage goes to a grief group, sharing next to nothing, but trying to atone for her mortal sin: on the night of her graduation, three years back, Sage had caused a car accident which resulted in the death of her mother, sometime after that, due to some complications. Consumed by guilt, Sage tells everybody that her mother died of cancer; what is more, she sees her scar the same way it was after the accident, and uses food-related metaphors to explain her view:

In this, I suppose I'm like a girl with an eating disorder, who weighs ninety-eight pounds but sees a fat person staring back at her from the mirror. It isn't even a scar to me, really. It's a map of where my life went wrong. (Picoult 2013: 10)

Sage's story focuses on the idea that she may not afford to have a choice in life, that her scar and her guilt of having inadvertently killed her mother dictate her whole destiny. Similar to all the life narratives that *The Storyteller* encompasses in its textual fabric, Sage's story emphasises the close relationship between life and death; thus, her lover is a married man called Adam, whom she met at her mother's funeral, in his capacity as the mortician in charge with taking care of her mother. Her extremely low self-esteem determined her to begin an affair with Adam, because she considers herself damaged goods, with her scar and her life history, and she keeps hearing the "quiet whisper in her head: beggars can't be choosers; take what you can get; who else would ever love someone like you?" (27).

As the main story goes, at the group therapy, Sage befriends a nonagenarian, called Josef Weber, who usually goes to the bakery where she works to have coffee and a roll that he shares with his dog Eva. As it happens, once, he leaves his "little black book" (24) behind, so Sage runs out into the storm to give it back to him, wondering jokingly whether that is his 'Great American Novel', only to see Josef looking startled at the idea of having it published. Somewhat secretly, he remarks that "this is just a place to keep my thoughts. They get away from me, otherwise" (24) and, before getting on the bus, he "pats his pocket. 'It's important to remember,' he says" (25).

Readers in need of typologies and in-depth thinking may quickly recognise in Jodi Picoult's *The Storyteller* subjects and themes that pose questions related to the dilemmas most people who survive horrific encounters or incidents are faced with: remembering and letting go, punishment and forgiveness, hunger and abundance, sin and absolution, death and survival. One character, Mary DeAngelis, is cast in the role of Sage's employer and a former nun, with a life story that is, again, related to food – in its two-fold sense of the body and soul alike. A reformed nun, to whom Jesus appeared in a vision telling her "there were many souls to feed" (13), Mary opens Our Daily Bread, a shrine and a bakery that will cater for both types of hunger her visitors might experience, material and spiritual. For baking the actual bread and a diverse

range of specialities, Mary DeAngelis employs Sage, who, in her turn, unravels her story as one ruled by recipes and hunger. Readers learn that the death of her parents played a paramount part in Sage's becoming a baker, who works nights, shying away from the rest of the world, who prefers daylight activities. Thus, after her father's death, 19-year-old Sage finds her interest in life and studies waning, giving way to an insatiable passion for baking. Miraculously, much like Mary DeAngelis's experience, Sage feels driven by an overwhelming urge, as if possessed by a spirit, compelling her to feed others:

I woke up in my dorm room and smelled flour [...] It reminded me of Sunday mornings as a kid, when I would awaken to the scent of fresh bagels and bialys, crafted by my father. He'd always tried to teach my sisters and me, but mostly we were too busy [...]. Or so I thought until I started to sneak into the residential college dining hall kitchen and bake bread every night. (14)

Paralysed by grief at the loss of her father, and unable to turn in papers or persuade her brain to pay attention to lectures or books, Sage experiences what might be labelled as a compulsive baking disorder, as if that was the only action she has been genetically programmed to perform:

I left the loaves like abandoned babies on the thresholds of the offices of professors I admired, of the dorm rooms of boys with smiles so beautiful that they stunned me into awkward silence. I left a final row of sourdough rolls on a lectern podium and slipped a boule into the oversize purse of the cafeteria lady who pressed plates of pancakes and bacon at me, telling me I was too skinny. On the day my academic adviser told me that I was failing three of my four classes, I had nothing to say in my defence, but I gave her a honey baguette seeded with anise, the bitter and the sweet. (14)

Saved by her mother from a sense of despair that she alone could not shake off, Sage eventually graduates but causes a car accident that puts her mother into a 6-month battle for life – which she finally loses. Again, stress and guilt combined urge Sage to resort to her own, personalised therapy – compulsive baking: “I brought artisan loaves to her doctors. I made pretzels for the nurses. For my mother, I baked her favourite – cinnamon rolls, thick with icing. I made them daily, but she never managed a bite” (14). After her mother's death and her life going downhill, Sage takes her therapist's advice and finds a job at Mary DeAngelis's bakery. In part, she does that because, for her own reasons, she identifies with a piece of dough that needs time alone in order to get in the best shape possible:

That's the point where you have to leave the dough alone. It's silly to anthropomorphize bread, but I love the fact that it needs to sit quietly, to retreat

from touch and noise and drama, in order to evolve. I have to admit, I often feel that way myself. (17)

In the unfolding of the story, Mary DeAngelis plays a decisive and delicate role as a catalyst: she helps things happen, as if by divine intervention. For once, she describes Josef in warm colours, as “everyone’s adoptive, cuddly grandfather”, or “as close you can get to being canonised while you’re still alive” (22). Despite that, her ironic comment to Sage— “the worst he could do is talk you to death” (22)—will eventually turn true when Josef confesses to something that will put an end to Sage’s trust in him. The readers’ hunger for the sensational is satisfied at this point: Josef is not the innocent retired old man Mary DeAngelis imagines, as he, all of a sudden, makes a strange request: that Sage help him die.

Readers may remark on Jodi Picoult’s strategy of imagining the perfect time and place to make Josef’s strange request sound even more challenging. Thus, one crazy night, after checking on Josef, who was taken ill, entirely by accident, Sage bakes a loaf of bread that resembles Jesus; the unlikely event brings the whole town and local television to Mary’s bakery Our Holy Bread, which becomes famous. Making her escape in an attempt to find a quiet spot unoccupied by the crowd that marvels at the Jesus Loaf, Sage finds Josef on the stairs to the Monet Garden, Mary DeAngelis’s place full of beautiful flowers, some of which are poisonous. Dramatically enough, that is the place where, out of the blue, Josef makes his strange request while everyone is marvelling about the Jesus Loaf: “I would like you to help me die.” (50) Seemingly, Josef shares some mythical creature’s genes that prevent him from dying, and he is trying to explain to Sage the difficulty he finds in dying: “This is God’s joke on me. He makes me so strong that I cannot die even when I want to.” (50) With the girl wondering at his apparently insane wish to end his life, Josef confesses to the truth that, according to his own judgement: “I should be dead, Sage. It’s what I deserve.” (51) While confessing to his crimes, Josef presses a picture in Sage’s palm, where she sees a young man dressed in the uniform of an SS guard, smiling, who is supposed to be Josef.

The story following that confession adds layers upon layers of narratives, and readers are presented with many texts that, knit together, form the fabric of *The Storyteller*. We, readers, will learn not only Josef’s story but also his former prisoner Minka’s—Sage’s grandmother—as well as read fragments from Minka’s fiction about a vampire who feasts on human hearts. The main thread of the novel, though, goes smoothly: Sage, in a state of shock at the idea of having befriended a Nazi, who, on top of everything, wants her to kill him, goes to the police, who refer her to the office of Human Rights and Special Prosecutions. There, she meets Leo Stein, who helps her unravel the mystery and discover Josef Weber’s true identity as Reiner Hartmann, get his confession on tape, and reconnect with her grandmother, Minka [2]. In their concerted

effort to build a case against Josef, Leo and Sage, two young Americans of Jewish origin, fall in love with each other, and find a common goal.

For the true story to be finally pieced together from the fragments collected from both Josef and Minka, Sage and Leo need patience, because, like a piece of dough, the process takes time, and the two WWII survivors tell their own versions of experiencing the war, and reflect on the way hunger, imagination and history may influence people's lives. Jodi Picoult has both war survivors die, in the end, and the dénouement proves partly disappointing, with Sage finally fulfilling Josef's wish, only to find out that she had killed the wrong Hartmann brother – Franz, not Reiner.

Food, families, survival

Family, nationality and food are key concepts in Jodi Picoult's narrative, and issues like life and death, punishment and atonement are deeply related to those three concepts. The two families whose life principles are presented in *The Storyteller* are representative of their respective nationalities and food habits. Trying to understand Josef's reasoning when she gets that shocking invitation to kill him, Sage learns that she has been chosen because she is a Jew and the granddaughter of a Holocaust survivor.

In the "Acknowledgements" to *The Storyteller* (2013), Jodi Picoult thanks her Jewish parents for their help with the book, especially her mother, who found some Holocaust survivors within a day, and thus "paved the way for this book" (xi). Like Sage, the author admits to finding herself in an awkward position, with a heritage that demands she take a stand. On her website, Picoult argues for the viability of her project as a means to safeguard against criminals and injustices:

A lot of people will ask me why, after all the Holocaust literature that has been written, I wanted to tackle this subject. I am agnostic, but I was raised by Jewish parents and so, like Sage, I find myself in the odd situation of being a spokesperson for a religious group I do not personally affiliate with anymore. And yet, someone has to be that spokesperson. (online)

Food is the element that determines the way one raises one's family, as it provides not only the proteins, fats, vitamins and minerals one needs to survive but also a whole philosophy of life. That is why, in the novel, readers find that families shape their children's behaviour according to their own standards and social realities, taking into account factors such as social and financial status, nationality, health, and character – all of which being reflected in the food they eat. Whether describing a piece of pastry or a rancid vegetable soup, Picoult's writing makes readers imagine the precise taste of the respective food; when, in turn, she chooses to tell a story about generosity and kindness, she touches

their souls; that is what happens when Sage chooses to speak about the difference between Heaven and Hell during a group therapy session:

“When my mother was in the hospital,” I say, “her rabbi told her a story. In Heaven and Hell, people sit at banquet tables filled with amazing food, but no one can bend their elbows. In Hell, everyone starves because they can’t feed themselves. In Heaven, everyone’s stuffed, because they don’t have to bend their arms to feed each other.” (38)

Kindness and selflessness are the keys to Heaven, that would be the Jewish lesson, taught in a food parable. Talking about food, thinking about food and sharing food is how people get to know one another or the standard by which they get to be measured. When Sage announces, “I baked a loaf of bread that had Jesus’s face in it,” her grandmother Minka introduces her granddaughter to a tiny fragment of her own past, confessing that, “There was a time when I could see God in a single crumb.” (61) That proves to be the beginning of the story of Minka’s battle for survival during the WWII Holocaust, a story about the food that many were denied, and dreamed about in the Nazi prison camps. Reminiscing about prisoners’ collective dreams, Minka tells Sage that the primordial, basic need Auschwitz residents painfully felt was for food:

You know, that was what we missed most. Not our beds, not our homes, not even our mothers. We would talk about food. Roast potatoes and briskets, pierogi, babka. What I would have given my life for back then was some of my father’s challah, fresh from the oven. (61)

In Jodi Picoult’s novel, female characters – at all narrative levels – have fathers who bake and show their affection by presenting their loved ones with their favourite pastry, baguette, challah, or boule. Having experienced both a happy childhood of plenty and a horrific wartime of hunger and terror, 80-year-old Minka bakes four times the amount of bread she can eat every week, only to share it with the needy, as Sage discovers that: “she wants to have the luxury of giving the rest away to those who are still hungry” (61).

Conversely, the German family where Josef was born and raised had another perception of life, dictated by hunger and hatred. The Hartmanns, as well as most German families at that time, resented the fact that inflation had ruined them all, despite their efforts to save up for a long time. What is worse, in most Germans’ view, it was the Jews who, as shrewd investors, were to be blamed for the Germans’ misfortunes. Discussing the hatred against Jews that Hitler constantly fed in his anti-Semitic propaganda, Julia Kristeva writes about it in terms of “developing abjection” (Kristeva 1982: 180). However, recent research has examined the relationship between food, nutrients, and behaviour, revealing that the quality of the food consumed can influence

changes in behaviour. This may help explain the violent outbursts observed among trainees at Hitler Youth meetings:

Vitamin and mineral deficiencies may lead to the formation of undesirable behaviour and misalignment in the nervous system. [...] Low serotonin and high dopamine levels play a role in the formation of aggressive behaviour. Hunger and associated nutrient deficiencies can affect family members and may be the cause of negative behaviour towards children. (Özenoglu and Ünal 2015: 115)

In Josef's story, it is explained that brutality was needed in order to uproot evil, so, the perception of violence as a viable solution to poverty grew stronger in Hitler's Germany. Reflecting on the concept of brutality, Josef recounts a story about beating his brother to a bloody pulp and admits that he consciously made a pact with the devil for the privileged position it afforded him: "I always knew what I was doing, and to whom I was doing it. I knew, very well. Because, in those terrible, wonderful moments, I was the person everyone wanted to be." (Picoult 2013: 107). The two Hartmann brothers appear to be complete opposites: Reiner is a brute, whereas Franz is an intellectual who helps his Jewish friend Arthur Goldman with books, something that Reiner resents and puts a stop to, arguing that: "If it was books today, tomorrow it would be food. Money. Shelter. That, I could not let happen." (138) The food of the mind is, again, closely linked with the material food that may help one survive. The link between Josef and Minka is, as Sage is surprised to learn from her grandmother, the German's love for fiction and his insatiable hunger for fantastic characters, as Josef (pretending, at the time, to be Reiner), remarks: "My brother believed in all sorts of mythical creatures: pixies, dragons, werewolves, honest men." (42) In other words, Sage's grandmother, Minka, is saved from Auschwitz by Franz because he was fascinated with mythical creatures, particularly due to the story she writes about an *upior*, a Polish vampire.

Under pressure from Sage and Leo to share her story, Minka, a Holocaust survivor, invites her audience into a world where reality is framed by food, love, hatred, blood, and hope. She transports her eager listeners back in time to her father's bakery in Poland, where she spent many hours writing her tale about an *upior*, a vampire that fed on parts of its victims.

Saved numerous times by her proficiency in German, Minka witnesses the death of all the people she loves; in the end, she survives to tell both her stories - one which has turned into history, the story of her survival, and the other, which is the story she had been writing since her happier days, in her father's bakery, and which arouses the interest of the Auschwitz Hauptscharführer, Franz Hartmann. He takes Minka as his secretary and gives her a pen and a leather notebook where she is required to write ten pages of her story every night. Since "a disciplined body is the prerequisite of an

efficient gesture" (Foucault 1991: 152), at Auschwitz, prisoners are disciplined by other people, according to their rank.

Hunger vs horror

The Storyteller (2013) suggests that everything may be judged and valued in terms of hunger; at some point, Minka remarks that, during the time spent in the ghetto, one boy who fancied her, Aron, once, gave her "a bit of his bread ration during lunch at school, which Darija said was virtually a proposal of marriage in these times." (263) Another instance of valuing life in terms of the food she longed for is when she sees a piece of bread and jam on an officer's plate, she touches it, sticks her finger in her mouth and starts thinking of all the things she and her family have loved and lost. What is more, she reflects on the meaning of the jam, which tops the sensorial and goes into the philosophical: "That jam tasted like a lazy summer day. Like freedom." (267)

Another interesting point to make would be that of the choice of the names given to Minka's granddaughters since they are all names of spices: Pepper, Saffron, and Sage - with the last name having a double meaning as both an herb with medicinal powers and the idea of wisdom. The real story of the Holocaust survivor who needed real food to eat is complemented by the fictional story she writes about the *upior* - and, in Minka's fiction, the *upior's* hunger is a force that drives him mad. Rather interestingly, from the very first pages of the book, readers find that: "Hunger [...] has nothing to do with the belly and everything to do with the mind." (17) A deep thinker herself, Minka takes some time to reflect on the hunger theme, and comes to an amazing conclusion:

I had come to see, too, that all my characters and I were motivated by the same inspiration. Whether it was power they sought, or revenge, or love - well, those were all just different forms of hunger. The bigger the hole inside you, the more desperate you became to fill it. (248)

When describing the horrors of her fictional character, Minka believes that underneath it all, there is a lesson to be learnt; still, she seems painfully aware of the fact that it is not the senses that are offended by the blood and gore one perceives, but the heart and soul. In that line, after she sees three people hanged from the gallows for having criticizing Germans, she compares reality to the fiction she writes and declares herself defeated:

I thought of all the blood and guts in the horror story I was writing, of the *upior* eating the heart of a victim, and realized that none of it mattered. The shock value was not in the gore. It was the fact that a minute ago, this man was alive, and now, he wasn't. (236)

As a defence mechanism triggered in the face of real horror, Minka begins to unravel her own vampire story, as a means to help her fellow prisoners focus on something else than the grim reality surrounding them. In a way, Minka plays the role of Scheherazade for the block, in hopes that it becomes a reason for everyone to stick around. Even if you are deprived of food, fiction is worth surviving is the message of the fictional storyteller, for the simple fact that “sometimes all you need to live one more day is a reason to stick around” (Picoult 2013: 266). Feeding the hungry minds of the prisoners by telling the story of the undying monster that falls in love with a mortal—while also writing the mandatory ten pages a night for Frank, the Hauptscharführer—transforms Minka into a storyteller in her own right. On top of that, writing her fiction also gives Minka hope against hope, which feels better than real, tasty food: “When I wrote, I felt untethered, impossibly free.” (261) With the hope of food growing slimmer every day, Minka confesses to having believed in her Scheherazade-like fate:

I was delusional enough to convince myself that as long as my story continued, so would my life. Yet even Scheherazade had run out of stories, after 1001 nights. [...] I only wanted the Allies to show up before I ran out of plot twists. (292)

When all stories are told, a bereaved Sage, whose grandmother Minka is recently deceased, grants Josef Weber/Franz Hartmann’s wish and kills him with her perfect roll filled with chopped monkshood from Mary DeAngelis’s Monet Garden. There is a sense of poetic justice in that, food being the baker’s weapon of choice. Still, before eating the poisonous food, Josef gets to confess to Sage his only crime, that of failing to help his brother, who died as he choked on sour cherries. Ironically, after her deed, Sage realises she had killed the wrong brother: it was not Reiner who had told her the story of his murderous past, but Franz, who had lived with the guilt of not giving his brother the Heimlich manoeuvre. As, with his dying breath, Josef asks Sage, “How does it end?”, he betrays his identity as Franz, the dreamer, instead of Reiner, the monster. Sage comes to an understanding of Josef’s actions at last, but it is too late for her to remedy anything: interpreting facts depends on how and what Sage chooses to read her grandmother’s fiction. As English novelist A.S. Byatt wrote, the impossibility of knowing the past is something one must accept, as “truth is a meaningless concept, and all narratives select and distort” (Byatt 2001: 11).

In Jodi Picoult’s multi-layered narrative, baking, eating, writing, loving, punishing, killing, or simply dying are seen as reasons to make the narrator(s) and the readers ponder and wonder at humans’ capacity to survive, love and hate. In the novel, the two types of hunger, that of the body, and that of the mind, are to be satisfied in the end by the very act of reading and sharing food and fiction. In a conversation about *The Storyteller*, available on her website, the

author affirms that storytelling is as important as food when it comes to surviving the horrors of history:

Am I more qualified because I have relatives who died in concentration camps? That's not for me to say. But some stories need to be told, and this is one of them, [...] That's why I wrote this book. Because stories matter, and there are six million people who did not have the opportunity to tell theirs. (online)

Notes

[1] In Jewish cuisine, the concept of *kashrut* provides the cook with the standards for the appropriate food preparation. On the website of the Jewish Museum Berlin, visitors are introduced to the gist of that concept, namely that "the Hebrew word *kashrut* means 'ritual suitability' and refers to the Jewish dietary laws. These dictate how to prepare, store, and eat food and how to slaughter animals that are permitted for consumption. Foods that are permitted to eat under *kashrut* are 'kosher.' Non-kosher foods are known as *treyf*." More details at: <<https://www.jmberlin.de/en/topic-kashrut>>.

[2] In a comparison related to the psychological distress experienced by daughters and granddaughters of Holocaust (CCS) survivors and daughters and granddaughters of OCCS, Freud and Berant (2022) report interesting data, among which: "No difference between groups was found in Holocaust communication between survivors and their granddaughters. No difference was found between groups in their psychological distress. The granddaughters of CCS scored higher on attachment anxiety than the other group." (1655)

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Famished Souls Struggling for Food in George Orwell's *Down and Out in Paris and London*

Raluca Ștefania PELIN*

Abstract

Bread and margarine with wine, or "tea-and-two-slices", presents a choice that triggers vast contemplations on poverty versus wealth and meaningful versus meaningless life. This paper aims to highlight how George Orwell's Down and Out in Paris and London tackles the centrality of food and the people striving to obtain it. The purpose of this reading is to raise contemporary readers' awareness of the inequality between the effort to procure food and the meagre outcomes, portrayed through a symphony of smells, a shocking juxtaposition of food abundance and scarcity, and a conflict of states needing interpretation. Orwell sets the two capitals in a mirroring progression where reflections magnify or diminish depending on people's involvement in solving the constant dilemma of survival. While Paris offers the poor a chance to look for work, London reduces the struggle to mere begging for food, which is officially banned. The layered perspective brings the reader to a stark realization: a heavenly meal in a Parisian restaurant may have been prepared in "the hell of" a kitchen. In London, reality unfolds on a horizontal plane, where charities providing food deprive the poor of the chance to work for it. The contexts differ, but the props remain the same: filth, famine and an abundance of feelings.

Keywords: *food studies, postwar literature, poverty, tramp, George Orwell*

Down and Out in Paris and London is Orwell's "first work of social exploration", a literary genre "founded upon the ignorance of the prosperous concerning their impoverished fellow citizens" (Clarke 2007: 14-16). The book recounts the unnamed narrator's personal experiences, aiming to shed light on the causes, manifestations, and impacts of poverty at both individual and societal levels. Orwell's decision to leave the narrator unnamed, along with his use of second-person moralising, transforms the narrative into a powerful social document. This approach invites readers to confront the true face of reality and encourages a response of awareness, compassion and a call for change.

Described as a "memoir, reportage, autobiography, travel diary and autobiographical fiction" and rejected several times to the author's dismay (Quinn 2009: 133-134), the book was finally published in January 1933. The chronology of the events is the reversed picture of reality: the narrator's immersion into the state of poverty starts in London and then continues in Paris. The reason Orwell "set out to explore the lower depths of English society,

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the world of itinerant tramps" (133) was to become a credible voice defending the rights of these people: "Poverty is what I am writing about, and I had my first contact with poverty in this slum. The slum, with its dirt and its queer lives, was first an object-lesson in poverty and then the background of my own experiences." (Orwell 2008: 8) Orwell's book is grounded in the historical and social context of postwar Paris and London, yet it transcends these specific settings to issue warnings relevant to contemporary life, particularly in times of rising conflict. The postwar period mirrors current times, where tensions and instability persist. By moving from specific examples to broader societal themes, Orwell effectively builds credibility with his readers. His journalistic talent in presenting facts with clarity and confidence lends authenticity to the narrative. However, readers are encouraged to look beyond any potential bias shaped by the historical moment, engaging more critically with the underlying issues.

Critics have examined *Down and Out in Paris and London* from various angles, including political commentary, social exploration, poverty, injustice and religion. In his chapter from *Bloom's Modern Critical Reviews*, Roger Fowler highlights the role of food and the grim conditions of the kitchens described by Orwell. He briefly mentions the "pretentious but filthy and disorganised restaurant" where Orwell worked after his stint at Hotel X. Fowler ties these observations into his broader analysis of Orwell's use of naturalism, realism and even surrealism, noting how Orwell evokes vivid, hellish imagery using simple, everyday language: "Remarkably, this highly picturesque and impressionistic writing, with a strong literary heritage in images of hell, is achieved with a very ordinary vocabulary." (Fowler 2007: 38) This paper seeks to consolidate these observations on the struggle for food, encouraging deeper reflection on the inequalities and contradictions inherent in such a struggle.

The book begins by vividly depicting the atmosphere of rue du Coq d'Or: "a sort of French Impressionist slum" (Calls 2013: 33). Orwell immerses the reader in a sensory-laden experience, with food presented in a decayed state amidst the chaotic street life: "Quarrels, desolate cries of street hawkers, shouts of children chasing orange peel, and at night, loud singing and the sour reek of the refuse-carts." (Orwell 2008: 3-4) Orwell's use of capitalised words, such as BISTROS, imprints visual markers for readers. The narrator's stay at the Hotel des Trois Moineaux (Hotel of Three Sparrows) gains symbolic significance when viewed through the lens of biblical references to God's charity: "Look at the birds of the air; they do not sow or reap or store away in barns, and yet your heavenly Father feeds them. Are you not much more valuable than they?" (Matthew 6:26), mirroring a distorted form of charity observed in the English tramps.

Some of the lodgers living in the Parisian area are "fantastically poor" (Orwell 2008: 5) which gives the narrator the insight that, "Poverty frees them

from ordinary standards of behaviour, just as money frees people from work.” (5-6) The concept of freedom experienced by the poor manifests in various forms: freedom from the burden of possessions, freedom of will and the limited freedom to choose from a narrow set of options. It includes the freedom from having to make complex choices about food, the liberty to act without responsibility and the ability to justify undesirable behaviour or poor hygiene due to the lack of adequate food and shelter. Ultimately, it extends to freedom in facing death, as the poor are unburdened by material possessions both in life and in death.

For someone accustomed to taking daily meals for granted, the narrator's description of the strategies involved in procuring food evokes a deep sense of gratitude for not enduring such hardship and embarrassment. From the desire to create the illusion that one goes out to eat to the hard decision of buying slightly more expensive bread made of rye just because it is smaller and easier to smuggle in one's pockets, the way the poor person has to calculate everything and see this as wasting, not as spending, is impressive:

This wastes you a franc a day. Sometimes, to keep up appearances, you have to spend sixty centimes on a drink, and go correspondingly short of food. Your linen gets filthy, and you run out of soap and razor-blades. Your hair wants cutting, and you try to cut it yourself, with such fearful results that you have to go to the barber after all, and spend the equivalent of a day's food. All day you are telling lies, and expensive lies. (Orwell 2008: 18)

Edward Quinn describes the struggle to make ends meet as a form of “eccentricity”, viewing it as “another outgrowth of poverty, as various people, pushed to extremes, resort to bizarre and complex coping strategies” (2009: 158). Disaster may strike when filth invites bugs into one's living space, threatening what little food is available:

You have spent your last eighty centimes on half a litre of milk, and are boiling it over the spirit lamp. While it boils a bug runs down your forearm; you give the bug a flick with your nail, and it falls, plop! straight into the milk. There is nothing for it but to throw the milk away and go foodless. (Orwell 2008: 18)

The hungry narrator's decision to discard the milk may seem whimsical, but beyond the health risks, it reflects a desire to preserve dignity, even amid extreme poverty. To worsen the situation, a baker might cut a slightly larger piece of bread than the poor person can afford, deepening their despair and pushing them to avoid the bakery in the future.

With only bread and margarine to sustain them, the Parisian poor come to truly understand the agony of hunger as they pass by shop windows filled with lavish displays of food: “huge, wasteful piles; whole dead pigs, baskets of hot loaves, great yellow blocks of butter, strings of sausages, mountains of

potatoes, vast Gruyere cheeses like grindstones" (19). This sight triggers a double struggle—intense physical hunger combined with self-pity and dread over the temptation to steal food and the fear of getting caught. The scene vividly contrasts the abundance of food with the overwhelming surge of negative emotions stemming from deprivation.

The simple, meagre diet of bread and margarine serves as a grim bond between the poor of Paris and London, uniting them in their shared struggle for survival. This diet leaves a lasting, hopeless mark on the faces of the destitute in both cities: "A man who has gone even a week on bread and margarine is no longer a man, merely a belly with a few accessory organs." (19-20) While the aftermath of World War I shaped both cities differently, with Paris focusing on poverty and London on homelessness, the environments still echo similar post-war realities. In London, this shift may be justified by a remark of Phil Lyon (2020): "World War I had drawn men from the labour market for military service and provided opportunities for young women, in large numbers, to engage with employment in offices and factories rather than domestic service." (2020: 179) According to Quinn, the mirror reflection is distorted and inverted, though the background stays largely consistent, mirroring the post-war realities: "The difference between Paris and London is the difference between poverty and homelessness." (2009: 159) Moreover, this difference is evident in the use of language, the levels of hope and the limited employment opportunities—jobs that are basic and demeaning, yet offer the prospect of having enough to eat and earning a bit of money to be spent solely on survival necessities. In France, however, the PLONGEUR can at least take pride in purchasing their own bread, margarine and wine, provided these are not supplied as part of their job allowance.

Stepping into the role of a PLONGEUR—the slave in the burgeoning modern world—the narrator poses a question that should resonate with many: "why this life goes on—what purpose it serves, and who wants it to continue, and why I am not taking the merely rebellious, FAINEANT attitude" (Orwell 2008: 138). The "dark labyrinthine passages" (63) leading to the kitchen of Hotel X, where the narrator and his Russian friend Boris eventually find work, may symbolise the life journey of the impoverished. In the boiling bowels of the kitchen, "the same heat and cramped space and warm reek of food, and a humming, whirring noise" (63-64) hurl the reader into the hidden mechanism that creates the luxurious dishes served in the luxury and tranquillity of the restaurant above. The image of "a boy with a great slab of veal on his shoulder, his cheek pressed into the damp, spongy flesh" and the cry of "'SAUVE-TOI, IDIOT!'" (64) create a naturalistic tableau that, according to Fowler (2007: 38), borders on hyperrealism. This contrast juxtaposes the stark reality of a kitchen where corpses are transformed into gourmet dishes with the echo of a desperate plea to escape from this inferno. "Roughly speaking, the more one

pays for food, the more sweat and spittle one is obliged to eat with it" (Orwell 2008: 93). Orwell's statement aims to alert diners to a startling reality. While he has been criticised for presenting an exaggeratedly negative view of Parisian hotels and restaurants, Ingle (2006: 50) sees in Orwell's work a "wider and more trenchant criticism of the nature of society". In this perspective, what is expensive is cheap and what is cheap is costly. Those who can afford it end up paying a premium for food that, in reality, is of lower quality.

Since food becomes the core of most conversations, the manner of speaking becomes lethargic. The hungry person finds solace in solitude and laziness. People may resort to reading in times of starvation as movement is impeded by the frailty of the body. The hungry person discovers life, culture and arts from a different angle, inaccessible to others:

Hunger reduces one to an utterly spineless, brainless condition, more like the after-effects of influenza than anything else. It is as though one had been turned into a jellyfish, or as though all one's blood had been pumped out and luke-warm water substituted. Complete inertia is my chief memory of hunger. (Orwell 2008: 42-43)

As hunger becomes overwhelming, the narrator falls into despair, a state noted by his friend Boris: "How easily you despair, MON AMI! Where is that English obstinacy I have read about? Courage! We'll manage it." (46). Boris attempts to lift his spirits and considers various strategies to devise a plan for salvation. The plan involves pawning their last possessions, requiring it to function effectively like a wartime tactic: "Boris was so pleased with this scheme (he called it UNE RUSE DE GUERRE) that he almost forgot being hungry" (45). However, Boris must come up with alternative solutions since they need papers to pawn their items and locate a new pawnshop. Fortune seems to intervene when he discovers a "five-sou piece" on the pavement, allowing them to buy a pound of potatoes which they "wolfed [...] skins and all", feeling rejuvenated (47-48). Additionally, due to an error by the pawnshop clerk, they end up with a fifty-franc note, which provides them with "bread and wine, a piece of meat, and alcohol for the stove" (48-49). The narrator conveys such depth of relief from the anguish of hunger that the reader experiences the characters' joy with equal intensity. A significant term in this context is "gorge", which the author uses to describe their ravenous approach to food. This sense of relief infuses Boris with renewed optimism, prompting him to exclaim: "The fortune of war!" (49) This word choice is further illustrated in another episode, where the narrator reflects on how hunger alters the perception of food: "Have you noticed how bread tastes when you have been hungry for a long time? Cold, wet, doughy—like putty almost. But, Jesus Christ, how good it was! As for the wine, I sucked it all down in one draught, and it seemed to go straight into my veins and flow round my body like new

blood.” Valenti, the Italian recounting this moment, “wolfed the whole two pounds of bread without stopping to take breath” (101).

The dire circumstances faced by various ethnic groups in Paris enhance the author’s skill in portraying diverse characters. Contemporary readers encounter descriptions that extend beyond the text itself. However, a deeper examination reveals that the Jewish pawnshop owner, criticised for not meeting the expectations of the impoverished, might actually be a benefactor to those who rely on pawning personal items to buy food. Similarly, the Russian friend is a complex figure in the struggle for sustenance. While he uplifts the author’s spirits, maintains hope, brings food and devises financial rescue plans, he also challenges the author’s moral inclinations. He proposes an opportunity to work for a secret society by writing articles on English politics for a Russian newspaper—a scheme that turns out to be a deception, an attempt by desperate individuals or swindlers, as the narrator calls them, to make quick money.

Orwell’s direct observations, laced with ironic criticism, do not spare any particular nationality, underscoring the idea that the world comprises diverse people, all sharing similar virtues and vices. The placement of different nationalities in unexpected roles is disheartening: for example, an Englishman seeking a *PLONGEUR* position—a slave’s slave position—in a Russian restaurant, despite the dubious moral standing of the prospective patron. Encountering the future restaurant owner and his French wife sparks food-related imagery in the narrator: “dead-white face and scarlet lips, reminding me of cold veal and tomatoes” (59). The prospect of the new restaurant opening in a fortnight further widens the gap in their ongoing struggle for stability and steady pay. The narrator and his Russian friend spend their last money on bread and garlic, using it to enhance the flavour of their meagre food and make it last longer. The state of hunger prompts one of the narrator’s most extended reflections on food:

...we wrote dinner menus on the backs of envelopes. We were too hungry even to try and think of anything except food. I remember the dinner Boris finally selected for himself. It was: a dozen oysters, borsch soup (the red, sweet, beetroot soup with cream on top), crayfishes, a young chicken en *CASSEROLE*, beef with stewed plums, new potatoes, a salad, suet pudding and *Roquefort* cheese, with a litre of Burgundy and some old brandy. Boris had international tastes in food. Later on, when we were prosperous, I occasionally saw him eat meals almost as large without difficulty. (61)

It is the optimistic Boris who first secures a job at Hotel X and subsequently brings a selection of French delicacies—“minced veal, a wedge of *Camembert* cheese, bread and an *éclair*, all jumbled together”—to his friend, who briefly subsists “entirely on stolen food” (62), before he himself gets hired as a

PLONGEUR at the same hotel. Working as a PLONGEUR and receiving payment elevates the narrator's perception to a new level: he says that "I had no sensation of poverty" and feels a "heavy contentment, the contentment a well-fed beast might feel, in a life which had become so simple" (106), as "being hungry had taught me the true value of food." (107)

When the narrator later describes his work in the Russian owner's restaurant, readers are presented with a stark and unsettling depiction of the backroom conditions: "The conditions behind the kitchen door were akin to a pigsty" (125) and "the floor was usually an inch deep in a mixture of trampled food" (126). The scene is marked by precariousness and filth: "Meat, vegetables, and other items lay on the bare earth, overrun by rats and cats" (127). The impression conveyed is that of a chaotic battlefield, with the cook continuously shouting orders laced with profanity. This rare female character makes a strong impression: she is a stout, loud individual who studied music in Vienna but now has to endure a "CRISE DE NERFS" (130), whenever there are customers to serve.

The similarities between the two capitals are evident in the pervasive poverty that engulfs and depletes and the strategies used to escape the relentless cycle of starvation. Filth emerges as a ravenous monster, taking on hyperbolic proportions: it permeates the clothing of the poor, their homes and the kitchens of the restaurants where they work, accumulating from discarded or improperly managed food waste. This filth grows like an organic mass, a kind of mulch that covers everything and promises a potential for life beneath it. Despite immersing the reader in an overwhelmingly unpleasant smell and sight, this filth sustains the fabric of society – it is the sacrificed lives of the poor that nourish the lives of the rich. In London, the stifling, stinking stench of poverty seems to go unnoticed by those who could bring about change and improvement, presenting itself as a kind of entrenched institutionalized filth. Thus, the emaciated bodies of PLONGEURS and tramps contribute to the broader backdrop of waste. Their physical deterioration reflects the severe lack of access to food. At the entrance of a workhouse in London, the tramps "in the mass, lounging" present a "disgusting sight; nothing villainous or dangerous, but a graceless, mangy crew, nearly all ragged and palpably underfed" (170). Here, they have a slim chance of receiving a bath, some food and work the next morning – specifically, "peeling potatoes for the pauper's dinner" (175). The tramps' conversations often focus on the "spikes" or "casual wards" in England (165), where they can be admitted for only one night, making them perpetual wanderers. After having a bath in the filth left by the others, they receive their supper: "Each man's ration is a half-pound wedge of bread smeared with margarine, and a pint of bitter sugarless cocoa in a tin billy. Sitting on the floor we wolfed this in five minutes..." (173). Breakfast is "identical to the previous night's supper" (175), leading to widespread

undernourishment. Although they are given meal tickets for coffee-shops along the route, the irony is that tramps are often cheated out of even this minimal amount of food. For example, the: “serving-maid, seeing our tickets and recognizing us as tramps, placed two ‘large teas’ and four slices of bread with dripping on the table – equivalent to eightpence worth of food. It turned out that the shop regularly cheated tramps out of twopence or so on each ticket.” (177)

Paddy, the tramp whom the narrator befriends in London, has “lank cheeks with a greyish, grimy appearance” (178). This young man, who served two years in the war and lost his job, is “horribly ashamed of being a tramp, but he had picked up all a tramp’s ways” (178-179). Despite his emaciated state, his moral character shines through in his reaction to the opportunity to steal a bottle of milk from a doorstep. His sickly, drooping face reveals his inner struggle: “‘Best leave it. It don’t do a man no good to steal. T’ank God, I ain’t never stolen nothin’ yet.’” The narrator offers a paradoxical explanation for Paddy’s stance: “It was funk, bred of hunger, that kept him virtuous. With only two or three sound meals in his belly, he would have found courage to steal the milk.” (179) Paddy’s hunger extends beyond mere food, shaping him into the “regular character of a tramp – abject, envious, a jackal’s character” (181), who resents those who work and blames unemployment on foreigners. Nevertheless, the narrator balances the negative view by highlighting Paddy’s positive traits: “he was a good fellow, generous by nature and capable of sharing his last crust with a friend” (182). His prospects for employment were hindered by “two years of bread and margarine”, as he “had lived on this filthy imitation of food till his own mind and body were compounded of inferior stuff. It was malnutrition and not any native vice that had destroyed his manhood” (182). For Paddy, even one decent meal a day was considered “a wild extravagance”, while food “had come to mean simply bread and margarine – the eternal tea-and-two-slices, which will cheat hunger for an hour or two” (213). Thus, the reader understands that a tramp’s only real pleasure is “the occasional tea-and-two-slices” (214).

What is surprising is that all these stark realities sharply contrast with the hopes the narrator harbors as he travels to London. At the start of Chapter XXIV, he is en route to his homeland, reflecting confidently: “There are, indeed, many things in England that make you glad to get home; bathrooms, armchairs, mint sauce, new potatoes properly cooked, brown bread, marmalade, beer made with veritable hops – they are all splendid, if you can pay for them.” (150). And then he adds: “It was, at any rate, notoriously impossible to starve in London, so there was nothing to be anxious about.” (152) However, the crude reality soon brings him to a sobering realization: the streets of London are filled with poor tramps in alarming numbers, perpetually

searching for a place to stay, as the spikes (or casual wards) can only provide accommodation for one night.

In London, where begging was illegal, church charities provided tea and two slices of bread to the needy. What is striking in the book is that these charities offer the same type of food but in larger quantities. However, Brennan's in-depth critique highlights a critical view: Nonetheless, in his in-depth analysis of the critical aspects of the book, Brennan notes: "Church missionary work supporting the poor of London becomes in *Down and Out* a Babel of competing, meaningless tongues, with bland words of salvation dispensed as the obligatory cost of paltry food and warmth" (2017: 36). The narrator's portrayal of the tramps' reaction to charity food reveals their contempt for these offerings, which they even find humiliating. Gratitude appears as a shattered concept, nearly nonexistent among the tramps who have been denied any opportunity for a dignified life.

Attempts to provide the tramps with sustenance for a few hours evoke no visible gratitude: "Evidently the tramps were not grateful for their tea. And yet it was excellent tea [...] and we were all glad of it. I am sure too that it was given in a good spirit, without any intention of humiliating us; so in fairness we ought to have been grateful—still, we were not." (Orwell 2008: 169) A similar incident later in the book depicts the tramps receiving "a one-pound jam-jar of tea each, with six slices of bread and margarine", and then they "the tramps began to misbehave in the most outrageous way", leading the narrator to remark: "One would not have thought such scenes possible in a church." (217) The intellectual and physical nourishment provided by the church services and the food offered by church charities are strikingly similar to the generally inadequate food available to the tramps—lacking in nutrients and substance. Unsurprisingly, the expected gratitude manifests instead as indecent, even childish mockery. Orwell concludes with a surprising observation: "A man receiving charity practically always hates his benefactor—it is a fixed characteristic of human nature..." (219). This underscores the idea that charity fails to elicit gratitude because people should be allowed to earn their food and thus feel a sense of responsibility.

The only genuine gratitude the tramp displays is towards a "nice, chubby, youngish" clergyman who, "shy and embarrassed", hands out food tickets without "waiting to be thanked" (220). Unlike most people in religious contexts, who exhibit a patronising attitude, this clergyman exemplifies what a true Christian should be. This brief episode seems intended to highlight qualities that Christians might reflect on and emulate. Similarly, Orwell subtly critiques Christian practices through Paddy the tramp's view of the book *Of the Imitation of Christ* as "blasphemy" (180), using this as a sharp commentary on the disparity between Christian teachings and their actual application. This

reversal prompts readers to ponder how Christian principles should materialise in reality.

Outside of London, other locations in England offer similarly bleak prospects. According to Billy the Tramp, Kent is another area where many people resort to mooching, with bakers more likely to throw away their bread than give it to beggars. Oxford is also noted as a prime spot for begging, where he recounts: "I mooched bread, and I mooched bacon, and I mooched beef, and every night I mooched tanners for my kip off of the students." (223)

The mirror held up by the author reveals global issues: poverty, the right to a decent job and diet, and society's responsibility to create an environment where people can find work rather than rely on charity and suffer from despondency and humiliation. As Peter Brian Barry notes in *George Orwell: The Ethics of Equality*: "The food and diet of the poor is also a source of shame" (2023: 181). This shame leads Boris, the narrator's friend, to comment that "It is fatal to look hungry. [...] It makes people want to kick you." (Orwell 2008: 58) The denial of the poor's dignity, both in securing adequate food and in caring for their bodies, traps them in a multi-layered prison: one imposed by society, another by their physical condition and yet another by the despair within their minds.

The overwhelming number of tramps underscores the failure of society to address employment gaps, revealing a deep scar left by the war. Amidst the booming industrialisation, the image of countless hopeless individuals needing food and care is profoundly disheartening. George Orwell concludes his exploration of poverty by proposing solutions for a struggling postwar society, acutely aware of the ills caused by a lack of food and hope. The narrator suggests that workhouses could evolve into partially self-supporting institutions, where tramps, by settling and contributing according to need, would no longer be tramps. They would engage in meaningful work, receive decent food and live a stable life (246). By the end of the book, the narrator expresses a commitment to avoid harsh judgments of individuals while considering the broader context that has led to such circumstances.

Adopting an inside perspective has allowed the author to delve deeply into poverty and the desperate struggle for food. Given that the text represents Orwell's personal view, which includes elements of bias, readers should examine the issues from multiple perspectives to better understand the conditions leading to poverty, the moral dilemmas faced in trying to make ends meet and the resulting consequences. Orwell's frequent references to bread, margarine and tea, within a world where waste becomes filth and people are seen through the lens of food, prompt readers to develop a deep sense of gratitude for their own abundance. In times of conflict or scarcity, the quest for food becomes central to survival and Orwell's text serves as a powerful wake-up call for those who cannot imagine such a life-and-death struggle. Further

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studies on how the theme of striving for food as a reflection of the ongoing struggle for justice is addressed by authors from various ethnic backgrounds will help determine whether Orwell's insights remain relevant for future generations.

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Savouring the Veiled Narratives of Banquet Menus

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Abstract

The study explores the semiotic significance of late 19th to early 20th-century Romanian banquet menus, transcending culinary functions to convey broader societal messages. By examining thirty menus from Romania and Austro-Hungarian Romanian-speaking Transylvania, predominantly sourced from newspapers, it reveals banquets as platforms for political and social expression. Written in Romanian or French, these menus serve as conduits for political opinions, declarations of friendship or enmity, and expressions of pride or despair. Intentionally published in newspapers, they reflect a society valuing freedom of speech and exhibit a discernible discursive character, treating food as intellectual nourishment. The coverage of banquets in newspapers offers glimpses into contemporaneous events and personalities, serving as historical documents shedding light on overlooked events and individuals. Through the examination of these menus' meanings, researchers gain insights into forgotten personalities and societal dynamics, illustrating the enduring cultural significance of food beyond mere sustenance.

Keywords: *banquet menus, pre-war Romania, food and memory, zeitgeist, food as a platform*

Introduction

A meal is a composite entity comprising cooked foods, their socially constructed tastes, and the protocols dictating how they should be consumed – a set of manners, codes, and labels (Barthes, 2008). However, food transcends its immediate sensory experience; it serves as a sign, revealing identity, terroir, and even a nation by triggering “imagined metonymies” associated with a particular culture (Sobral, 2019). While the symbolic power of food is often discussed in the context of diplomatic gatherings involving world leaders, this article contends that ordinary individuals also leverage food as a communicative tool. This view follows the idea put forward by Linda Morgan: “All commensality signals information to the individuals at table, including messages of status and symbolic kinship.” (2012: 146) It also takes into account the notion of food proposed by Claude Lévi-Strauss (1969) as being good to think with, which finds resonance in the examination of late 19th to early 20th-century Romanian banquet menus, which go beyond culinary considerations

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to convey broader statements and messages. This study aims to unravel the intricate semiotics associated with gastronomy by delving into menus that provide intellectual nourishment before satiating physical appetites.

Methodology

Cookbooks, though informative about gender roles, economy, culture and other aspects of society, are prescriptive in nature and may not accurately depict what people truly cook and eat (Albala, 2012: 229-231). In contrast, banquet menus offer a unique window into the actual meals consumed, making them more credible sources. Their content and ceremonial nature reveal valuable insights into societal views, beliefs, and practices prevalent at a given time.

This essay meticulously examines thirty menus from banquets held in the Kingdom of Romania and Austro-Hungarian Romanian-speaking Transylvania during the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Most of the analysed menus have been sourced from newspapers, with only two found in books, and a few foreign menus retrieved from the Internet. Today, many of them are collectibles, especially when signed by illustrious guests. These documents have been treated as artefacts and subjected to systematic review. A taxonomy has been constructed through successive rounds of coding, categorising menus based on a central theme, with connotations related to either entertainment or politics. The study does not focus on aspects of food such as seasonality, taste, complexity, price, class or status. While chronological order is not strictly adhered to, menus have been grouped based on their overarching message. Although not employing prosopography, the analysis of these menus collectively offers insights into the beliefs and attitudes of their authors.

History of the menu

The term “menu” as defined by the 2009 edition of *New Larousse Gastronomique* was first officially used in 1718 “but the custom of making such a list is much older” being a “bill of fare of ceremonial meals [...] displayed on the wall and enabled kitchen staff, in particular, to follow the order in which dishes should be served”. While historical documentation of menus is scarce before the 19th century, instances such as the 879 BC Banquet Stela documenting Assurnasirpal’s feast (Mark, 2020) and the distribution of menus in Chinese Song dynasty restaurants during the 13th century (Gernet, 1962) offer glimpses into early festive culinary practices. The prevalence of menus in the Western world, primarily in written form, became more pronounced in the late 18th century and evolved stylistically over time, mirroring changes in typography and culinary fashion.

Menus serve the dual purpose of conveying a restaurant’s standard offerings and providing information about special selections tailored for

specific events or guests, such as dinners or banquets honouring notable individuals, professional organisations, cultural entities, military units, and more. In the French culinary lexicon mentioned above, “menu” refers to a set meal with its composition determined collaboratively by the restaurant manager and the paying party, while *à la carte* encompasses the comprehensive list of dishes available daily on the premises. This research primarily focuses on the discursive nature of banquet menus.

Social and historical context

The 19th century marked a transformative period for Romania, a nation that had historically comprised separate regions – the largest being Moldova, Wallachia and Transylvania— the first two within and outside the Ottoman Empire’s influence, the last under the Hungarian and, later, Austro-Hungarian’s Empire domination. The aspiration for national unity gained momentum, leading to the unification of Moldova and Wallachia in 1859. Efforts to include Transylvania and other smaller Romanian-language regions under foreign rule, Bukovina and Bessarabia, intensified (Boia, 2022). By the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Romania emerged as a young independent monarchy undergoing rapid change, fuelled by significant social and political shifts (Hitchins, 2015). The era witnessed the convergence of liberal and conservative ideologies, activism within cultural elites, and a dynamic political landscape (see Queen Mary of Romania’s memoirs). Banquets and social events became platforms for expressing political and social sentiments. Newspapers played a crucial role in reporting on the activities of political parties, cultural elites, and other entities. Banquets, covered by journalists, provided insights into the lives of the middle class, reflecting culinary heritage and serving as mirrors of socio-demographic groups. These banquets, while not entirely private or public, acted as snapshots in time, revealing the names of notable attendees, their patriotic discourses, and the laudatory toasts exchanged.

Doctors and professors frequently found themselves the subjects of honour during retirement celebrations or upon receiving prestigious titles or new positions within local hospitals or universities. Trade unions, cooperatives, cultural associations, political parties, newspapers and various professional bodies organised events to pay tribute to leaders, commemorate anniversaries, and celebrate successful resolutions to conflicts. Newspaper articles offered uncritical coverage and thus provide valuable context and insights for today’s researchers.

The banquets *per se* serve as evidence of culinary heritage, but some of the menus crafted for private events also function as mirrors of specific socio-demographic groups or, at the very least, their hosts. The menus themselves became vehicles for expressing political opinions, declarations of friendship or enmity, and various other reflections. A good example would be the

nationalism-infused rhetoric of one Cluj-based professor or the apparently light-hearted war remembrance of one Moldavian military menu. By examining these banquets and their menus, researchers gain access to a slice of history that reflects the attitudes and reactions of normal individuals to the realities of their time, encompassing themes of war, political disillusionment, patriotism, nationalism, economic prosperity, professional pride, disenchantment, frustration, and a spectrum of other emotions.

In contrast, conventional menus of the time tended to be straightforward and descriptive. Most menus primarily listed the main ingredients and applied techniques such as “Foie gras en Bellevue” or paid homage to individuals, as exemplified by “Gateaux Boissier aux Pistaches,” created by Maison Capşa to honour its founder’s French mentor; wines were typically listed by vineyard and vintage, maintaining linguistic simplicity (all examples are taken from a May 1885 banquet menu of the Jockey Club). The British Colony in Bucharest celebrated Queen’s Victoria Jubilee in June 1897 with what seems to be a very simple and plainly phrased menu made of “soup, sterlet, roast beef, *vol-au-vent*, roast duck and chicken, salad, asparagus, ices, dessert, coffee”; they did have two wines and champagne, though. The Royal family of Romania had a clearly richer menu in 1890 on their visit to the recently annexed province of Dobrogea to launch the construction works of a bridge over the Danube; they dined on *caviar frais*, *consommé à la Royale*, sturgeon, *bécasse*, *fromage*, dessert, old sherry, wine and *champagne Pommery frappé* (Dinu, 2019). Royals are bound to keep it simple and neutral, so no embellishment on the wording here nor in other more important menus such as the British royal ones. Diana Spencer’s wedding to Charles, Prince of Wales, in 1981, offered a menu that was deliberately concise in French, the language of food and formality. Iconic historical menus, like those on the Titanic or from the Orient Express, lacked linguistic or semiotic nuances too and even contemporary examples, such as El Bulli’s farewell dinner in 2011, featuring a spectacular 49-course feast, employed a simple, functional, and descriptive menu language, reflecting the prevailing fashion of the time (Franklin and Johnson, 2019: 57, 166). While conventional menus may or may not convey much about people and their times, this article focuses on menus that go beyond mere descriptions of food, categorising them as either having or lacking entertainment value or political significance.

Do play with your food

Over a few decades, in the Romanian-speaking regions and especially Moldova, renowned for hosting a large number of writers, banquet menus ventured beyond traditional culinary descriptions to offer an engaging reading experience that goes beyond typical gastronomic delights. Some menus stand out for their entertainment value, devoid of any hidden agenda, designed solely to amuse. One such menu, dated 1912, from a trip to the village of

Bârnova by the Unirea Printing House Workers Society, humorously announces a “salad that is mixed but not soiled,” a “spritz made with wine as old as Gutenberg,” and a “nonpareil coffee.” [1] Another, composed in verse, from *Evenimentul* (1920), playfully describes dishes, such as this fish:

Then, spicy as a *bon mot*
A fish in sauce *ravigot*
Surely Cotnari wine will not miss, its gloss
Allows the sturgeon to swim not only in sauce

On 3 January 1897, *Evenimentul* newspaper reported on a New Year’s Eve traditional party hosted by Professor Doctor Sculy, where guests were informed of unconventional dishes like “sarcoma liver *paté*”, “fresh human brains”, and *consommé* with hydatid parasites. The menu included humorous elements such as “soupperime” made with “liberal-conservative truffles” and a medical punch named “magnesium citrate”, ending with an “ideo ataxique” champagne affecting movement coordination. Another New Year’s Eve medical banquet in the previous year featured quinine, ricin oil, tar, and goose *à la* iodine, with mineral water replacing wine. The menu concluded with the doctor’s post-party diet recommendations.

In 1919, the Journalists Trade Union of Moldova offered a banquet with a “summary” menu containing “various news” as entrees, a *consommé* served with “less important pieces”, and a play on words with ham and eggs. The menu included “forbidden fruits”, “old wine from the current year”, “veritable ersatz coffee” and censored ice cream. Years later, the journalists of *Adevărul* rejoiced upon positively settling a conflict with one Toma Bazilescu dining on “Harpagon caviar”, probably referring to a rather small quantity, and a “republican mayo on a monarchic sturgeon” (*Dimineața*, 1933).

Engineers too displayed creativity in their menus. In 1889, Romanian alumni of a Zürich polytechnic school designed a menu featuring “fillet of bovine locomotive”, “geological bonbons”, “coffee from the chemistry lab”, “liqueurs for the sedimentary formation”, and “eruptive cognac” (*Românulu*, 1889). In 1911, Moldavian train engineers created a menu mirroring a project’s phases, from terrain study to reception (*Mișcarea*, 1911). Various other professional groups crafted amusing menus, such as the Social Sciences Group mentioning minorities, religion, and local administration in their banquet (*Opinia*, 1897). Naturalists celebrated 1922 New Year’s Eve with *hors d’oeuvres* spiked with essence of *Prunus* (brandy) and *Sus scrofa*, a wild boar dish that required a parenthesis to clarify the local saying about the arrogance of a sow in a tree. Traders celebrated with humour as well. A banquet honouring Mr Richard R. Tuffli featured “a little old brandy” paired with “collaborative olives”, “legally imported fish”, “syndicate member lamb steak”, and “wine spilt in 1916” (*Evenimentul*, 1920). A Cooperative banquet in 1883 proudly and

entertainingly displayed local ingredients and brands, showcasing crayfish, deer, rabbit, cognac, and wines. These menus reflect a rich tradition of wit, creativity, and camaraderie across various professional and social circles in Romania, blending culinary delights with humour and cultural references.

Military personnel also demonstrated their wit through creative and thematic menus. In 1909, a war-inspired menu was served at the Royal Court, featuring dishes such as “surveillance-ready soup”, “fish shell from the arsenal waters”, “bullets of the shrapnel” peas, frozen cannon fires, and “Ready!” coffee (Dinu, 2019). In March 1919, the 4th Queen Mary Roşiori Regiment had a lunch comprised of “Oituz-like liver *pâte*”, lamb prepared like in the trenches, shrapnel-like peas with cheese, ice from the Carpathian Mountains and “English, not Turkish, coffee”, while wine was Romanian and French, from the renowned Bordeaux region (Iorga and Iorga, 2015: 149).

During a banquet on 1 September 1913, honouring Lt. Col. Raicovici, a respected military figure and storyteller, the menu reflected his troops’ experiences during the Second Balkan War. Dishes included “anti-cholera cognac”, “disinfectant brandy”, fish roe salad, and charcuterie with Bulgarian names. Each item carried historical significance, connecting to lesser-known war sites and highlighting soldiers’ experiences (*Evenimentul*, 1913). Similarly, a banquet for the 4th Battalion of Hunters in Moldova during the same Balkan War structured its menu as a strategic battle. With dishes symbolising military actions, the menu included references to the Bulgarian river Iskar sturgeon, illusions of the enemy (*vol-au-vent* pastry compared to Bulgarian prime minister’s dreams), and a counter-offensive with red meat. The dessert section simulated the attack, complete with a charlotte cake made using army crockery and a “comma-free compote”, made of foraged Mirabelle plum, where ubiquitous worms are the commas. Military menus extended beyond battles to the cultural realm.

Intellectuals and cultural societies played with food and menus in their own ways. In 1885, Junimea, the famous leading cultural society, one which brought Moldavian writers and thinkers together under the motto “enters who wants to, stays who manages” sent a “summons” for its 22nd traditional lunch, emphasising the importance of drinking over eating. *Revista Nouă* literary magazine initiated a tradition in 1889, celebrating each year with a lunch for staff and contributors. The menu started with *hors d’oeuvres à la Hagi Tudose*, a Romanian Harpagon known to have asked the cat’s tail to be cut, so cold would not enter the room. It continued with *potage julienne à la Trandafiloff*, an allusion to an 1844 political affair involving a Russian receiving an abusive mining concession from the Wallachian government. Other dishes held literary allusions, such as *Petit pates aux “legende costiniane”* and the *Parfait au café* or the “drunkard’s repentance” champagne – all references to works that have been previously published by the magazine. Even in New York, an 1868 literary

dinner at Delmonico's, to honour Charles Dickens, featured creatively named dishes, connecting to famous authors known for their literary and culinary contributions – e.g. Fenimore Cooper, *Temple de la literature* and *file de boeuf à la Lucullus*, *creme d'asperges à la Dumas*, *timbales à la Dickens*, all references to authors famous for their gastronomic interest and culinary prowess (Franklin and Johnson, 2019: 166).

These menus show the diverse ways in which traders, military personnel and intellectuals used humour, creativity, and cultural references to enrich their dining experiences and commemorate significant events in history.

Talking politics at the dinner table

In 1881, C.A. Rosetti's banquet celebrating his newspaper's 25th anniversary featured a menu subtly infused with patriotism. It deviates slightly from the norm, but it is still conventional, marginally bent to customise it for its guest of honour. Dishes such as *timbale de poulardes à la Rosetti* and beef fillet *à la Plevna* honoured the pivotal 1877 Battle of Plevna, symbolising Romania's independence from the Ottoman Empire. They were all washed down with Chateau Lafitte 1869 and champagne Roederer. The evening, hosted at Le Grand Hôtel du Boulevard or, according to other sources, at the National Theatre Bucharest, saw wife Maria Rosetti and other ladies dressed in national costumes, adding a cultural touch to the celebration (Cebuc 1969).

Dimitrie Butculescu, a prominent archaeologist and a highly regarded president of merchants and manufacturers, received several banquets in his honour. His menus cleverly blended professional pride with patriotic elements. The Liga Culturală's 1891 party showcased a harmonious mix of Carpathian brandy, Balkan mastic, Bulgarian cucumbers, Saxon ambrosia, Oriental coffee, and Moldova's foundational mythic beef, celebrating the diverse ethnicities coexisting in Romania; a two-verse folk stanza further emphasised the country's richness and timeless Romanian identity. In 1894, Butculescu elevated his menu (Jaklovszky, 1997) for another banquet, naming the soup a "pan-Romanian cooperative" and associating the beef fillet with the Dacian-Roman descent. The desire for national unity was symbolised by a side dish of Transylvanian potatoes, expressing the hope for the three regions to be united peacefully, as reflected in the "diplomatic peas". The chicken dish, titled "The Triumph of Plevna", featured Bukovina snipes on "emancipated polenta" signifying the unification of Bukovina with Romania, which eventually took place in 1918. This menu highlighted geographical representativity and unity, transcending political borders.

The 1891 Democratic-Radical Party banquet at the Traian Hotel in Iași featured a tradition of crafting menus with humorous political innuendos. Even in the face of a snow blizzard hindering attendance, the event was a

success, with “succulent and copious” food. The journalist dispatched by *Lupta* newspaper to cover it explains that:

every cutlery set had a list of dishes, written as in previous years, with foods and drinks metamorphosed into epithets bearing political innuendos *du jour*; this habit of writing the menu in a humorous, ironic way is traditional and will remain traditional at all our parties, the wit and intelligent joke shall not be eliminated ever from the bosom of the radical party (no page number)

The witty menu showcased dishes like “aperitif lymph Koch style” (honouring the German microbiologist), charcuterie linked to cultural league Junimea, and pastries representing “old decrepit men from the Senate”. Opposition figures were humorously referenced in a rabbit dish with a “governmental mushroom sauce” while the “ministerial arrogance” appeared as turkey stuffing. The menu concluded with restored cake *à la Lecomte*, recalling a French architect invited by King Charles I to recondition monuments in Romania. Drinks included “irredentist champagne”, vintage wines, and “Triple Alliance liquors”. Another notable menu, from 1921, honouring Prof. Julien Suchaire, featured champagne *du la Victoire* and “vins crus Verdun-Mărășești”, evoking memories of recent WWI battles. A similar trend was observed in the menus of the Indian Independence Night in 1947 and its 2017 follow-up, with dishes named *à l’Indienne*, *Délices à l’Hindustan*, *Poulard Soufflé Independence*, and *Vacherin de Pêches Liberation* (Franklin and Johnson, 2019: 83).

In 1893, Alexandru Roman, a Romanian professor working in Hungary, marked his 30th teaching anniversary with a banquet. Serving as a Romanian professor at the Budapest University, a founder of the Romanian Literary Society (later the Romanian Academy), and a deputy in the Budapest Parliament from 1865 to 1888, Roman faced political persecution for advocating Romanian rights in Transylvania under the Austro-Hungarian dual leadership. *Tribuna Sibiului* dispatched a reporter to document the banquet, revealing a Romanian national sentiment despite the customary toast to “our glorious monarch Franz Josef I.” Comparatively, the 1920 Hampstead Communist Party First Annual Party menu in Great Britain omitted a toast to the King, instead quoting Lord Byron with “the Toscin of the Soul, the Dinner Bell” (Franklin and Johnson, 2019: 76, typo in original). Anti-monarchy sentiments can be found in a Dublin banquet exhibiting Irish nationalist sentiments, evident in menu items like *mort à la reine*, Irish stew, “deviled anything”, “hearty chokes”, “dynamite” and “bitter beer”, reflecting discontent with Queen Victoria (*Dublin Daily Express*, 1883). Returning to the Romanian banquet in Hungary, *Tribuna Sibiului* reported guests being greeted with “Wake up, Romanian”, the Romanian national anthem dubbed by the newspaper “our strong Marseillaise”; a jubilee album and portrait were presented to the professor, with congratulations and speeches. The journalist admits to taking the liberty

to write down the menu to satisfy “the curiosity of the gentile female readers”, usually not invited to this type of function. The menu itself lacked ironic or political references, resembling a classic French end-of-century dinner, but two Hungarian words caught the eye, *Magyarádi* and *Sashegyi*, later in-depth research revealing that they refer to wine made of the regional *cadarcă* grape variety.

In 1896, a Moldavian newspaper celebrated its fourth year with a banquet exemplifying satirical journalism. Featuring twelve dishes and five drinks, the menu cleverly referenced prominent figures, associating soft roe fish salad with Lascăr Catargiu, aged President of the Conservative Party and former War ministry. The *consommé*, served with “gugoase din Program” (i.e. “lies” in Romanian), humorously alluded to political deceit. The turkey steak represented “arrogant Lahovary”, another Conservative politician, while “liberal elections” influenced the fine peas dish. The ice cream was “frozen like Junimea’s hopes” and the global occult was associated with the *timbale à la financière*. Desserts featured universally “dried fruits in all political parties”, while the 1848 vintage wine symbolised the revered revolutionary generation. Noteworthy was the mention of chef “*mâitre* Irimia Spiridon” along with the musicians that provided entertainment (*Evenimentul*, 1896).

The focal point of this investigation is a menu from a banquet hosted by I. Paul in celebration of his appointment as a professor at the University of Cluj-Napoca in 1919, a significant year marked by recent political events. Published in *Evenimentul*, the menu commences with Clemenceau brandy, named after the French politician associated with Hungary’s territorial concessions, including the cession of Transylvania to Romania. The longstanding Romanian-Hungarian feud over Transylvania culminated in its unification with Romania on December 1, 1918. Paraphrasing Jane Austen, it is a truth universally acknowledged that *țuică* or brandy goes well with olives, so the menu proceeds with “olives from the peace olive branch.” The subsequent culinary offerings like ham, demi-lune radishes, etc. symbolise historical events, such as Bela Kuhn’s Bolshevik regime in Hungary and his troops entering Romania, the Romanian army’s short and decisive intervention, and the partial ceding of Banat to Romania after the end of the World War I. Noteworthy items include “clean Romanian language beef tongue, undeformed by Hungarian”, lion cubs with Bulgarian vegetables (a linguistic pun), and “Tisza tiger on a spit.” The dessert is associated with a poem written by patriot poet George Cosbuc while the “freedom fruits” represent Woodrow Wilson’s influence in transferring Transylvania from Hungary to Romania. Beverages include “requisition wine *à la Tokay*” and Enver bey Turkish coffee, referencing Enver Paşa’s role in the Ottoman Empire and its alliance with Germany. The menu concludes with a postscript verse urging the consumption of food and drink while being oblivious to the surroundings, with a request to

write from Kolozswar (Cluj-Napoca), underscoring the anti-Hungarian sentiment and the menu's manifestation of intense nationalism.

Castigat ridendo mores

The organisation of social gatherings, particularly during the late 19th and early 20th centuries Romania, provided an avenue for members of the middle class to articulate their concerns and viewpoints. The banquet menus from these events acted as entertainment or served as instruments for conveying messages, transcending their culinary function to encapsulate beliefs, attitudes, opinions, and societal reactions. Crafted in Romanian or frequently in mistake-ridden French, part of them served as conduits for political opinions, declarations of friendship or enmity, and expressions of pride or despair.

Tailored for specific audiences, the publication of these menus in newspapers acknowledges their intentional public nature, reflecting a society that valued freedom of speech. The menus with explicit political statements exhibit a discernible discursive character, treating food as intellectual nourishment before being consumed physically. These menus conceal political and cultural motifs in plain sight, demonstrating how food can serve as a transformative medium, revealing social dynamics and metaphorically representing notions of nationhood and identity.

As personal events, the coverage of banquets in newspapers offers glimpses into the intersection of private and public life. The menus reference contemporaneous events, public figures, organisations, and noteworthy news relevant to the hosts and guests. While some menus comprise light-hearted *mots d'esprit* easily forgotten, others employ sarcasm to convey their messages. A subset of these menus serves as historical documents, shedding light on events often overlooked by mainstream historical accounts. By examining the semiotics of these banquets, researchers gain insights into forgotten personalities, their lives, and their societal impact. These menus provide a voice to individuals, act as memory support and as a form of restitution. It is evident that these witty menus, even after more than a century, are not static representations but rather living *tableaux*. They remain fresh and engaging, illustrating that food transcends mere sustenance and encompasses a broader cultural significance.

Notes

[1] All quotations from Romanian are translated by the author unless stated otherwise.

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The Flavour of *Poor Things* (2023)

Alin TEMELIESCU*

Abstract

Poor Things has achieved remarkable success, surpassing \$100 million globally and becoming Yorgos Lanthimos's highest-grossing film. This accomplishment highlights the film's broad appeal and its ability to engage audiences with its unique blend of dark comedy, magical realism, and rich thematic content. The present paper aims to analyse *Poor Things* (2023), adapted from Alasdair Gray's 1992 novel and reinterpreting Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* for a modern audience. The film follows the journey of Bella Baxter, a resurrected woman navigating a surreal, gothic version of Victorian London, as she evolves and grapples with questions of identity, morality, and empathy. This paper seeks to uncover a potentially overlooked thematic dimension in the film – its subtle engagement with veganism. By examining the narrative and thematic elements, the paper reveals how *Poor Things* subtly aligns with vegan principles, particularly in Bella's growing empathy toward animals and her rejection of meat. While veganism is not explicitly emphasised, it emerges as a significant undercurrent, deepening the film's exploration of ethics and the interconnectedness of all living beings. Through this lens, the paper positions *Poor Things* as a multifaceted cinematic work that not only reinterprets classic literature but also engages with contemporary ethical issues, showcasing Lanthimos's ability to provoke thoughtful reflection through cinema.

Keywords: *reading food, veganism, weird, Victorian fiction, multifaceted cinema*

From Mary Shelley to Yorgos Lanthimos

Yorgos Lanthimos's *Poor Things* (2023) is a cinematic odyssey that navigates the tumultuous waters of creation, identity, and ethical responsibility. Drawing inspiration from Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* and Alasdair Gray's 1992 novel, the film reimagines the tale of resurrection, not merely as a return to life, but as an awakening to the moral complexities of existence. Set in a mesmerising, gothic version of Victorian London, *Poor Things* presents the story of Bella Baxter – a creature reborn into a fascinating and cruel world.

While *Poor Things* serves as a reimagination of Shelley's novel, it deviates from traditional interpretations by depicting Bella as an attractive young woman rather than a monstrous creature. This portrayal introduces a unique twist to Bella's character, which gradually unfolds as the narrative progresses. The film explores Bella's transformation from a passive being, brought back to

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life by the eccentric Dr Godwin Baxter, into an assertive and self-aware individual who begins to challenge the societal norms imposed upon her.

Beneath this reimagined surface lies a deeper connection to the original text, particularly in its subtle engagement with ethical questions – a connection that becomes more apparent when considering Mary Shelley’s ethical stance.

Shelley’s vegetarianism, as evidenced in her portrayal of the creature’s refusal to consume meat, adds a subtle yet significant layer to the thematic discourse of the film. In *Frankenstein*, the creature explicitly states: “My food is not that of man. I do not destroy the lamb and the kid to glut my appetite; acorns and berries afford me sufficient nourishment.” (Shelley 1831: 120) This ethical choice reflects a broader commentary on the moral responsibilities of creation and existence – a theme that *Poor Things* explores through Bella’s evolving empathy and ethical awareness. This aspect of the *Frankenstein* novel, as highlighted by vegan scholar Carol J. Adams in *The Sexual Politics of Meat*, remains underexplored despite the extensive critical attention the work has received. Adams notes the remarkable oversight in critical discourse regarding the creature’s vegetarianism, which subtly underscores a broader ethical narrative within Shelley’s work (1990: 108).

Lanthimos’s film, with its dark humour and surreal landscapes, invites audiences to contemplate the boundaries of humanity and the nature of empathy. Yet, beneath its vivid narrative and striking visuals lies a deeper current – one that questions the ethical fabric of our interactions with all living beings. In a world where beings are often commodified, where the distinction between human and animal blurs, *Poor Things* challenges us to reconsider our place in the web of life.

Understanding vegetarianism and veganism

This foundational connection between Shelley’s ethical stance and the narrative of *Poor Things* invites a deeper exploration of how the film aligns with themes of veganism and ethical living. In order to discuss the significance of this message, it is necessary to briefly consider the ethical frameworks that underpin it – namely, vegetarianism and veganism. These concepts transcend dietary choices, encompassing broader philosophical and ethical considerations that are important to understanding the film’s subtle yet powerful commentary. Vegetarianism and veganism both stem from ethical concerns about animal treatment, but they differ in their extent and intensity. Vegetarianism typically involves avoiding meat while still consuming other animal products like dairy and eggs. In contrast, veganism goes further by rejecting all forms of animal exploitation, including the use of animal products in food, clothing, and other areas of life.

In *The Edinburgh Companion to Vegan Literary Studies* (2022), edited by Laura Wright and Emelia Quinn, veganism is portrayed not simply as a diet

but as an all-encompassing ethical stance. Wright and Quinn argue that, “veganism does operate for many as a way of thinking about and engaging with the world, one that is experienced as a deeply felt and embodied response to suffering” (2022: 1).

Similarly, *The Routledge Handbook of Vegan Studies*, also edited by Laura Wright, explores the complex dimensions of veganism, examining its connections with critical race studies, feminist theory, and environmental activism. Wright emphasises that veganism should be understood not just as a personal lifestyle choice, but as a political and ethical position that challenges systemic injustices, whether they affect animals, marginalised human communities, or the environment (2021: 4). This holistic perspective is essential for analysing how veganism subtly appears in cultural texts, including cinema.

The editors of both volumes are committed to expanding the understanding of veganism beyond its dietary dimensions. Wright and Quinn, in the introduction to *The Edinburgh Companion to Vegan Literary Studies*, articulate their vision of veganism as an interdisciplinary and intersectional field of study that intersects with ecofeminism, posthumanism, and literary theory. They argue that by exploring veganism in literature, scholars can uncover “the multiple contradictions and failings embedded in the enactment of a vegan life”, while also offering new perspectives on human and non-human relationships (2022: 2). In *The Routledge Handbook of Vegan Studies*, Laura Wright similarly emphasises the need to understand veganism as a critical framework that addresses broader ethical concerns. She highlights how veganism can serve as a lens to interrogate power dynamics, challenge entrenched social hierarchies and promote a more just and sustainable world. The choice to focus on veganism in these scholarly works reflects a broader cultural and academic shift towards recognizing the importance of ethical living and its representation in various media (2021: 6).

The theoretical perspectives offered by these collections of articles provide a vital context for understanding the ethical dimensions of *Poor Things*. The film’s portrayal of Bella Baxter’s evolving empathy towards animals and her rejection of meat can be seen as a reflection of the broader vegan principles articulated by Wright, Quinn, and other contributors to these volumes. Bella’s journey is not just a personal transformation, but an ethical awakening that aligns with the comprehensive view of veganism as an engagement with the world that challenges existing norms and advocates for a more compassionate and just society.

From Gray’s Glasgow to Lanthimos’s vision

The narrative of *Poor Things* is rooted in Alasdair Gray’s 1992 novel of the same name, which serves as the foundation for the film’s storyline. Gray’s novel, largely set in Glasgow, provides a deliberate social commentary on the city. In

contrast, Lanthimos's adaptation deliberately omits specific Scottish references, a choice that carries implications beyond geographical context, affecting the film's thematic emphasis, audience appeal, and artistic interpretation.

One significant implication of omitting Scottish references is the broadening of the film's appeal to a wider, more global audience. By removing the specific cultural and geographical context of Glasgow, Lanthimos transforms the story into a more universal narrative that can resonate with viewers from diverse backgrounds. This approach enables the film to explore themes of identity, ethical boundaries, and societal norms without being tethered to a particular location, thereby making the narrative more accessible internationally. As film scholar Andrew Higson observes, "Transnational cinema often seeks to avoid specific cultural markers that might limit a film's international appeal, opting instead for a more universal approach to storytelling." (2006: 19)

Moreover, the absence of Scottish references shifts the focus from the socio-political commentary on Glasgow to a more abstract and fantastical exploration of the human condition. Gray's original novel used the setting of Glasgow to critique the social and political landscape of the time, embedding the story within a specific cultural context. In contrast, Lanthimos's film, by eschewing these references, opts for a more stylised and surreal representation of Victorian London. This shift enables the film to delve deeper into the fantastical elements of the story, enhancing its Gothic atmosphere and emphasizing the universal aspects of Bella Baxter's journey.

Lanthimos's approach was deeply influenced by his interaction with Alasdair Gray. As noted in an interview, Lanthimos met Gray shortly after acquiring the rights to adapt the novel and discussed his vision for the film. Although Gray passed away before the film's completion, Lanthimos has mentioned that their meeting gave him a better understanding of Gray's intentions and the thematic depth of the novel. This interaction allowed Lanthimos to preserve the novel's essence while bringing his unique vision to the screen, blending Gray's narrative with his distinct cinematic style (Welsh, 2024).

The omission of Scottish references also underscores Lanthimos's artistic vision, which prioritises a stylised and otherworldly depiction of the story over a culturally specific one. By doing so, the film aligns itself with the broader tradition of Gothic literature and cinema, where settings often serve as symbolic backdrops rather than realistic depictions of specific places. This choice reinforces the film's exploration of universal themes such as the boundaries between life and death, the nature of monstrosity, and the search for identity.

Yorgos Lanthimos's directorial style

Yorgos Lanthimos is renowned for his distinct directorial style, characterised by unconventional narratives, surrealism, dark humour, and a keen exploration of human behaviour and societal norms. His films often delve into themes of power, control, and the absurdity of social constructs, creating thought-provoking and visually striking cinematic experiences. Lanthimos's previous films, including *Dogtooth* (2009), *The Lobster* (2015), and *The Favourite* (2018), serve as critical touchstones in understanding his approach in *Poor Things*, particularly regarding the portrayal of food and consumption and their broader narrative significance. What follows is a brief introduction to each of these films with a focus on the representations of food.

1. *Dogtooth* (2009): Lanthimos's breakthrough film, *Dogtooth*, which won the Prix Un Certain Regard at the Cannes Film Festival, explores the extreme measures taken by parents to isolate their children from the outside world. Food plays a symbolic role, often used as a tool of control and manipulation within the isolated family. The parents dictate the children's access to food, reflecting the broader theme of control and the perversion of natural instincts. Here, food embodies power dynamics and the absurdity of the controlled environment, underscoring the artificiality of the family's isolated existence.
2. *The Lobster* (2015): This film presents a dystopian society where single people are transformed into animals if they fail to find a partner within a specific timeframe. *The Lobster* blends dark comedy with a critical examination of societal expectations around relationships, with food again serving as a crucial thematic element. The rigid rules around dining in the hotel where singles stay highlight the oppressive and dehumanising nature of society. The absurdity of these rituals, including the preparation and consumption of food, mirrors the broader absurdity of the social constructs entrapping the characters.
3. *The Favourite* (2018): Set in the court of Queen Anne, *The Favourite* explores themes of power, jealousy, and manipulation through a darkly comedic love triangle. Food is depicted grotesquely and excessively, symbolising the decadence and moral decay of the ruling class. The lavish feasts and indulgent consumption contrast with Queen Anne's physical ailments, emphasising the excesses of the elite. Food becomes a symbol of power and the corruption it engenders, with scenes of overeating and vomiting highlighting the grotesque realities of unchecked indulgence.

In *Poor Things*, Lanthimos continues his exploration of complex characters and societal norms through Bella Baxter. However, this film marks a significant departure in his portrayal of food. While Lanthimos's earlier films use food to

underscore themes of control, absurdity, and excess, *Poor Things* introduces a more nuanced and ethically charged portrayal. Here, food becomes a vehicle for exploring ethical boundaries and identity, particularly through Bella's evolving relationship with consumption. Unlike the grotesque or absurd representations in his earlier films, Lanthimos uses Bella's refusal to eat meat and her preference for plant-based foods to subtly introduce themes of veganism and ethical living. This shift aligns with the film's broader themes of resurrection and self-discovery, as Bella's dietary choices reflect her growing empathy and ethical awareness. The film's focus on Bella's rejection of meat serves as a quiet yet significant departure from Lanthimos's previous works, marking *Poor Things* as a film that not only questions societal norms but also engages with deeper philosophical considerations.

Grand appetites

Poor Things has clear ties to the traditional Gothic novel, but the film also draws inspiration from the historical figure of Dr Anna Kingsford, a prominent Victorian-era antivivisectionist, feminist, and mystic. The character of Bella Baxter embodies many of the ethical and philosophical stances associated with Kingsford, suggesting a deeper connection between the film's narrative and Kingsford's pioneering activism.

Dr Anna Kingsford was a pioneering advocate for animal rights and a staunch opponent of vivisection, paralleling the creature in Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein*. Kingsford was also a committed vegetarian, believing that a plant-based diet was essential for fostering compassion toward animals and improving human health. In her influential work, *The Perfect Way in Diet* (1881), Kingsford argued for a return to what she considered humanity's natural diet, free from the cruelty of animal exploitation. Her activism and writings challenged the scientific and social conventions of her time, advocating for a new ethical paradigm that recognized the interconnectedness of all living beings (Coulthard 2022: 325-326). As noted in *The Edinburgh Companion to Vegan Literary Studies*, "Before the twentieth-century term 'veganism' appeared, some proponents of vegetarianism argued that dietary change did not complete the reform required to achieve the 'perfect way'" (Gregory, 2022: 319). Kingsford's contributions significantly shaped the early ethical frameworks of vegetarianism and veganism.

In *Poor Things*, Bella's actions and ethical choices echo Kingsford's philosophy. Like Kingsford, Bella rejects meat and demonstrates profound empathy for animals, particularly those disfigured by bizarre vivisection experiments. Her evolution from a passive creation to an assertive advocate for the oppressed mirrors Kingsford's journey as a woman who defied societal norms to champion the rights of both humans and nonhumans. Bella's

declaration in the film's final act— "I was created to break the rules"— resonates with Kingsford's defiance of the rigid structures of Victorian society.

Other characters and plot elements in *Poor Things* also engage with these themes. Dr Godwin Baxter's role as Bella's creator mirrors the scientific hubris Kingsford critiqued, while his eventual recognition of Bella's autonomy subtly challenges his initial disregard for ethical concerns. The subplot involving vivisection directly echoes Kingsford's opposition to animal cruelty, with Bella's empathy for the disfigured creatures reinforcing her alignment with Kingsford's advocacy for compassion. In contrast, characters like Archie represent the societal norms that Bella—and, by extension, Kingsford—defies. His patriarchal attitudes challenge Bella's ethical awakening, highlighting the resistance to Kingsford's ideals in her time. Additionally, the broader society depicted in the film reflects Victorian-era practices of commodification and exploitation, further challenging the ethical frameworks Kingsford championed.

While it is possible that the production team was not explicitly aware of Dr Kingsford, the parallels between Bella Baxter and Kingsford are striking. These parallels likely arise from the cultural and historical context. The Victorian influence on modern ethical debates, the Gothic tradition's focus on societal critique, and the revival of interest in figures like Kingsford contribute to the natural alignment between Bella's character and Kingsford's ideals. This connection enriches our understanding of Bella's character, and the ethical themes embedded in *Poor Things*, suggesting that the film's narrative resonates with the pioneering spirit and ethical commitments of figures like Dr Anna Kingsford.

The multifaceted meaning of *Poor Things*

The title *Poor Things* initially may not seem immediately clear, but the novel on which the film is based provides insight. Like Bram Stoker's *Dracula* and other Gothic novels of its time, Alasdair Gray's novel employs a frame narrative, presenting itself as a "found document" that the author is merely editing, suggesting the entire story is true. Within this narrative, the "editor" remarks:

I have also insisted on renaming the whole book POOR THINGS. Things are often mentioned in the story and every single character (apart from Mrs Dinwiddie and two of the General's parasites) is called poor or calls themselves that sometime or other. (1992: xi)

Chris Lambert, in his review "Poor Things Explained", offers the following interpretation of the title:

I think the title ultimately gets at this notion that we are all our poor things facing the overwhelming struggle to live well. The experience can break us. But some

continue to seize whatever hope is within reach. Either way, the title evokes a sense of empathy for humanity as a whole. (2023 online)

The implications of the title extend beyond the characters, encompassing empathy for all sentient beings, which aligns with vegan and anti-speciesist principles. The phrase “poor things” can be interpreted as “poor beings,” referring to not just the animals experimented on in the film, but also the various tormented characters Bella encounters, the impoverished individuals she tries to assist, and Bella herself, whose artificial nature raises questions about whether she is a being or a thing. The film suggests that there is no significant distinction between humans and other animals, aligning with the core axiom of anti-speciesism, where all beings are treated as things.

At the beginning of the film, Bella is more a thing than a human being, her brain replaced by that of a newborn. Brought back to life by Dr. Godwin Baxter, Bella starts as a being with little sense of self but vast intellectual potential. Her journey begins when Duncan Wedderburn (Mark Ruffalo), a lawyer intending to exploit her, takes her on a journey through Lisbon, Alexandria, and Paris. Along the way, Bella faces numerous challenges that help her develop a strong sense of self. Her experiences with the poor and marginalised, particularly those subjected to vivisection, lead her to unlearn societal conditioning and foster an ethical framework centred on care—much like the visions of Mary Shelley, Dr Anna Kingsford, and Carol J. Adams.

Bella’s transformation from an object to an empathetic, self-aware being directly reflects the film’s title. *Poor Things* encapsulates the film’s exploration of empathy and ethical living, extending compassion not just to humans but to all sentient beings. In this way, the title is a powerful symbol of the film’s overarching message, challenging the viewer to reconsider the boundaries between beings and things, human and animal.

The broader cultural and cinematic impact

Poor Things can be seen as a contemporary reinterpretation of classic Gothic literature, bringing new relevance to themes of creation, identity, and ethical responsibility. By positioning Bella Baxter’s story in a fantastical Victorian London, Lanthimos invites viewers to reflect on contemporary issues through the lens of a period setting. This approach highlights timeless ethical dilemmas while drawing parallels between historical and current societal issues, resonating with modern audiences.

The film’s unique blend of genres and rich visual style significantly contribute to its broader cinematic impact. *Poor Things* masterfully combines elements of Gothic fiction, dark comedy, and magical realism, creating a genre-bending narrative that challenges traditional cinematic boundaries. The Gothic elements are evident in the exploration of resurrection, monstrosity, and human identity, echoing the eerie atmosphere of classic Gothic literature.

Simultaneously, Lanthimos infuses the narrative with dark humour, using absurdity and satire to critique societal norms and human behaviour, much in the tradition of black comedies.

Magical realism plays a crucial role in grounding the fantastical elements within a believable, albeit surreal, world. By blending the real with the fantastical, Lanthimos explores profound ethical and philosophical questions without losing the audience in fantasy. This genre-blending enriches the narrative complexity of *Poor Things* and positions it within a broader cultural discourse, challenging viewers to reconsider the boundaries of genre in contemporary cinema.

The film's striking visual style amplifies its impact. Lanthimos's use of a fish-eye lens and hyper-stylized cinematography creates a distinctive aesthetic that sets *Poor Things* apart from conventional period dramas. The exaggerated and sometimes disorienting visuals contribute to the film's surreal atmosphere, reinforcing themes of distorted identity and reality. Thomas Elsaesser (2005) notes that "the blending of genres and the disruption of classical narrative forms are characteristic of a cinema that seeks to engage the viewer on multiple levels, both intellectually and emotionally" (506). Lanthimos's visual strategy exemplifies this approach, inviting viewers to question their perceptions of reality and the nature of the cinematic experience.

Moreover, the film's success could pave the way for more experimental and genre-blending films in mainstream cinema. By challenging the conventions of genre and narrative structure, *Poor Things* encourages directors to take creative risks and explore unconventional storytelling methods. This opens the door for a more diverse range of films that push the boundaries of traditional cinema, potentially leading to a richer and more varied cinematic landscape. In this way, *Poor Things* not only reinterprets Gothic literature but also contributes to the evolution of contemporary cinema, encouraging a rethinking of what modern films can achieve both aesthetically and thematically.

Subtle vegan narratives in cinema and the unique approach of *Poor Things*

Veganism has been portrayed in various ways in cinema, often reflecting contemporary attitudes towards animal rights and ethical consumption. Early portrayals were rare and somewhat peripheral, but in recent years, there has been a growing interest in exploring vegan themes more directly. Three notable films stand out for their impactful depiction of veganism and animal rights:

1. *Earthlings* (2005): Narrated by Joaquin Phoenix, this documentary is a powerful exposé of animal exploitation across various industries. Using explicit, graphic imagery, it confronts viewers with the realities of animal cruelty, adopting a direct and confrontational style to convey its message.

2. *Okja* (2017): Directed by Bong Joon-ho, *Okja* tells the story of a young girl and her genetically modified super-pig, combining adventure with social satire to critique the meat industry. The film embeds its vegan message within a narrative that blends fantastical elements with sharp social commentary, making it accessible to a wide audience.
3. *Cowspiracy* (2014): This documentary explores the environmental impact of animal agriculture and advocates for a plant-based diet to combat climate change. Like *Earthlings*, it uses a documentary format to present its argument, focusing on the global environmental consequences of meat consumption.

Poor Things enriches cinematic portrayals of veganism by subtly embedding vegan themes within a narrative that is not explicitly about veganism. Unlike the direct approach of *Earthlings* or *Cowspiracy*, *Poor Things* uses cinematic techniques based on the show-don't-tell approach to convey its ethical message. This subtlety allows the film to reach a larger audience, encouraging viewers to reflect on ethical issues without feeling overtly preached.

Bella Baxter's growing empathy for animals and her rejection of meat reflect key vegan principles, similar to the characters in *Okja*. However, where *Okja* uses a clear narrative to critique the meat industry, *Poor Things* weaves its vegan themes into a rich tapestry of other issues, such as identity, resurrection, and societal norms. This multifaceted approach allows the film to explore veganism within a slightly different ethical context, challenging viewers to consider the interconnectedness of all living beings as part of the film's larger narrative.

While *Earthlings* and *Cowspiracy* use the documentary format to directly address the exploitation of animals and the environmental impact of animal agriculture, *Poor Things* offers a more nuanced, fictional exploration of such themes. By focusing on Bella's personal journey and her gradual ethical awakening, the film integrates veganism into its character development and thematic depth, demonstrating that ethical considerations can be woven into diverse narratives without being overtly didactic.

As Jason Mittel argues, "the most powerful cinematic stories often convey complex ideas and ethical considerations through character development and narrative subtlety, allowing viewers to arrive at their own conclusions" (2015: 322). *Poor Things* exemplifies this approach, using Bella's transformation and ethical choices to explore broader vegan principles. By doing so, the film not only fits within the cinematic tradition of vegan portrayals but also challenges and expands it, showing that subtle, character-driven narratives can be just as impactful in conveying ethical themes as more direct approaches.

Kinds of kindness

The phrase “you poor thing” is a familiar British expression of sympathy, often used to console children or loved ones. One can imagine Dr Anna Kingsford uttering it upon witnessing a dog undergoing vivisection without anaesthesia for the first time. This initial empathy can evolve into the intellectual foundation of veganism and other philosophies inspired by *ahimsa*, the Sanskrit term for “do no harm” or “non-violence,” though these often fall short of vegan principles. Bella, the protagonist, begins exploring these concepts after meeting an unconventional couple on a ship.

The film opens and closes with the title *Poor Things*, but by the end, its meaning evolves, reflecting Bella’s perspective. Initially an anarchic, rebellious figure, Bella matures into a self-assured woman ready to care for others. This transformation mirrors the journey of long-term vegans, who come to understand the complexities of human behaviour and recognise that even those deemed “bad” may be victims of a corrupt society – a recurring theme in Lanthimos’s films.

The portrayal of other characters further explores these themes of kindness and empathy. Dr Godwin Baxter, the seemingly mad scientist, is revealed to be a victim of his father’s cruel experiments, marked by numerous scars. Duncan Wedderburn, the flamboyant lawyer who attempts to corrupt Bella, is portrayed as a desperate man overwhelmed by his emotions, similar to the weasel in *Pinocchio*. Max McCandles, Dr Baxter’s assistant, helplessly falls in love with Bella, becoming a pawn in uncontrollable plot twists. Even the most despicable character, General Alfie Blessington, is ultimately shown as pathetically weak, becoming a “poor thing” himself. These characters, though flawed, are portrayed with a certain empathy, suggesting that their actions are shaped by the oppressive societal structures they inhabit.

Emma Stone’s description of Bella required a skilled ensemble, which Lanthimos achieved through excellent casting, team-building rehearsals, and expert direction. The performances, even in minor roles like Hanna Schygulla’s sublime Martha Von Kurtzrock, enhance the film’s exploration of empathy and transformation. Stone’s performance, supported by this ensemble, underscores Bella’s journey from a “poor thing” to a liberated, compassionate individual.

Just as veganism offers humanity a second chance to prove its worthiness on this planet, Bella receives a second chance at life, free from the societal conditioning of her past. She refuses to be crushed again by the oppressive patriarchal society into which she was first born. Instead, she liberates herself and begins to help others who remain trapped, embodying the essence of a true vegan. *Poor Things* thus uses its characters and narrative to explore different “kinds of kindness,” showing how empathy can lead to transformation and ethical awakening.

A fantastical discovery of mind, body and world

Poor Things exemplifies Yorgos Lanthimos's distinctive ability to intertwine dark comedy, magical realism, and gothic elements into a narrative that challenges viewers to engage with profound ethical questions. The film's exploration of creation, identity, and moral responsibility is not only a reimagining of Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* but also an intricate commentary on the ethical complexities of existence.

Central to this analysis is the subtle engagement with veganism, emerging through Bella Baxter's evolving empathy and rejection of meat. By weaving this ethical dimension into the narrative, Lanthimos extends the film's relevance beyond its gothic and surreal elements, positioning it as a critique of human-animal relationships and the broader societal implications of empathy and ethical living.

Bella's transformation from a passive creation to a self-assured advocate for the oppressed mirrors broader societal movements toward compassion, justice, and the questioning of entrenched norms. Her journey embodies the film's overall message that true ethical living requires a deep empathy for all beings, challenging viewers to consider their responsibilities within society. Lanthimos's nuanced portrayal of these themes ensures that *Poor Things* resonates as both a work of art and a commentary on contemporary ethical issues.

Ultimately, *Poor Things* exemplifies cinema's power to entertain, provoke reflection, and inspire discussion. Lanthimos's ability to evoke thoughtful reflection through his unique directorial style solidifies *Poor Things* as a significant and enduring work in contemporary cinema. Its engagement with ethical issues, particularly veganism, enhances its relevance and importance, positioning it as a film that not only reimagines classic narratives but also challenges modern audiences to reconsider the ethical frameworks of their own lives. This ethical depth, combined with its artistic innovation and cultural relevance, will ensure that *Poor Things* continues to be analysed and appreciated for years to come.

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PART II

Translating Food

Activating Sensory Modalities: Translating (or not) Texture and Taste of Bosnian-Herzegovinian Traditional Drinks

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Abstract

The present paper illustrates and discusses decisions made by the translator when rendering the texture and the taste of Bosnian-Herzegovinian traditional drinks into English, as described in The Bosnian Cuisine (2016), which, apart from collected recipes, contains excerpts from travelogues and literary works. In the paper, I refer to the adjective and the noun phrase equivalence or the lack of equivalence thereof in the English language, whereas special attention is given to using footnotes and brackets in translation, as well as to the negotiation process between the translator and the proofreader whose L1 is English. Based on corpus analysis, it can be concluded that the majority of decisions made regarding the nouns denoting traditional dishes were made to preserve the original names and to resort to footnotes and/or bracketing in order to render the reading experience and sensory modalities more accessible to readers, bearing in mind that they may not have tasted or seen the drinks mentioned, but also taking into consideration the wider socio-cultural context.

Keywords: *texture, taste, sensory modalities, translation, Bosnian cuisine*

Introduction

This paper aims to highlight the importance and/or possibility of activating sensory modalities (see Sanchez et al, 2020) in reading texts for translation and vice versa as well as to provide researchers and scholars with new perspectives on decoding texture from text (by reading experience only or due to relying on oral tradition) in similar corpora in different languages. As for the topic of the paper, the research motivation arises from the fact that the register of Bosnian-Herzegovinian menus is very complex and may represent a difficulty for the translator due to a large number of loanwords, hybrid structures, names of dishes and drinks that already include certain ingredients, which may lead to redundancy in the translation, as well as names of dishes and traditional drinks in which the adjective comes after the noun. Another complicating factor is certainly the heterogeneity of the Bosnian-Herzegovinian market in terms of dish names. Namely, in different cities of Bosnia and Herzegovina, we find different names for the same traditional dishes and drinks. For this reason, the research corpus includes a part of the book titled *The Bosnian Cuisine* translated

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into English in 2016. The analysis of the corpus chronologically follows my MA research, mentioned in the theoretical framework below, which refers to the classification of translatability of dish names. The reason why the decisions on the transmission of the message matter is not relevant only from a linguistic and translation point of view, but also due to the importance regarding the transmission of valuable texts through generations and among those who live abroad as “food practices help create a sense of diasporic identity” (Razia 2016: 47). Furthermore, this paper is a self-reflection on the methodology used in my MA thesis (Kalajdžisalihović 2010). The classification of the translation possibilities included in my MA thesis was made starting from frequent names for traditional dishes in Bosnia and Herzegovina, whereas little attention was given to traditional drinks. The traditional drinks mentioned in *The Bosnian Cuisine* (2016) are culturally and semantically relevant as they are part of a terminological constellation which includes the containers used to keep and serve the drinks, as well as the occasions on which they are served.

The first part of the paper presents the theoretical framework focused on the translatability of noun phrases denoting traditional dishes in Bosnia and Herzegovina, frequently seen on menus. In the second part, the focus is on names of less-known traditional drinks mentioned in *The Bosnian Cuisine* (2016) and on examples of cultural and literary contexts in which they occur. Finally, this brief analysis of the translation decisions aims to find similarities and differences in terms of the classification and the frequency of the nouns denoting traditional drinks.

Theoretical framework

In this paper, I will use my classification of the translatability of noun phrases denoting traditional dishes in Bosnia and Herzegovina starting from the analysis of restaurant menus available at the time my MA research was conducted (Kalajdžisalihović 2010). The classification of the translatability that will be mentioned in this paper consists of four groups: Type 1 – *untranslatable*: Bosnian noun phrases that retain the same form in their English equivalents; Type 2 – *acceptable translatability*: complex Bosnian noun phrases that can be translated into English; Type 3 – complex noun phrases that are *partially translated* into English; and Type 4 – complex noun phrases whose translation is *culturally conditioned*. Each type will be illustrated and discussed below.

Type 1 – untranslatable: Bosnian noun phrases that retain the same form in their English equivalents: The Type 1 nouns may be divided into two subgroups: (1a) and (1b). Subgroup (1a) has a simple structure. It consists of one head noun, in singular or plural, which is not translated because the name of the dish is either characteristic of the area of Bosnia and Herzegovina or is already well-known around the world, for example: *hurmašica* (sg.) and *tiriti* (pl.). Bosnian noun phrases in Subgroup (1b) consist of an adjective or noun

premodifier and a proper noun in singular or plural. Their relationship is the relationship between the head noun and the noun or adjectival premodifier, which, being an obligatory constituent of the phrase, operates as a functional argument of the head noun. The names of these dishes are characteristic of the Bosnia and Herzegovina area, and foreigners who stay longer in the country are well acquainted with their composition and taste (e.g. *kadun butići, sarajevski sahan*).

Type 2 – acceptable translatability: Bosnian noun phrases that are and can be translated into English: Type 2 includes nouns that may be divided into eight subgroups: (2a), (2b), (2c), (2d), (2e), (2f), (2g), (2h). Like the first subgroup of Type 1, the first subgroup (2a) has a simple structure. Both the Bosnian noun phrases and their English equivalents in this subgroup consist of one singular or plural head noun and are fully translated into English (e.g. sg. *paradajz, riba, salata, sataraš, supa, kompot* / cf. *tomato, fish, salad, stew, soup, compote*). Subgroup (2b) includes Bosnian noun phrases (compounds) whose combination and order of constituents are fully reflected in their English translation equivalents. In both Bosnian and English noun phrases of this subgroup, the constituents are organised according to the scheme N2+N1, where N2 is the modifier and N1 is the head noun. At first glance and according to the structure N2+N1, phrases of this subgroup may resemble the phrases of subgroup (1b), but, unlike them, all the constituents of the Bosnian phrases in subgroup (2b) are or can be translated into English. In addition, the constituents of the English translation equivalents fully reflect the order of the constituents in the corresponding Bosnian compounds. In this subgroup, the relationship between the constituents is the relationship between the head noun and its nominal premodifier, which is an obligatory element and, therefore, has the status of a functional argument of the head noun (e.g. *paradajz supa, kupus salata, paradajz sos, krompir čorba, špinat čorba, orah kocke* / cf. *tomato soup, cabbage salad, tomato sauce, potato potage, spinach potage, walnut bars*).

In the Bosnian noun phrases of Subgroup (2c), the head noun denotes a limited amount of the ingredient (or ingredients) expressed by the noun or the following nouns. An example of such a phrase can be found in the name of the dish *plata sireva*. The noun complement (*sireva*) in the Bosnian noun phrase retains the status of a functional argument in the English translation equivalent. However, from the postnominal position, which it has in Bosnian, it moves to the position before the head noun, where it performs the function of a modifier of the head noun within the compound, and thus we get the phrase *cheese platter*. Subgroup (2d) of the noun phrase is structured so that the verbal adjective *trpni* appears as a modifier of the head noun, which agrees with the head noun in gender, number, and case (e.g. *miješana salata*). This adjective is translated as an English participle adjective with the suffix *-ed*, i.e. *mixed salad*. Subgroup (2e) contains Bosnian noun phrases consisting of an

attributive adjective, which agrees with the head noun in gender, number and case. The translation equivalent of an attributive adjective in English is most often a possessive adjective or a noun (e.g. *riblja čorba/fish potage*; *riblji paprikaš/fish stew*).

Subgroup (2f) includes Bosnian noun phrases that are more complex than the previous ones. In this case, a specific form of the descriptive adjective ending in *-ći* (*teleći file*) or the verbal adjective *trpni* (*punjeni file*) appears before the proper noun as a modifier. Two adjectives can also appear as modifiers in this type of noun phrase, for example, *kuhani* (Adj.) *teleći* (Adj.) *file*/ cf. *boiled veal fillet*. Their order cannot be changed, because the second modifier in the sequence is closely related to the head noun and represents its functional argument (**teleći kuhani file*). The English translation equivalent of this phrase is *boiled veal fillet*. As we can see, the first modifier in English is a participial adjective with the suffix *-ed*, while the second one is closely related to the head noun (**veal boiled fillet*).

Subgroup (2g) includes a large number of Bosnian names of dishes that have the same syntagmatic structure, i.e. N1 *od* N2gen, where N1 is a proper noun and N2gen is a noun in the genitive form, an integral part of the prepositional phrase with the preposition *of* (*od*). Such are the following Bosnian phrases: *mus od čokolade*, *štrudla od jabuka*, *carpaccio od sira*, *tartar od lososa*, *salata od lignji*, *supa od povrća*, *salata od paradajza*, *salata od pečenih paprika*, *čorba od luka*, *salata od tjestenine*, *salata od pilećeg mesa*, *salata od šampinjona*, *musaka od krompira*. Here, systematicity was observed in the translation into English. Namely, the prepositional phrase with the preposition *of*, which represents the mandatory complement of the head noun in the Bosnian phrase, is realised in all English translation equivalents in the form of a noun or noun phrase in the position before the head noun as its mandatory modifier. In both languages, therefore, these constituents represent functional arguments, but in Bosnian they are complements, and in English, they are modifiers in singular. Thus, the above Bosnian phrases appear in English as *chocolate mousse*, *apple strudel*, *cheese carpaccio*, *salmon tartare*, *squid salad*, *vegetable soup*, *tomato salad*, *roasted pepper salad*, *onion potage*, *pasta salad*, *chicken salad*, *champignon salad*, *potato moussaka*.

Subgroup (2h) includes Bosnian phrases in which the prepositional phrase follows the head noun as its obligatory complement (e.g. *povrće na žaru*). Unlike subgroup (2g), in which the prepositional phrase with the preposition *of* shows what the given dish consists of, in this subgroup the prepositional phrase shows how the given dish was prepared. This Bosnian prepositional phrase translates into English as a participial adjective (cf. *povrće na žaru* and *grilled vegetables*).

Type 3—complex noun phrases that are partially translated into English: The Type 3 nouns may be divided into four subgroups: (3a), (3b), (3c), (3d). Subgroup (3a) includes noun phrases in which words from oriental

languages, mainly Turkish or Arabic, appear as head nouns, which are not translated because they refer to familiar culinary expressions. Only the premodifiers of the head noun are translated, which in such phrases can be nouns or adjectives. This subgroup incorporates the following noun phrases in Bosnian and in English: *sogan dolma* (*onion dolma*), *šarena dolma* (*assorted dolma*), *jagnjeća kapama* (*lamb kapama*), *pileći pilav* (*chicken pilaf*).

Subgroup (3b) includes Bosnian noun phrases in which, unlike the previous subgroup, the head nouns are translated into English, whereas the modifiers of the head nouns that entered Bosnian from Turkish or Arabic remain unchanged. This subgroup incorporates the following noun phrases in Bosnian and in English: *kulak čorba* (*kulak potage*), *bungur čorba* (*bungur potage*), *škembe čorba* (*škembe potage*).

The Bosnian noun phrases in Subgroup (3c) are structured so that a non-predicative possessive adjective derived from a proper noun, which denotes a geographical name, appears as a modifier of the head noun, while the head noun consists of one noun in singular. An example of this type is the noun phrase *sarajevska čorba*. The Bosnian possessive adjective derived from a proper noun, which takes the position before the head noun, when translated into English returns to the noun, i.e. its underived form, and also occupies the prenominal position, i.e. *Sarajevo potage* or *Sarajevo broth*.

A special subgroup, (3d), consists of noun phrases that contain a prepositional phrase introduced by the preposition *à la*, borrowed from French. This prepositional phrase indicates the style of preparing the food, and is also used in other registers, for example, *piletina à la king* (*chicken à la king*).

Type 4—complex noun phrases whose translation is culturally conditioned: In the case of phrases belonging to this group, it is more important to point out the problem of unevenness of terminology, most often related to the cultural aspect, which greatly complicates the translation process. Thus, for example, a translator may be faced with a dilemma as to which variant to use when trying to find the best equivalent for the same type of fish or steak for which different terms are used in different countries (see Collins Dictionary, n.d.). We also find a culturally interesting phenomenon in the translation of the word *pita*. In English, there are two words for this dish: *pitta* and *pie*. However, none of them is a faithful translation equivalent for the word that refers to the traditional dish found in the menus of the wider Balkan area. Discussing Type 4 in detail, however, is beyond the scope of this paper. As a subject for further research, this category could be related to the concept of “native eaters” (Bloom, 2008) and to food writing as a genre.

In the following part of the paper, the classification presented above will be used to determine whether it may be utilised in the analysis of the selected corpus denoting names of traditional (but less-known) Bosnian-Herzegovinian drinks in order to assess which category the translator’s decisions belong to

and to draw general conclusions about the translation process and the reasons for certain decisions.

Methodology and corpus analysis

The methodology used in the corpus analysis is based on the search of the keywords “drink” and “drinks” in the text of *The Bosnian Cuisine* (2016) and the exploration of the context surrounding the keywords. Out of the 44 results, the analysis of the noun phrase(s) denoting drinks in the corpus may be analysed and classified first on the basis of the decisions made for (a) *containers of drinks*, (b) *events and processes associated with a particular drink*, as well as when it comes to the very (c) *names of traditional drinks*.

(a) Containers: The following examples are found in the corpus with reference and emphasis given to containers used to store or serve traditional drinks:

- (1) For drinks, they used ewers, big and small pitchers made of copper (*ibriks*) that were called *bochale* or, less frequently, *mastrappa*, a word of Arabic origin. (p. 26-27).
- (2) *Šerbe* used to be a very popular drink in Bosnia. It was prepared in a sherbet ewer (*šerbetni ibrik*) and served with ice. The sherbet ewer is a tall, richly engraved copper pitcher. From the sherbet ewer, sherbet was poured into decorative glasses (*maštrafa*) and served on engraved saucers (*tabak*). A special embroidered napkin, *šerbetna mahrama*, was also used when serving sherbet (p. 64).
- (3) Coffee is prepared in special jugs, i.e. coffee pots (*džezva*) or coffee ewers (*kahveni ibrik*). Coffee sets are usually made of copper, brass and are sometimes even silver-plated or silver. A *džezva* has a particular shape: its neck has to be narrower than its body. Such a shape allows the coffee grounds (*toz*) to remain at the bottom when pouring coffee into cups (p. 86).
- (4) Bosnian coffee is served in the *džezva* in which it was baked, together with small decorated handleless demitasses (*findžan*), water, sugar, Turkish delight, or other snacks. Each *findžan* comes with a nicely wrought copper cup (*zarf*) meant to hold it (p. 87).
- (5) At the event called *akšamluk*, the guests drink soft brandy from small long-necked glass bottles (*čokanj*) and eat specially prepared dishes, the *mezetluk*. Soft brandy has much less alcohol than the so-called “burned Slivovitz,” which “fills you with a nice slow but long buzz leaving your soul laden with noble and fathomless melancholy” (p. 73).

Following this analysis of the corpus with a special emphasis given to containers, it can be concluded that it is not important only to decide on the type of the noun phrase in question, but also to understand its wider socio-cultural context, which is important both for the reader and the writer of the text in terms of “activating sensory modalities” pertaining to sight (i.e. shapes), touch (i.e. temperature), taste (sweet, sour, bitter, salty) and smell. In this case, the translator and the proofreaders opted for the Type 1 – untranslatable but positioned the noun phrases after their descriptive equivalents in order not to affect the reading process. Another problem was related to providing the nouns in singular or plural where a balance was achieved to ease the reading process in the way that the original term was often preserved in singular and given in brackets, whereas the descriptive equivalents were given in plural.

(b) Events and processes: The following examples are found with reference and emphasis given to gatherings, events and processes related to serving traditional drinks:

- (6) As *sevdalinkas* are songs about love and yearning, they were first popular among women, who were humming them in their homes, hidden from the public. Traditional Bosnian cuisine is also bound to the privacy of the home. The journey of *sevdalinka* and Bosnian cuisine out of the private sphere of life involve public restaurants (*aščinicas*), soup kitchens (*imarets*), coffee houses (*kahve*), outings to the countryside (*teferičs*), evening gatherings over a drink (*akšamluks*) and travellers’ guesthouses (*musafirhanas*) (p. 14-15).
- (7) For Bosnian culture, coffee played an important role as it established a specific connection between the private and the public spheres of life. *Kahvedžinicas*, or *kahve*, as they are called more simply in Bosnia, were coffee houses opened in every town. They created a new atmosphere that had been unknown before. The coffee house was a public space accessible to everyone, and yet it had a homey atmosphere and hospitality (p. 80).
- (8) Bosnian coffee is made using a special utensil and following a precise procedure, different from the Turkish and European methods of coffee brewing. The main difference is that Bosnian coffee is “baked” since it is not brewed together with water. Ground coffee is first put in a heated-up coffee pot (*džezva*) and then boiling water is poured over it. The coffee is removed from the heat after it has risen (p. 86).
- (9) The baking process starts when ground coffee is put into a previously heated-up dry *džezva*. Boiling water is poured over the coffee and the *džezva* is not removed from the hotplate before the coffee has risen at least three times. Water is boiled in a special coffee ewer (*kahveni ibrik*).

At the end of the process, the little boiling water left in the ewer is poured over the coffee to allow the grounds to fall to the bottom of the *džezva*. Well-prepared Bosnian coffee has to allow a thick brown foam (*kajmak*) to form on top during the baking process (p. 86).

- (10) Bosnian coffee is never served on its own. A sweet or salted biscuit (*lokum*), sherbet, juice, etc. are served before the coffee. These snacks enrich the coffee-drinking ritual, just like serving tea in Great Britain so that it is regarded as a special kind of intermediate meal. Coffee is poured into *findžans* in such a way that first a small amount of the foam is skimmed and placed into every *findžan*, and then the coffee itself is poured. Without the foam on top of the cup, the Bosnian coffee simply is not “the coffee” (p. 87).
- (11) In Bosnia, coffee is sipped with a distinctive kind of pleasure (*ćeif*), without any hurry, anxiety or agitation. It is insulting and impolite to just “grab a coffee”. In the olden days, coffee bakers (*kahvedžija*) would refuse to take money from guests who would not abide by the ritual: “You do not owe me a single dinar, but I beg you, come to my coffeehouse – no more” (p. 88) [1].
- (12) The ritual commences by serving water, which prepares the palate to fully experience the true coffee flavour. The guest will put a sugar cube under their tongue and melt it as no sugar is added to coffee, and it is at this point that the long sipping ritual commences (p. 88).
- (13) The underlying paradigm of Bosnian culture is founded on the principles of “the open” and “the closed”. In the coffee-drinking ritual, this is manifested through an enchanting play between conversation and pregnant, friendly silence (p. 88).

By analysing the part of the corpus which refers to events and processes, it can be concluded that many activities described happen within the context of the “coffee culture”. In this case, the translator and the proofreaders opted for Type 2 – acceptable translatability for the noun “kahva” and Type 1 for the nouns denoting events and gatherings, whereas the English plural was added to the original nouns to preserve collective-culture connotations. Strategies applied in the category (a) can be found here too (e.g. coffee bakers (*kahvedžija*)), whereas the greatest emphasis is given to the sensory modality of taste, texture (of coffee) and touch (temperature).

(c) Names of drinks: Finally, the following examples are found with reference and emphasis given to actual names of traditional drinks:

- (14) In the Bosnian tradition, a special kind of after-dinner gathering at home is called *sijelo*. As light meals are eaten on this occasion, it is

common to serve *šerbe* (a syrup-like drink made by adding sugar and spices like cloves, honey or lemon to water; sherbet), coffee, light cooked meals, fresh or dry fruits (p. 57).

- (15) *Šerbe* (sherbet) is made from sweetened water, spices, rose petals, honey, lemon, etc. There is another kind of sherbet called *šurup*, which is made of a sweet fruit syrup. In the Bosnian language, the word *šerbe* is also used to refer to thickly boiled sugared water used as a coffee-sweetener or in sweet *pitas* (p. 64).
- (16) *Sofra* drinks. The individual dishes served at the *sofra* (meal in Islamic cultures) are accompanied by various drinks. These drinks are usually considered a replacement for salad, as the concept of salad we know today did not used to be present in the Bosnian cuisine (p. 63).
- (17) In the Bosnian cuisine it was common to serve a thicker yoghurt-like sour milk (*kiselo mlijeko*). This drink, an important food source, has always been known for a multitude of health benefits (p. 63).
- (18) *Boza* is a yellowish, slightly sour refreshing drink made of maize flour, yeast and sugar. Connoisseurs claim that genuine *boza* does not contain yeast and sugar, but three kinds of rough flour (maize, barley, wheat). After *boza* is left to ferment in wooden barrels, usually for three days, its flavour becomes refreshingly brisk. According to writer Miljenko Jergović, the brisk flavour, which makes it so popular, comes from alcohol (*boza* may contain from 0.5% to 5% of alcohol). A *špricer* (spritzer) is what you get when *boza* is proportionally mixed with lemonade (p. 64).
- (19) While *boza* is usually considered to be a summer drink, *salep*, a warm sweetened drink, is usually consumed in winter. *Salep* is made by brewing the lizard orchid (*Satyrium hircinum*, L.) (p. 64).
- (20) According to Evliya Çelebi, an Ottoman travel writer from the 17th century, apart from *rakija*, numerous other alcoholic beverages (though not as often) were brewed in Bosnia, such as: non-mulled wine (*muselez*), a kind of young wine called *hardaliye* (spiced by adding charlock, grapes, and other spices) and mint liquor (*nane rakisi*). Another popular and specially brewed drink, which contained 17% of alcohol, was *medovina* (mead; honey wine), the famous drink among ancient Slavs. In Sarajevo, there was a drink called *ramazanija* that, according to Çelebi, “was made of grapes and knocked you down” (p. 70).
- (21) Aside from *rakija*, usually made of the domestic plums, the Ottomans also brought *mastika*, a kind of fruit brandy spiced by the whitish sweet resin of the mastic tree. Rum is also mentioned in some sources (p. 70).

After analysing the names of traditional drinks and processes, it can be concluded that the translator and the proofreaders opted for Type 2—acceptable translatability in the case of alcoholic drinks while preserving their original name (in brackets), and Type 1 for the nouns denoting less familiar non-alcoholic traditional drinks (*salep*, *boza*, *šerbe*). The effect that the translation attempted to achieve while preserving every word that was not redundant in the reading process, was to appeal to the sensory modalities of taste and texture. It was sometimes necessary to use footnotes. This option was scarce, bearing in mind that the reader would need to look at the footnotes frequently, although footnotes should not present a problem in non-fiction texts (Landers, 2001).

The degree to which cultural distance should be bridged and the amount of explanation that is needed vary from one term to another. In the case of the present corpus, however, omission as a strategy was not used. In the case of bridging cultural gaps when certain artefacts do not exist in the target culture, different strategies were used, footnotes being employed very rarely (e.g. a “Bosnian rose”, *đulbešećerka*, from Turkish *gulbeşeker*, a very fragrant garden rose similar to the Bulgarian rose) while attempting to preserve the sensory modality (e.g. “ice-cold”) in the very description rather than the footnote. In the case of the word “čorba”, or “broth”, a footnote was used at the end of the book, to explain that broths served for breakfast were usually sour and thick. As for rare words, gelatine sheets, for example, rarely called *almasija*, were mentioned in the book only once (in the recipes section), which is the reason why their taste and texture—varying from solid to liquid state—were described in the footnote rather than in the text of the recipe itself.

Concluding remarks

This paper has explored the choices that the translator made when translating the texture and taste of traditional Bosnian-Herzegovinian drinks, as they are described in *The Bosnian Cuisine* (2016), by referring to a classification of noun phrases according to their translatability. In addition to the collected recipes, the publication analysed includes fragments of travelogues and excerpts from literary works, which allows readers to see the gastronomic terms in different contexts.

The English language equivalency between adjectives and noun phrases in food writing and translation, or a lack thereof, has been discussed in the paper as well. I have also addressed the use of footnotes and brackets in translation, as well as the negotiation process in terms of terminological, lexicological, lexicographical and intersemiotic debates with regard to four types of Bosnian noun phrases used for traditional or common dishes and the applicability of the classification for Bosnian traditional and less-known drinks.

In terms of methodology, the paper is a self-reflection on the theoretical framework proposed in my MA thesis in 2010 and applied to the translation of *The Bosnian Cuisine* (2016), which has allowed me to work on a similar corpus, produced with the contribution of proofreaders whose L1 is English. The analysis shows that there are similarities between the strategies used for translating names of traditional dishes and drinks, but that the context and discourse as such may determine translators' and proofreaders' decisions, especially if the focus of the text is on activating sensory modalities such as texture, taste, sight and touch in terms of the drinks described, occasions on which they are served, shapes of containers they are served in, etc. where the text may be classified in the domain of visual experience (Bourget 2017). In addition, another aim of this paper is to reach out to readers whose identity may be shaped by a reminiscence to food practices in their home country, whereas each word that is not redundant has been preserved in the translation. Taste and texture are two of the sense modalities that the translation aimed to evoke while keeping all the words that were not superfluous in reading and in terms of their order. Although footnotes should not be an issue in non-fiction works, it was occasionally required to use them. However, this option was not exhausted as the reader would have needed to often review the footnotes. Therefore, it has been once again confirmed that the issue of translating names of traditional dishes and drinks remains a challenge for linguists, a challenge that, nevertheless, allows translators to produce instructional input as well as hybrid equivalents.

Notes

[1] "If you go into a Starbucks and ask for 'coffee,' the barista most likely will give you a blank stare. To him the word means absolutely nothing." (Bellos 2012)

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When “To Cook Dog” Becomes “Ragoût de Chien” – Reclaiming the Language of Recipes in the French Translation of Jonathan Grimwood’s *The Last Banquet*

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Abstract

The translation of cooking recipes is always a challenge irrespective of the source and target language. However, this becomes even more challenging when the source text is set against the backdrop of the Enlightenment, Versailles, and the French Revolution. Jonathan Grimwood’s The Last Banquet proves to be an epic story of one man’s quest to know the world through its many and marvelous flavors. So, although the source language is English, the setting is French and since the book is replete with all sorts of sometimes mouthwatering, sometimes macabre dishes (“Three Snake Bouillabaisse” or “Pickled Wolf’s Heart”), the French translator is faced with the difficult challenge of French food that has to be translated from English. The present article is, consequently, going to look into the translation of this book into French, and argue that the French translator opted for a re-domestication or perhaps a reclaiming of food terminology. The translator’s choice here is to reclaim the French food culture, obviously “superior” to the Anglo-Saxon one, by enriching and re-appropriating the food-related language of the English source text. To show that this is strictly the translator’s choice for French, the corpus will extend to the Spanish translation of the novel, which turns out to be more loyal to the source text.

Keywords: culture-specific items, cultural reappropriation, metaphor, overtranslation, reclaiming translation.

Introduction

In analysing Jonathan Grimwood’s *The Last Banquet* and its translations in French and Spanish, it is essential to examine the way in which recipes are formulated in these languages since the food, which is a central part of this picaresque book, is mostly present through recipes that the main character tries to cook. Since the novel is written by an English writer but set in France seemingly paying tribute to the picaresque tradition, it is going to be intriguing to look at how the French translation recaptures elements that are typical of French cuisine are rendered in the English source text. It is predicted that the French translator is not going to be invisible (Venuti 1995), at least as far as the food sections are concerned, given the rich French cuisine tradition we are all familiar with.

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Theoretical background

Before delving into the proper analysis of the corpus, let us briefly discuss a few theoretical elements that help better comprehend some of the concepts to be used in this investigation.

Following Beaugrande and Dressler (1981: 197), a text type is a distinctive configuration of relational dominances obtaining between or among elements of (1) surface text; (2) the textual world; (3) stored knowledge patterns; and (4) a situation of occurrence.

Certain texts seem to be used repeatedly in certain situations with more or less the same function or functions. Consequently, such texts acquire conventional forms sometimes even rising to the status of social norms. Hence, the participants in the communication process are expected to observe these norms, otherwise, non-observance may be penalised. This is also the case of *The Last Banquet*, where the use of recipes is recurrent throughout the book.

Text-type conventions and norms play an important part both in text production, where authors have to comply with the conventions if they want to succeed in realising their communicative intentions, and text reception, where the receiver may infer the author's intentions from the conventional form of the text.

In the case of the selected corpus, which is made up of excerpts from the novel which are written in the form of culinary recipes, the translator is required to have some sort of familiarity with the language of recipes (Paradowski 2018: 54). This is in its turn a restricted form of practically oriented "technical" language used by a limited circle of specialists (Nordman 1996: 556), encompassing jargon, strictly formalised syntax, discourse conventions, and special mode of expression. Recipes distinguish themselves from other types of specialised genres by means of layout and a highly conventionalised macrostructure which is also interculturally stereotyped and easily recognisable (558). As such, recipes fall under Christiane Nord's umbrella of "instrumental translation", produced when the target text is supposed to "achieve the same range of functions as an original text" (1997: 50).

The second type of requisite knowledge is what is called 'encyclopaedic' knowledge and experience, especially in the domain of culture-specific items. This refers to phenomena characteristic of only one culture, or better known in the culture from which they stem (Hejwowski 2004: 128). In the case of recipes, embracing foodstuffs specific for particular cuisines, names of dishes traditional to a country, and terms describing cooking utensils, etc unknown in the target culture, among others. According to David Crystal, translators must "have a thorough understanding of the field of knowledge covered by the source text, and of any social, cultural, or emotional connotations that need to be specified in the target language if the intended effect is to be conveyed" (1987: 344).

All instructing texts, such as operating instructions, directions for use or, in the case of *The Last Banquet*, recipes, are characterised as stipulated above by a strictly formalised syntactic structure, illustrated in the table below:

Language	English	French	Spanish	Romanian
Syntactic structure	Imperative/ Simple Present Tense (instantaneous value for recipes)	Imperative	Traditional impersonal construction / now replaced by the infinitive	Impersonal reflexive voice
Example	"Melt the butter on medium heat"	"Plumez et videz les volatiles."	"Se mondan y lavan las patatas" / "mondar y lavar las patatas"	„Se fierbe apa, se curăță legumele, etc..."

According to K.C. Riley and A.L. Paugh, similar to "age, gender, kinship, and caste, socioeconomic class operates as a feature of contrast to highlight the social categories around which unequal social structures are forged and marked by food. This notion is codified in the term *haute cuisine*, the form of cooking first associated with the upper classes of France and then spread to other corners of the globe" (2019: 95). A.B. Trubek (2000: 127) explains how French cuisine came to signify *haute-ness* (that is, the high or upper class) and serve as a model for what cuisine itself could be, specifically the transformation of natural stuff by trained artisans into exquisitely cultural stuff and commodities people would pay for.

Therefore, aside from the morpho-syntactic structures described above, one has to pay close attention to lexical items as well. It is quite intriguing to look at the strategies employed by the French and Spanish translators of *The Last Banquet*, especially since the French translator sometimes opts for overtranslation in the case of the recipes scattered throughout the book.

Corpus analysis

The corpus under analysis is made up of the source text, henceforth ST, Jonathan Grimwood's *The Last Banquet*, and two translations of this novel: one into French by Carole Delporte, *Le Dernier Banquet*, published by Hachette in 2013, Target Text 1, henceforth TT1; and a Spanish translation, by Maria Maestro, *El ultimo banquete*, published by Alevosía in 2014, Target Text 2, henceforth TT2.

For the analysis of the corpus, the ideas of Aixela (1996: 53-4) are considered, which suggest that each linguistic community has a set of habits, value judgments, and classification systems that may overlap in some cases but are distinct in others. This leads to variation that needs to be taken into account

by any translator. Additionally, cultural transference is something that plays an important part in translation. Acknowledging the differences between two or more linguistic communities leads to cultural asymmetry in Aixela's terms. This means that the discourses of the two or more linguistic communities will reflect these differences in translation which may sometimes lead to opacity or even unacceptability in the target cultural system.

To this end, let us examine the first excerpt from the corpus.

(1) ST: To cook mice

Drown first. Clubbing produces sharp fragments of bone. Gut, skin and clean in water. Wrap three or four together in wet clay and bake in a bonfire. Alternatively, halve along length, fry with sliced onions and season with salt, pepper and thyme. This also works for sparrows. *Tastes like chicken.* (Grimwood 2013a: 25)

TT1: Fricassée de souris

Noyez-les. Les frapper laisse de minuscules éclats d'os. Enlevez les entrailles, la peau, et lavez à l'eau claire. Puis enrobez-en deux ou trois d'une couche d'argile et cuire au feu de cheminée. Sinon, coupez-les en deux dans le sens de la longueur, faites-les frire avec des oignons émincés et ajoutez du sel, du poivre et du thym. Cela fonctionne aussi avec les moineaux. *Goût de poulet.* (Grimwood 2013b: 20)

TT2: Para cocinar ratones

Ahogarlos primero. El apaleamiento genera astillas afiladas de hueso. Destripar, despellejar y lavar en agua. Envolver tres o cuatro juntos en un paño húmedo y asar en una hoguera. En su defecto, partir por la mitad a lo largo, freír con cebolla troceada y condimentar con sal, pimienta y tomillo. Esto también vale para los gorriones. *Sabe a pollo.* (Grimwood 2014: 20)

In this excerpt, the author of the source text follows the already discussed structure of recipes in English. Grimwood uses the instantaneous simple present tense and the imperative. When looking at the French translation in TT1, it can be noticed from the very beginning that the title of the recipe resorts to overtranslation. Here, the French cuisine cultural background of the translator feels the need to overexplain. Therefore, unlike ST and TT2, TT1 resorts to something that could be called cultural reappropriation. It is as if the French translator does not consider that the author did justice to French cuisine by using such a straightforward title as "to cook mice", so she resorts to the name of the dish that can otherwise be guessed from the description of the cooking process in the recipe itself. Thus, the simplistic and apparently impoverished "to cook mice" becomes "Fricassée de souris" in the French version, or "mice stew" if back-translation is considered. He equally offers direct instructions in the English recipe of the "French" dish which are modulated and enriched in the French translation. Thus, the very direct, "Clubbing produces sharp fragments of bone." becomes "Les frapper laisse de

minuscules éclats d'os." Notice here the presence of the anaphoric pronoun "les" in subject position, the verb "club" which becomes "frapper" > "hit", which is more neutral than "club", and the adjective "sharp", replaced by "minuscules" > "tiny". The adjective in "sliced onions" becomes "émincés" which means in fact "thinly sliced", which means that the translator felt the need to explicitate since there are various ways in which onions are sliced in French cuisine. TT2, on the other hand, follows ST much closer and employs the infinitive as illustrated in the table above for rendering the impersonal style of the recipe. Unlike the French translator, the Spanish one does not feel the need to overtranslate or further explicitate the ST.

The second dish to be discussed is made of sparrow meat.

(2) ST: To cook sparrow

Gut, pluck, remove legs and clean carcass in water. Alternate layers of salt and cleaned sparrow in a jar. When needed, wash away salt and fry with a little olive oil. In a separate pan fry onions until clear and add diced tomatoes. Put sparrows on top of sauce and garnish dish with basil. *Tastes like chicken*. (Grimwood 2013a: 25)

TT1: Moineaux tomate-basilic

Plumez et videz les volatiles. Arrachez les pattes et nettoyez la carcasse à l'eau. Alternez couches de sel et moineaux dans un bocal. Le jour venu, ôtez le sel et faites-les frire dans un peu d'huile d'olive. Dans une autre poêle, faites blondir des oignons, puis ajoutez des dés de tomate. Plongez les moineaux dans la sauce et aromatisez au basilic. *Goût de poulet*. (Grimwood 2013b: 20)

TT2: Para cocinar gorrión

Destripar, desplumar, arrancar las patas y lavar el cadáver en agua. Alternar capas de sal y gorrión limpio en una jarra. Si es necesario quitar la sal lavándolo en agua y freír en un poco de aceite de oliva. En otra sartén sofreír la cebolla hasta que se quede transparente y añadir tomates troceados. Colocar los gorriónes sobre la salsa y aderezar el plato con albahaca. *Sabe a pollo*. (Grimwood 2014: 20)

In this excerpt, a similar tendency is evident, with TT1 attempting to bridge the invisible cultural gap, as if the cultural knowledge of the English writer is not suitable enough to properly describe French cuisine, so "to cook sparrow", the title of this recipe, is rendered as "Moineaux tomate-basilic" > "sparrows in tomato and basil" (back-translation mine), which is again an instance of overtranslation and explicitation. TT2 opts for equivalence of the title of this recipe. The first instruction in the ST, "Gut, pluck, remove legs and clean carcass in water." is split into two separate syntactic structures in TT1 "Plumez et videz les volatiles. Arrachez les pattes et nettoyez la carcasse à l'eau." > "Pluck and empty the birds. Pull out the paws and clean the carcass in water." (back-translation mine) The simple instruction, "fry onions until clear" becomes "faites blondir des oignons" > "brown the onions" (back-translation

mine), the French translator becoming once again visible through the choice of a more specialised verb. Another more specific verb is used to translate “put” > “plongez” > “dip” (back-translation) TT2 opts in this case for “colocar” = “to place”, which is closer in meaning and register to the ST verb “put”.

The third recipe to be discussed is a dish made out of cat meat.

(3) ST: To cook cat

Gut animal, skin, remove head and tail, cut off paws and lower limb at joint, wash body cavity thoroughly. Carcass looks just like rabbit and can be roasted in similar way. Spit, brush with oil, season with tarragon. Cook until juices run clear when meat pierced with a knife. *Tastes like chicken.* (Grimwood 2013a: 26)

TT1: Chat à l'estragon

Videz et dépecez l'animal, ôtez la tête et la queue, coupez le bout des pattes et les membres inférieurs au niveau de l'articulation. Lavez à grande eau l'intérieur du corps. La carcasse ressemble à celle d'un lapin et peut être rôtie de la même manière. Embrochez la bête, enduisez-la d'huile et ajoutez de l'estragon. Laissez cuire jusqu'à ce qu'un jus clair s'écoule quand on perce la chair avec un couteau. *Goût de poulet.* (Grimwood 2013b: 21)

TT2: Para cocinar gato

Destripar al animal, despellejar, quitar cabeza y cola, cortar las zarpas y cuartos traseros por las articulaciones, lavar a conciencia el orificio corporal. La carcasa es exactamente igual que la del conejo y puede asarse de un modo similar. Espetar, untar con aceite, condimentar con estragón. Cocinar hasta que el jugo salga claro al pinchar la carne con un cuchillo. *Sabe a pollo.* (Grimwood 2014: 21)

Again, as was the case with the previous excerpts, the French translator resorts to explicitation/overtranslation of the recipe title “To cook cat” which becomes “Chat à l'estragon” which is in fact if back-translated, “cat with tarragon”. It is important to specify that the French translator does not make up these titles, but rather chooses them as a result of the description offered by the author in the instructions of the recipes. The tarragon is, in fact, mentioned in the cooking instructions. The first sentence in the recipe, which is nothing but a very direct instruction on how to prepare the meat, is again split into two separate syntactic structures “Videz et dépecez l'animal, ôtez la tête et la queue, coupez le bout des pattes et les membres inférieurs au niveau de l'articulation. Lavez à grande eau l'intérieur du corps.” The split into apparently two separate instructions somehow emphasizes on the importance of the thorough washing of the meat. The very straightforward verb “Spit” becomes “embrochez la bête” > “skewer the beast”, which is another instance of explicitation, TT2, using the equivalent verb “espeter” > “spit”.

The fourth recipe to be discussed refers to ways of cooking dog meat, followed by the main character's musings on how the different types of meat taste.

(4) **ST: To cook dog**

Gut, skin and joint. The thighs are too fatty to make good eating, the flanks can be trimmed for steak, the rest can be stewed or fried at a pinch. Boiling the meat before roasting or frying removes fat and helps lessen the distinctive flavour. Sauce heavily or season with chillies. *Tastes like sour mutton.*

The sad truth is that, apart from dog, one animal tastes much like another, and those that don't taste like chicken mostly taste like beef, with the rest tasting like mutton. The secret of variety for meat is in the spicing. Vegetables, fruits, herbs have far wider variations in taste than the creatures that pick, browse or gnaw upon them. Even the way we describe the taste of meats other than the obvious ones is wrong. We say cat tastes like chicken when, had we been weaned on kitten stew, we'd say chicken tastes like cat. (Grimwood 2013a: 25)

TT1: Ragoût de chien

Videz, dépecez et désarticulez l'animal. Les cuisses sont trop grasses pour être cuisinées, les flancs peuvent être découpés en steaks, le reste peut être cuit en ragoût, voire frit à la poêle. Faire bouillir la viande avant de la faire rôtir ou la frire dégraisse et adoucit la saveur caractéristique. Ajoutez une sauce forte ou pimentée. *Goût de mouton aigre.*

La triste vérité, c'est qu'en dehors du chien, tous les animaux ont pratiquement le même goût, et ceux qui ne ressemblent pas au poulet font presque tous penser à du bœuf, les autres, à du mouton. Le secret de la variété des viandes est l'épice. Les légumes, les fruits et les herbes aromatiques ont un éventail de saveurs bien plus large que les créatures qui les cueillent, les mâchent et les digèrent. Même notre description du goût des viandes est faussée. Nous pensons que le chat a la saveur du poulet alors que, si nous avions été nourris toute notre enfance au ragoût de chatons, nous aurions dit que le poulet avait le goût du chat. (Grimwood 2013b: 20)

TT2: Para cocinar perro

Limpiar, destripar y trocear. Los muslos son demasiado grasos para resultar saludables, la falda puede cortarse en filetes, el resto puede guisarse o freírse si es necesario. Hervir la carne antes de asar o freírla elimina la grasa y ayuda a suavizar su característico sabor. Salpimentar generosamente o acompañar con guindilla. *Sabe a cordero rancio.*

La triste realidad es que, salvo el perro, casi todos los animales saben igual, y los que no saben a pollo, saben en su mayoría a carne de vaca, y el resto a cordero. El secreto de la variedad en la carne está en las especias con que se adereza. La verdura, la fruta, las hierbas tienen muchas más variaciones de sabor que las criaturas que las picotean, desbrozan o rumian. Incluso el modo en que describimos el sabor de carnes distintas a las típicas es erróneo. Decimos que el gato sabe a pollo cuando, si nos hubiéramos acostumbrado al guiso de gato, diríamos que el pollo sabe a gato. (Grimwood 2014: 20)

As with the previous excerpts, it is the French translation that stands out. It seems to be a constant attempt on the part of the French translator to bridge the cultural gap by overtranslating the title of the recipe. Thus, "to cook dog" is rephrased as "Ragoût de chien" > "dog stew".

The following instruction in the recipe “Sauce heavily or season with chillies” is rendered in two very different ways in TT1, “Ajoutez une sauce forte ou pimentée” (= “Add a hot or spicy sauce”), and in TT2, “Salpimentar generosamente o acompañar con guindilla” (= “Season generously with salt and pepper or add chilli. ”) In this case, both the French and the Spanish translators are highly visible, their choices clearly coming from a place that wishes to bridge the cultural culinary gap between the source and target cultures.

In the excerpt that immediately follows the recipe, where the main character muses over the various tastes of the unusual types of meat in his recipes, the following sentence appears: “Vegetables, fruits, herbs have far wider *variations in taste*” > “Les légumes, les fruits et les herbes aromatiques ont *un éventail de saveurs bien plus large*” > “La verdura, la fruta, las hierbas tienen muchas más *variaciones de sabor*”. Interestingly, while TT2 opts for equivalence in the case of *variations in taste*, TT1 chooses a more metaphoric translation of *variations* by using the word *un éventail* (= a fan), which in most Romance languages recalls the image of a wide array of something.

Conclusions

In the current analysis of the French and Spanish translations of Jonathan Grimwood’s novel *The Last Banquet*, the various strategies adopted by the two translators were examined. It was argued that the French translator chose to re-domesticate, reclaim, or even re-appropriate food terminology. The translator’s choice in TT1 was to reclaim the French food culture. One can perceive in the French translator’s choices the concept of a “superior” French cuisine in comparison to the Anglo-Saxon one. This is achieved by enriching and re-appropriating the food-related language of the English source text. Conversely, analysis of the Spanish translation of the novel, showed that the Spanish translator is more loyal to the source text, resorting in most cases to equivalence.

In an attempt to supposedly bridge the cultural gap, the French translator goes as far as reclaiming French cuisine by overtranslating and explicating the titles of the recipes. This makes the French translator more visible although it cannot openly be argued that she is less loyal to the source text.

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“The Dinner Was as Well Dressed as Any I Ever Saw”: Intertextuality in Nine Romanian Versions of *Pride and Prejudice*

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Abstract

The present article investigates intertextuality in the retranslation of food-related culture-specific items employed in Jane Austen’s novel *Pride and Prejudice*. Such an investigation is important because, as shown in the literature, Jane Austen mentions food stuffs and food-related habits sparingly but meaningfully, in order to characterise her protagonists. The textual-based analysis in the article is couched in Zhang & Ma’s (2018) framework on intertextuality in retranslation and in Klaudy’s (2009) system of translational strategies. The investigation conducted in this article disproves my initial prediction that the second translation, published during communism, is the more influential target text, to the detriment of the first one, published in 1943, and that the subsequent target texts are in a relation of filiation with the second target text.

Keywords: culture-specific items, dissidence, filiation, intertextuality, retranslation

Introduction

The present article aims at tracing instances of intertextuality in nine Romanian versions of Jane Austen’s novel, *Pride and Prejudice*. I will conduct this investigation in the framework proposed by Zhang & Ma (2018) with regard to intertextuality in retranslation (IR henceforth) and by Klaudy (2009) with respect to explicitation and implicitation as translational strategies. I am especially interested in looking at how the (re)translators of this classic deal with culture-specific items that have to do with food, cooking and table manners. Culture-loaded items (also known as culturemes or culture-specific items, Aixelá 1996) are known to provide important clues with respect to translational choices. Moreover, as pointed out by Mona Baker (1992: 230), any kind of reference to a type of food that the reader is not familiar with might come as disruptive to the textual continuity of the translated version, which makes the treatment of such items in translation subject to various specific strategies on the part of the (re)translator. Therefore, this article will rely on a textual-based analysis to identify the strategies employed by (re)translators and to establish to what degree they count as instances of IR.

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In Zhang & Ma's article, the definition of intertextuality is borrowed from Genette (1997: 1) as "all that sets the text in a relationship, whether obvious or concealed, with other texts". A rough taxonomy of intertextuality in translation studies evinces three main categories: intertextuality between the source text and the other texts in the source culture's polysystem [1], intertextuality between the various target texts that are available for a certain source text (what Zhang & Ma refer to as "intertextuality in retranslation", abbreviated as IR) and intertextuality between the target text(s) and the target culture's polysystem. While the first category has been extensively discussed in various literary and translation studies, the second has been only marginally tackled in the literature, and mainly from a "paratextual" perspective, whereas the third has not been documented at all. With respect to the second category, Zhang & Ma propose a shift from an analysis that involves "direct links between human agents" (2018: 580) to a textual analysis that relies on tracing intertextuality between various versions by looking at textual cues. In other words, they propose a shift from perusing (often poorly represented) paratexts to analysing the target texts themselves so as to trace instances of what they call "filiation" and "dissidence". In their study, filiation is defined as "textual similarities that reflect a filiation stance from one translation towards another" (580), while dissidence is seen as "textual differences that indicate one translation is made to distinguish from or even to compete against another" (581). These phenomena can be identified at various levels of analysis: lexical, semantic, syntactic, pragmatic, etc. One good way of identifying traces of IR is, for instance, to look at how much overlapping is present in two (or more) target texts. As shown in the literature (VanPoucke, 2020), overlapping is a phenomenon that characterizes retranslation. Zhang & Ma (2018) remark that overlapping can be coincidental, but that there are certain clues that might indicate whether the retranslator has consulted the previous version and borrowed or, on the contrary, refrained from using the same techniques. One of the most effective ways of identifying filiation or dissidence is, for instance, looking at the treatment of culture-loaded terms. I would venture to say, however, that, in my opinion, filiation seems much easier to prove than dissidence, a statement that I intend to check while analysing the corpus.

Culture-specific items are, therefore, seen as one of the important features of a source text that can reveal in translation whether a target text is indebted to another or whether it is in a relation of rivalry with it. If the source text is part of a literary canon, as is the case of Jane Austen's novel, chances are that the translator will refrain from intervening (mediating) and from working too much for a transparency of the element. This is because of an "anxiety of influence" (Koskinen & Paloposki 2015, borrowing from Bloom 1973) generated both by the original (as part of the literary canon) and, possibly, by one of the early versions that might count, itself, as a "pseudo-original" (Pym

2004). In retranslation theory, the first target text is often seen as introductory (it introduces the source text to the target readers, by “domesticating” the exotic, opaque elements), while the subsequent target texts might adopt a “foreignizing” strategy (by protecting the “alien” character of the culturemes and explaining them intra- or extra-textually rather than absorbing them into the target culture). I intend to check whether this is in fact the case with the target texts under analysis.

Romanian translations of the novel

Pride and Prejudice counts as a classic and it has been very influential culturally worldwide. One can trace, for instance, the subgenre of regency romances [2] as originating from Austen’s work (Kamblé *et al.* 2020). This is why I expected to find at least three or four Romanian versions of *Pride and Prejudice* when I started to investigate the history of the Romanian translation of this book. Like many other English novels that were welcomed in the Romanian polysystem, the first translation into Romanian happened quite late (although the original was published in 1813, the first Romanian version was in 1943, as mentioned in Burlacu *et al.* 2005) and appeared under the title *Surorile Bennet* (“The Bennet Sisters”). All the subsequent target texts appeared under the title *Mândrie și prejudecată* (“Pride and Prejudice”). The second version was due to Ana Almăgeanu and was published twenty-five years later in the prestigious collection of *Clasicii literaturii universale* (“The classics of world literature”) by one of the most important publishing houses of the communist era. This version was the one that kept being republished even after 1989 (the post-communist period), as shown in Table 1 below. Its history is quite intricate, since not only did it undergo many republications, but also it was sold to the readers as a distinct version by at least three various publishing houses that had no qualms in either erasing the name of the translator or in placing this text under a different translator’s name (see Target Text 6 in Table 1). The third target text, published in 1992 is as yet unattested in the dictionaries, as no mention is made in Borza *et al.* 2017, and I believe it was a very obscure publication and had no impact on the subsequent translations. The fourth target text belongs to Anca Florea and appeared in 2004, twelve years later than the third version, only to be constantly republished by various publishing houses until recently (2022 is the year of its latest publication). This version must have constantly competed with TT2/6, the “communist” translation, as well as with TT8, i.e. Florența Simion’s version, which was first published in 2016 by Litera Publishing House and republished twice since. Since these three target texts (TT2, TT4 and TT8) were constantly republished, I expect that they will prove as the more “influential” versions in the lot, which is also confirmed by the fact that they have already been subject to analysis (Baicu 2023) in the literature. TT5 and TT7 were published at Cluj and Oradea, respectively, and

must have been less influential versions, probably because they were not as widely distributed. While TT5 is riddled with instances of mistranslation, TT7 is the only version whose source text is an American annotated version, with a taxonomy of colourful notes marked by emoticons that must have been created with a view to making the classic text palatable to the modern American reader. Finally, the last target text under discussion, TT9, was published in 2017 by RAO and its translator is not a “person” but a company (Grael Soft SRL), which makes one wonder whether this target text was the object of more than one translator.

From what I have noticed so far, working on the retranslation of literary works from English to Romanian for the past few years, there are three periods in the translation of English literature: the pre-communist, communist, and post-communist periods. So far, in most cases, the most influential version (many times republished) has been the “communist” one, which I expect to be the case here as well. Most of the “communist” target texts held the status of “pseudo-non-retranslations” (to adapt a notion proposed by Svahn 2023), in the sense that they were the only accessible versions and were many times republished, reigning supreme for a few decades and influencing the new generations of translators. Retranslations as such started to be commissioned only after 1989 and were dictated by the post-communist boom in the publishing business (Constantinescu *et al.* 2021: 134) as well as by other considerations. Consequently, I expect that TT2 (TT6) will count as the most influential version, as a “pseudo-original” (Pym 2004). My intuition is that IR is traceable, especially with respect to this particular target text.

Table 1: The Romanian Versions of *Pride and Prejudice*

The Pre-Communist Period	TT1 - <i>Surorile Bennet</i> 1943, translated by Gh. Nenişor, Socec & Co. S.A.R. publishing house (republished in 1993 under the name <i>Mândrie și prejudecată</i> , Mengel Impex – S.R.L publishing house, Bucureşti).
The Communist Period (1947-1989)	TT2 - <i>Mândrie și prejudecată</i> 1968, translated by Ana Almăgeanu , Editura pentru literatură universală in the collection <i>Clasicii literaturii universale</i> (republished in 1970 by Eminescu Publishing House in the collection <i>Romanul de dragoste</i> (“The Love Novel”). Republished after 1989: 1992, Garamond; 1998, RAO.
The Post-Communist Period	TT3 - <i>Mândrie și prejudecată</i> 1992, translated by Al. Petrea, published by Valahia.
	TT4 - <i>Mândrie și prejudecată</i> 2004, translated by Anca Florea, republished in 2006, 2008 by Leda Clasic; 2013, republished in 2014 and 2022 by Corint Books.
	TT5 - <i>Mândrie și prejudecată</i> 2006, translated by Anamaria Alb, published by Maxim Bit (Cluj).

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	TT6 - <i>Mândrie și prejudecată</i> 2011, translated (plagiarised?) by Corina Ungureanu, published by Adevărul Holding (also republished in 2008 by Aldo Press, in 2016 by Dexon). Also printed as a pirated version by Daffi's Books, where no year of publication or translator is mentioned. The text is almost identical to TT2!
	TT7 - <i>Mândrie și prejudecată</i> 2012, translated by Mariana Bront, published by Casa Cărții (Oradea) – source text: annotated American edition.
	TT8 - <i>Mândrie și prejudecată</i> 2016, translated by Florența Simion, published by Litera, republished in 2018, 2020.
	TT9 - <i>Mândrie și prejudecată</i> 2017, translated by Graal Soft SRL, published by RAO.

Analysis

The investigation I propose seems meaningful the more so as it has been pointed out in the literature (Lane 2003, Pahlau 2019, Wei 2021) that Jane Austen mentions food stuffs only sparingly and makes use of food-related terminology to characterise the protagonists and provide insight into her dietary philosophy that has to do with good stewardship, decency and moderation. Also, some of the commonly used terms (*dinner, lunch, supper*) may count as culture-loaded items because the period in which Austen wrote was a transition period for eating habits (Lane 2003), which meant that the terminology itself was changing: see, for instance, the meaning of the noun *dinner*, which is not, in fact, the equivalent of the Romanian “cină”. In this case, the noun *cină* is more appropriate as a translation for the English term *supper*. At the time Austen was writing her novels, dinner, which had previously been an early meal, had been pushed later in the afternoon (according to Lane 2003 and Shapard 2007, the Bennets dined as late as 4 o'clock, while the richer families, such as the Bingleys, dined even later, i.e. around 6 o'clock). Suppers, on the other hand, were invariably provided later in the evening (at balls, such as the one organized by Bingley, or evening gatherings, such as the party thrown by Aunt Philips), and were falling out of fashion (Shapard 2007: 65).

Consider the following excerpt, where both *supper* and *dinner* are mentioned:

Mrs. Bennet had designed to keep the two Netherfield gentlemen to **supper**; but their carriage was unluckily ordered before any of the others, and she had no opportunity of detaining them. “Well girls,” said she, as soon as they were left to themselves, “What say you to the day? I think every thing has passed off uncommonly well, I assure you. The **dinner** was as well dressed as any I ever saw. The venison was roasted to a turn –and everybody said, they never saw so fat a haunch. (*Pride and Prejudice*, Volume III, Chapter 12, p. 359)

TT1 is the only one that renders *supper* as *supeu* (defined by The Dictionary of Romanian (DEX 2016: 1885) as “meal taken late in the evening, after coming out of the theatre/opera”), while all the other target texts, except for TT5, opt for *cină* (the equivalent of what passes for “dinner” today). TT5 goes for explicitation by division (*masa de seară* “the evening meal”). *Dinner*, on the other hand, is implicated by generalisation as *masa* “the meal” in TT1, omitted in TT2, translated as *prânzul* “the lunch” in TT3, TT4 and TT6, as *cina* “the dinner” in TT5, *masa* in TT7 and TT8, and as *meniul de la prânz* (“the menu for lunch”) in TT9. TT6, otherwise identical to TT2, repairs the omission by translating the missing sentence (*The dinner was as well dressed as any I ever saw.*), which indicates that the editor at least revised the text they appropriated. While the strategy employed in most target texts is to alternate between the terms *cină/prânz* for *supper/dinner*, or to use implicitation by generalisation, replacing the problematic noun *dinner* with *masă* “meal” or with a paraphrase, which counts as explicitation by division, TT5 manages to disrupt cohesion by referring first to keeping the gentlemen to an “evening meal” and then discussing their “dinner”, which is supposed to have already happened during the day. This counts as an instance of mistranslation.

Interestingly enough, the distinction *supper/dinner* is obliterated in many of the other instances where in the source text the noun *dinner* is mentioned in isolation (i.e. without being placed in opposition with *supper*). The source text mentions the word *dinner* on five different occasions. As suggested before, the word *dinner* is not translatable by the Romanian noun *cină* “dinner” because its semantics is not yet that of its modern counterpart. This was visible in the translation of the excerpt above, where most target texts, with the notable exception of TT5, attempted to distinguish the noun *dinner* from *supper*, either by translating *dinner* with “lunch”, or by using a vaguer term, *masă* (“meal”). What happens with the other five instances where the noun *dinner* is mentioned? TT1 renders it as *masă* “meal” (4 instances) or as *dineu* “dinner party” (1), TT2/TT6 opts for *masă* “meal” (2 instances), *prânz* “lunch” (1), *dejun* “lunch” (1), *cină* “dinner” (1), TT3 makes use of *masă* (2), *prânz* (3), a *prânzi* (“to take lunch”) (1), TT4 goes for *masă* (2), *cină* (3), TT5 and TT7 opt for *cină* (5), TT8 selects *masă* (2), *prânz* (1), *bucate* “victuals” (1), *cină* (1), while TT9 goes for *cină* (3), *masă* (2). In those instances where the word *cină* was employed by the target texts, the (re)translators were in fact inconsistent. A clear preference for this type of inconsistency can be identified in TT4, TT5, TT7 and TT9. This means that these particular target texts are characterized by overlapping, yet there is little indication that they borrowed from one another. A similar pattern of strategies can also be traced between TT2/6 and TT8, that only resort to the noun *cină* once. It seems that there is a similitude of strategies between these particular target texts.

Let us now look at the translation of some of the more problematic bits in the excerpt above and consider the lexical choices and strategies of the target texts. Consider Table 2:

Table 2: The dinner was as well dressed as any I ever saw.

ST	The dinner was as well dressed as any I ever saw. (p. 359)	BACK TRANSLATION
TT1	Masa a fost fără cusur. (p. 312)	The meal was flawless.
TT2	-	-
TT3	Prânzul a fost foarte gustos. (p. 224)	The lunch was very tasty.
TT4	Prânzul a fost atât de reușit, cum n-am mai văzut vreodată. (p. 322)	The lunch was so excellent, as I have never seen.
TT5	Cina fu la fel de arătoasă ca nimic altceva înainte. (p. 220)	The dinner was as good looking as nothing before.
TT6	Prânzul s-a prezentat cum n-am mai pomenit de mult. (p. 377)	The lunch presented itself as I haven't found it in a long while.
TT7	În viața mea n-am mai văzut masă îmbelșugată ca aceasta! (p. 403)	Never in my life have I seen such bountiful meal as this!
TT8	Masa a fost cum n-am mai pomenit de mult. (p. 348)	The meal was as I haven't found it in a long while.
TT9	Meniul de la prânz a fost extrem de bine întocmit. (p. 476)	The lunch menu was extremely well put together.

There are two hurdles to overcome in the translation of the sentence in Table 2. On the one hand, the participle (*well*) *dressed*, which comes from the phrase *to dress food*, that means preparing food for cooking or for serving in such a way that it looks as attractive as possible. Romanian does not have an equivalent for this phrase, which prompts the translators to resort to various strategies: either by employing evaluative phrases such as *fără cusur* “flawless”, *gustos* “tasty”, *reușit* “excellent”, or participles such as *bine întocmit* “well put together”, or by using verbs such as *a se prezenta* “present oneself”, or by employing an adjunct clause of comparison as a predicative (in TT8). There is no lexical overlapping, which might hint at “dissidence” on the part of the translators. The second difficulty in translation is the comparative phrase *as any I ever saw* which is, in fact, a fake comparison since it functions more as an intensifier. This is sensed by some of the target texts: they choose to reformulate the original sentence by employing superlatives (“flawless” in TT1, “very tasty” in TT3, “extremely well put together” in TT9). I would argue this is the most appropriate strategy here because the person uttering the sentence is the mistress of the house, who is remarking upon the excellence of her housekeeping skills in plotting an excellent dinner. The implication is not that she outdid herself or other ladies of quality, but that she rose to the occasion (Mrs Bennet is, in fact, complimenting herself.) A relation of filiation might be traced between TT6 and

TT8 with respect to lexical choices: both make use of the adjunct comparative clause *cum n-am mai pomenit de mult* “as I haven’t found it in a long while”, which can hardly be seen as coincidental in this case.

Table 3: Roasted to a turn

ST	The venison was roasted to a turn - and everybody said, they never saw so fat a haunch. (p. 359)	BACK TRANSLATION
TT1	Carnea bine friptă - (p. 312)	The meat well done -
TT2	Vânatul a fost fript tocmai la țanc și toți au spus că n-au mai văzut vreodată o pulpă atât de grasă. (p. 306)	The venison was roasted in the nick of time and all said they never saw such a fat haunch.
TT3	Vânatul a fost bine pregătit și suficient de împănat și l-au lăudat toți. (p. 224)	The venison was well prepared and sufficiently laced with fat and everyone praised it.
TT4	Vânatul a fost rumenit la timp și toți au spus că n-au mai văzut o pulpă atât de grasă. (p. 322)	The venison was done in time and all said they didn’t see such a fat haunch.
TT5	Căprioara a fost pusă la rotisor și toți au căzut de acord că nu au văzut o pulpă atât de mare. (p. 220)	The deer was turned against a rotisserie and everyone agreed that they hadn’t seen such a big haunch.
TT6	Vânatul a fost fript atât cât trebuia și toți au spus că n-au mai văzut vreodată o pulpă atât de grasă. (p. 377)	The venison was roasted as much as it should and everyone said they never saw such a fat haunch.
TT7	Carnea de căprioară a fost rumenită numai bine - absolut toată lumea a spus că niciodată nu a mai avut parte de un prânz atât de bogat ca acesta! (p. 403)	The deer meat was done to a turn - absolutely everybody said that they never had such a rich lunch as this one!
TT8	Vânatul a fost fript tocmai bine și toți au spus că n-au mai văzut vreodată o pulpă atât de grasă. (p. 348)	The venison was roasted properly and all said they never saw such a fat haunch.
TT9	Vânatul a fost făcut la proțap - și toți au zis că n-au mai mâncat o pulpă atât de grasă. (p. 476)	The venison was turned on a spit - and everyone said they never ate such a fat haunch.

Table 3 provides variants for the final sentence in the excerpt quoted above. There is a clear relationship between TT2 and TT4. TT2 translates the phrase *a turn* by *la țanc*, which is a rather rarely employed idiom in Romanian, meaning “in the nick of time”. TT4 chooses the phrase *la timp*, which is the equivalent of “in time”. Both are instances of mistranslation, and one might suspect TT4 of having consulted TT2 and replacing the rarer idiomatic phrase with a more commonly used one. Most translations resort to the verbs *a frige*

“to roast” or a *rumeni* “to brown” for the English verb *to roast*, but it is difficult to distinguish overlapping from filiation in these cases, since these are the available Romanian verbs equivalent with *roast*.

There is also overlapping between TT2/6, TT4 and TT8, and, arguably, partial overlapping between them and TT5, TT9, in the translation of the clause *they never saw so fat a haunch*. Again, it is difficult to figure out whether the overlapping is coincidental or strategic. TT5 and TT9 both resort to an unexpected image (*rotisserie, roasted on a spit*), which puts them in a relation of unlikely filiation (I believe it to be unlikely because, as I was saying, I doubt that the fifth target text was distributed widely enough so as to be accessible to subsequent translators). The most discordant of all versions seems to be TT3, which stands out by the distinct strategies employed both in its lexical choices and in its reordering syntax. However, there is nothing that indicates that the translator of TT3 has previously consulted TT1 or TT2 and is in a relation of “dissidence” with either of them.

Consider also the excerpt proposed in Table 4, where most versions have trouble finding an equivalent for the culture-specific term *mince pies* “sweet pie, filled with mincemeat, i.e. a mixture of fruit, spices, beef suet. Mincemeat formerly contained ground beef or venison.” Interestingly enough, only TT1 seems to imply that this is a kind of dessert (Lane 2003: 66), although the Romanian *budincă* “pudding” is not necessarily sweet.

All the other versions (except for the mistranslation in TT8) opt for either *pateuri* “pastry” or *placinte* “pies”, which might be because the most prestigious English-Romanian dictionary available to Romanian translators defines *mince pies* as “pateuri sau placinte cu carne” (“pastry or meat pies”), although in the next entry, *mincemeat* is correctly defined as “umplutură (din stafide, migdale, zahar, miere etc.) pentru prăjituri sau plăcinte.” (“filling made of raisins, almonds, sugar, honey, etc. for cakes or pies.”) (Levițchi et al. 1974/2004: 619).

Table 4: Dine. Mince pies.

ST	Did Charlotte dine with you? “No, she would go home. I fancy she was wanted about the mince pies. (p. 67)	BACK TRANSLATION
TT1	-Și Charlotte a rămas la masa la noi? -Nu, fiindcă zicea că are treabă acasă. Cred că avea de făcut o budincă. (p. 43)	“So did Charlotte stay for a meal with us?” “No, because she said she had work to do at home. I think she was supposed to cook a pudding.
TT2	-Charlotte a luat masa la noi? -Nu, a ținut morțiș să plece acasă. Îmi închipui că aveau nevoie de ea pentru pateuri. (p. 55)	„Did Charlotte have a meal with us?”

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		"No, she was adamant about going home. I imagine they needed her about the pastry."
TT3	-Ai oprit-o pe Charlotte la masă? -Nu, a insistat să se întoarcă acasă. Se pare că trebuia să ajute la pateuri. (p. 33)	"Have you asked Charlotte to stay for a meal?" "No, she insisted on going back home. It seems she had to help with the pastry."
TT4	-Charlotte a luat cina cu voi? -Nu, a preferat să plece acasă. Cred că aveau nevoie de ea pentru pateuri. (p. 56)	"Did Charlotte dine with you?" "No, she preferred to go home. I think they needed her for the pastry."
TT5	-Charlotte a cinat cu voi? -Nu, a plecat acasă. Cred că a fost chemată în legătură cu plăcinta. (p. 32)	"Did Charlotte dine with you?" "No, she left for home. I think she was summoned about the pie."
TT6	-Charlotte a luat masa la noi? -Nu, a ținut morțiș să plece acasă. Îmi închipui că au nevoie de ea pentru pateuri. (p. 51)	„Did Charlotte have a meal with us?” "No, she was adamant about going home. I imagine they needed her about the pastry."
TT7	-Charlotte a luat cina împreună cu voi ? -Nu, a dorit să meargă acasă. Cred că a fost chemată acasă pentru a găti plăcinte. (p. 58)	"Did Charlotte dine with you?" "No, she wished to go home. I think she was called home to bake pies."
TT8	-Charlotte a rămas la masă? -Nu, s-a dus acasă. Cred că era nevoie de ea pentru țânci. (p. 48)	"Did Charlotte stay for a meal?" "No, she left for home. I think they needed her for the kids."
TT9	-Charlotte a rămas la cină? -Nu, a preferat să plece acasă. Bănuiesc că era nevoie de ajutorul ei la bucătărie, pentru pateurile cu carne. (p. 63)	"Did Charlotte stay for dinner?" "No, she preferred to go home. I guess they needed her help in the kitchen, for the meat patties."

Another interesting point to make about the example in Table 4 is that TT1, TT2/6, TT3 and TT8 translate the verb *to dine* by the much more general (and therefore vaguer) *a lua masa* "to have a meal/to eat", while all the other target texts opt to mistranslate by using the verb *a cina* "to have dinner". Thus, implicitation (by generalization) is favoured by half of the versions, whereas the other target texts (TT4, TT5, TT7, TT9) attempt equivalence, but manage to be inconsistent and mistranslate. It is, however, difficult to identify this sort of overlapping as an instance of filiation.

The last food-related culture-specific item I would like to discuss is the term *white soup*, a soup made of veal stock, almonds and cream, thickened with rice, bread crumbs or egg yolk (Lane 2003: 58, Shapard 2007: 82) that Bingley mentions in Volume I, Chapter 11 as being a prerequisite for the ball he promises to the younger Bennet sisters: "as for the ball, it is quite a settled thing;

and as soon as Nicholls has made white soup enough I shall send round my cards" (p. 79). Three strategies are applied in this case: TT1 and TT5 resort to implicitation by omission, while TT3 opts for implicitation by generalization (*cum se termină pregătirile culinare, voi lansa invitațiile* "as soon as culinary preparations are over, I will launch the invitations" p. 40). TT7, TT8 and TT9 opt for *supă albă* "white soup", although this phrase is not a commonly used one in Romanian (Romanian has only *supă dreasă cu smântână* "soup seasoned with sour cream"). TT7 translates the American editor's footnote, TT8 offers a translator's footnote that accurately explains the contents of white soup, while TT9 does not offer any kind of extratextual explicitation. TT2/6 and TT4 on the other hand, opt for *cremă de legume* "vegetable cream soup", which is a form of domestication. TT2 adds a translator's footnote that mentions asparagus, mushrooms and cream, which does not in fact correspond with the ingredients of white soup. The tendency to domesticate, manifest in the replacement of the term *white soup* with the less exotic *cremă de legume* is opposed by the foreignising tendency manifest in the presence of the translator's footnotes in TT2. This is interesting to a translation theorist, because, as mentioned in the introductory part of this article, one would expect mostly domestication in early target texts.

Conclusions

The present article attempted to trace instances of intertextuality in retranslation by investigating food-related culturemes in nine Romanian versions of *Pride and Prejudice*. While certain instances of filiation were identified with respect to the translation of culture-loaded items, both in the lexical choices and in the translational strategies selected by the (re)translators, it proved much more difficult to trace instances of dissidence. It was not something unexpected, which confirms my belief that further research needs to be undertaken with respect to clues that prove the existence of such relationships of IR.

While, as predicted, (re)translators seem uninclined to mediate culture-specific items for the target readers, by resorting to very few instances of intra- or extra-textual explicitation, the second target text (the one I dubbed "the communist version") resorted to sporadic footnotes and domestication. However, a comparison with the other target texts did not confirm my prediction that TT2 would prove to be the most influential target text of the lot, although this was the case with other retranslations of English classics into Romanian.

Most target texts proved to be inconsistent with respect to the translation of terms related to table manners such as *dinner* or *to dine*, which can be explained by the fact that food-related terminology was undergoing a period of transition at the time Jane Austen wrote her novels. These inconsistencies

indicate that the (re)translators, especially the later ones, might have been remiss in their duties and dismissed important details in the history of table manners during the Regency.

Notes

[1] See the seminal text of Evan Zohar (1990) for a theory of the polysystem in translation.

[2] The subgenre of regency romances started with Georgette Heyer's novels.

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